

**INDUSTRIAL MANAGEMENT OF HAZARDOUS
MATERIALS IN PLASTICS FROM WEEE**

CECILIA CHAINE

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ABSTRACT

Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) is globally the fastest-growing waste stream, demanding the development of effective management, treatment, and disposal strategies due to its hazardous nature and economic value. Understanding WEEE generation and management is challenging as comprehensive data on both formally and informally generated and recovered quantities are scarce. Such information is crucial for identifying trends, supporting policy implementation, and preventing inadequate management, thereby promoting reuse and enhancing recycling efforts.

Plastics constitute approximately 21 wt.% of WEEE and often contain persistent and hazardous compounds like brominated flame retardants (BFRs) and antimony trioxide (Sb_2O_3). The presence of these additives challenges WEEE plastics management, as improper treatment can lead to severe environmental pollution and health risks. Disparities in economic development and regulatory frameworks between countries intensify these issues with developed nations typically having stricter regulations and better resources for managing WEEE, while developing countries struggle with implementing effective practices.

Identifying these hazardous compounds in plastics is technically and economically demanding, promoting the development of practical alternatives like X-ray fluorescence (XRF), which is rapid, effective, and non-destructive. This research focuses on waste Flat Panel Display (wFPD) equipment, as the category with highest BFR content among WEEE.

An initial evaluation of the global context highlighted stringent legislative requirements imposing strict BFR thresholds, resulting in large amounts of plastic being unsuitable for recycling. Identifying breaches in regulatory and management frameworks emphasizes the need for enhanced international collaboration and knowledge exchange. To address these regulatory and management challenges and to promote knowledge development through collaborative efforts, one of the main aims of this research was focused on advancing effective BFR and Sb_2O_3 detection and quantification methods.

Thus, a fast and robust technique for detecting hazardous components in WEEE plastics was developed and validated. The assessment showed that the presence of dust in items being screened has minimal impact on the accuracy of Br and Sb concentration measurements, ensuring the reliability of handheld XRF (h-XRF) analysis under varied assessment conditions. Optimal analysis conditions were established for WEEE plastics recycling, with a 10-second counting time achieving high accuracy within specified concentration ranges and acceptable throughput for industrial-scale implementation. Consistent patterns in Br and Sb distribution within wFPD casings indicated that analysing the centre area of the rear casing is appropriate for effective sorting, with consistency rates exceeding 95% therefore minimising the risk of false negatives.

Applying this validated h-XRF method, the characteristics of WEEE plastics were defined and management approaches were assessed for Europe and Latin America using Scotland and Uruguay as a case study of differing regulatory environments. Results highlight the disproportionately high amounts of EEE with hazardous materials in the Uruguayan market with lower regulatory control, illustrating the impacts of the lack of global regulations and differences between individual countries on international trade and safety harmonization.

Furthermore, detailed characterisation of wFPD plastics from items managed in Scotland was completed. The study revealed technological trends and material evolution in FPD equipment, showing that LCDs have a notably longer lifespan than LEDs. The types of polymers used remain largely consistent, with HIPS (High Impact Polystyrene) and PC/ABS (Polycarbonate/ Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene) being predominant, and approximately 70% of materials being recyclable with bromine concentrations below 830 mg/kg. The creation of this extensive database allowed for the development of predictive classification models using binary logistic regression and the Random Forest algorithm. The results indicated significant limitations in the statistical parameters of the logistic regression model, while the Random Forest algorithm improved classification precision for recyclable items to over 80% but underperformed by overclassifying non-recyclable samples, likely due to dataset imbalances. The significance of this work lies in the fact that the model developed could be applied to estimate the volumes of recyclable and non-recyclable plastic inputs, providing waste managers with valuable insights into potential revenues, infrastructure needs, and variability of recovered materials over time. Furthermore, to the best of the author's knowledge, there is no prior approach to the design of a predictive classification model for FPD plastics, considering the characteristics of these materials which have not yet been exhaustively described in full.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABS	Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene
ABS+PMMA	Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene + Polymethyl Methacrylate
BFR	Brominated Flame Retardant
CP	Consumer Product
CRM	Certified Reference Material
CRT	Cathode Ray Tube equipment
EEE	Electrical and Electronic Equipment
FCA	Food Contact Article
FPD	Flat Panel Display equipment
FR	Flame Retardant
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared
GC/MS	Gas Chromatography coupled with Mass Spectrometry
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HBCDD	Hexabromocyclododecane
HIPS	High Impact Polystyrene
h-XRF	Handheld XRF
ICP/OES	Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission spectroscopy
LCD	Liquid Crystal Display equipment
LED	Light Emitting Diodes equipment
NBFR	Novel Brominated Flame Retardant
PBDE	Polybrominated diphenyl ethers
PC+ABS	Polycarbonate + Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene
POP	Persistent Organic Pollutant
PPE	Polyphenyl Ether
PS+PPE	Polystyrene + Polyphenyl Ether
TBBP-A	Tetrabromobisphenol A
WEEE	Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment
wFPD	Waste Flat Panel Display equipment
XRF	X-Ray Fluorescence
YoM	Year of Manufacture

CHAPTER 1 Introduction

1.1 WASTE ELECTRICAL AND ELECTRONIC EQUIPMENT

In (Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE)), the European Union (EU) has defined Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment as ‘electrical or electronic equipment which is waste within the meaning of Article 3(1) of Directive 2008/98/EC¹, including all components, sub-assemblies and consumables which are part of the product at the time of discarding’. The Directive further defines Electrical and Electronic Equipment (EEE) as ‘equipment which is dependent on electric currents or electromagnetic fields in order to work properly and equipment for the generation, transfer and measurement of such currents and fields and designed for use with a voltage rating not exceeding 1,000 volts for alternating current and 1,500 volts for direct current’.

The EU WEEE Directive provides the classification for WEEE. Initially, it outlined 10 categories, which were applicable until 2018. Since August 2018 according to Annex III of the EU WEEE Directive, EEE have been classified into six categories as described in **Figure 1.1**.

Figure 1.1. WEEE categories and kg/person generated in the European Union. Source: (Meskers, Worrell and Reuter, 2023)

After the United Kingdom formally left the EU, the provisions of the WEEE Directive were retained in UK law under the European Union (Withdrawal) Act 2018 which ensured that there was no

¹ ‘waste’ means any substance or object which the holder discards or intends or is required to discard

immediate gap when the UK left the EU. Thus, in the UK the same categorization applied since January 2019. In January 2021 (end of the transition period) the Directive was updated to include minor amendments, which did not have an impact on compliance requirements and mechanisms.

EEE have rapidly evolved in functionality and use of raw materials. In the 1980s, a typical phone contained about 12 different chemical elements, but modern smartphones use over 60. Additionally, the complex material mix, mechanical properties, polymer composition, and chemical composition of WEEE vary not only between different types of equipment but also among individual appliances within the same type (Meskers, Worrell and Reuter, 2023). Consequently, each WEEE category is highly heterogeneous and subject to change over time. The increased variability of compounds used that are complexly bound for functional purposes, determines the physical and chemical properties of materials available for recycling. Thus, effective recycling requires a product-centric approach rather than a material-centric one.

EEE have become essential in modern society, playing a key role in simplifying daily tasks, enhancing comfort, and adding luxury to our lives. This equipment has a set of associated features including short lifespans, rapid changes in technologies and limited repair options for reuse, which result in steadily increasing volumes of waste of EEE being generated mainly in developed countries. In 2024 The Global E-Waste Monitor (Baldé *et al.*, 2024) reported a record of 62Mt of WEEE generated globally in 2022, of which only 22.2% were collected through a formal system.

The highest per capita volumes are generated in Europe (17.6 kg per capita) and Oceania (16.1 kg per capita), however, in the cumulative per continent the trend changes with the Americas and Asia being the largest generators with 14Mt and 30Mt per year, respectively (Baldé *et al.*, 2024). Despite the breach in generation between different areas of the World, WEEE management is currently a matter of global concern. This is because, promoted by the valuable extractable resources found in WEEE, a high proportion of these wastes are managed outside formal collection and recycling schemes with high volumes being illegally exported to Africa and Asia where they are treated by informal workers under inappropriate conditions from environmental, health and safety points of view (Baldé *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, effectively collecting, managing and disposing of this waste is central to sustainable practices, reducing negative impacts, and maximizing its overall value.

In 2019, the estimated recoverable value of materials from WEEE reached a staggering USD 57 billion (WEEE Forum, 2021). While this figure may appear substantial, it aligns logically with the inherent value of electronic devices; for instance, smartphones contain approximately 100 times more gold than a tonne of gold ore, rendering them a rich source of this precious metal. Furthermore, a report from 2022 (Moore, 2022) underscores this economic potential, suggesting that unused mobile phones in the UK could yield over £3 billion. This indicates the significant amount of untapped material resources present in unused electronics, highlighting the imperative of enhancing collection and recycling efforts to mitigate the need for extracting new materials for manufacturing purposes.

The initial stage of WEEE management is collection. In 2014 the global generation of WEEE amounted to 41.8 million s, with only 7.5 million s formally recovered and recycled, representing a recycling rate of 17.9%. By 2019, the volume of WEEE generated increased to 56.3 million s, accompanied by a rise in recycled volumes to 9.3 million s. However, despite the increase in recycled volumes, the recycling percentage experienced a slight decline. These figures, although abstract, evidence the disparity between worldwide recycling efforts and global growth rates. This discrepancy is closely linked to collection practices. In 2019, a substantial portion of the generated WEEE, approximately 83.5% of the total weight, likely evaded formal collection, thereby escaping environmentally responsible management (Forti *et al.*, 2020). Research has shown that one of the paths by-passing formal collection systems are higher-income households where small electronic devices may be disposed of in regular waste bins and subsequently incorporated into municipal solid waste streams. As these items are not subjected to proper recycling processes, valuable materials are lost. The same issue arises in developing countries where despite the households' income level, due to the lack of formal collection systems, WEEE are discarded with mixed waste.

Inadequate documentation and inconsistent reporting of flow data contribute to a lack of transparency regarding the actual volumes of WEEE managed and the subsequent handling procedures. The absence of data on formally collected and recycled WEEE implies that significant volumes are managed outside official collection channels.

Moreover, the absence of comprehensive data and statistics regarding the quantities of WEEE generated represents another significant obstacle. Effective measurement and monitoring of quantities at both national and global levels are imperative for addressing the WEEE issue. Accurate measurements and data facilitate trend tracking, inform policy and regulatory implementations, prevent informal trading and improper handling, promote recycling, and strengthen the reuse and recycling industry (Azizi, Hanafiah and Woon, 2023).

While statistics on WEEE are generally limited across most countries, transparency and standardization are more prevalent in European nations, where such information is readily available and accessible. Substantial disparities persist between developed and developing nations regarding the monitoring and control of national-level WEEE stocks and movements.

1.1.1 Materials in WEEE

WEEE contain various materials including steel, iron, plastics, non-ferrous metals, glass, wood, plywood, printed circuit boards, concrete, ceramics, and rubber, among others. In general, iron and steel constitute approximately 47 wt.%, plastics around 21 wt.%, copper about 7 wt.%, glass approximately 5 wt.%, with the remaining portion comprising various other substances (Zeng, Mathews and Li, 2018). This characterization varies between categories and in many cases from

device to device. The non-ferrous metals fraction includes precious materials such as gold, platinum, palladium, silver, and rare earth elements.

These high demand materials make WEEE economically attractive to both informal and formal recyclers, as they serve as viable secondary source as the concentration of these economically vital metals within WEEE can exceed that of natural ores by several orders of magnitude (Kaur, Kaur and Kaur, 2023). Consequently, WEEE stands out as a profitable source for recovering valuable materials, with relevant opportunities and motivations for efficient handling and recycling practices.

As of 2017, the estimated global value and reserves of waste materials within WEEE are as follows: 16,500 kt of iron/steel (worth 9 billion Euros), 1900 kt of copper (valued at 10.6 billion Euros), 220 kt of aluminium (equating to 3.2 billion Euros), 0.3 kt of gold (amounting to 10.4 billion Euros), 1.0 kt of silver (adding to 0.58 billion Euros), and 8600 kt of plastics (estimated at 12.3 billion Euros) (Liu *et al.*, 2023). The recycling cost of metal extracted from WEEE is significantly lower than that of mining crude ore (Hagelüken and Goldmann, 2022). This underscores the energy-saving and environmentally friendly nature of recycling these wastes.

The primary economic force behind WEEE recycling is metal recovery, with different techniques being currently used for the extraction of valuable metals. Among these, pyrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy, and biohydrometallurgy are the most widely applied, with the former two having the highest TRLs (Technology Readiness Level) being industrially scaled processes (Chaine, Hursthouse and Van Hullebusch, 2024).

Non-metallic materials like engineering plastics and glass fibres also hold considerable value for secondary use (Kaya, 2019). In WEEE, the most frequently found plastics include polymers such as ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene), HIPS (High Impact Polystyrene), PC+ABS (Polycarbonate + Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene) and PPE (Polyphenyl Ether) (Goosey, 2012). As a consequence of this diversity, sorting plastic is complex, resulting in low recycling rates with estimates suggesting that between 40-50% of recovered volumes are not being adequately recycled (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2020). Adding to this challenge is the presence of certain additives, which, if not treated properly, may be released from the polymer matrix as primary pollutants (Skjevraak *et al.*, 2003; Kim, Osako and Sakai, 2006) or function as catalysts for a variety of different dioxins and furans and therefore have a significant impact on health and the environment as secondary pollutants (Weber, 2003).

Recycling of the non-metallic fraction, mainly plastics, holds second highest recycling value. A wide range of techniques are used for their valorisation and recycling including mechanical, chemical and waste-to-energy processes. In mechanical recycling, plastics preserve their physical and chemical properties, while it is common to improve the physical characteristics of the material by adding plasticizers, polymer modifiers, fillers, and other additives. On the other hand, through thermo-

chemical recycling like pyrolysis, gasification, or hydrothermal liquefaction, it is possible to obtain the building blocks of the polymer (i.e., Naphtha) allowing to go back to the feedstock components for plastics production (Das *et al.*, 2021; Mtibe, Mokhena and John, 2023). Finally, incineration for exploiting the high calorific power of this material is a common practice; however, it is important to consider it does not allow for recovery of material and in many cases operating conditions are not sufficient to ensure gas emissions are adequate (free of dioxins and furans).

WEEE generated in high-income countries (mainly European and North American), where disposal costs are relatively low and environmental regulations are stringent, is frequently illegally shipped to low- and middle-income countries like China, India, Ghana, and Nigeria for recycling. This illegal trade is based on non-compliance with the rules defined in the Basel Convention, which restricts the transboundary movement of hazardous waste, such as WEEE, to prevent environmental damage in developing countries. Shipments are often mislabelled as 'second-hand goods' or 'reusable electronics' to evade customs inspections, despite containing hazardous materials that pose significant health and environmental risks in importing countries. However, the industrial infrastructure and recycling practices in these countries often operate informally, with workers resorting to unsafe methods to extract valuables. This results in adverse and irreversible impacts on local, regional, and even global ecological environments (Forti *et al.*, 2020). Heavy metals including lead, mercury, and cadmium, along with persistent organics pollutants (POPs) such as polychlorinated biphenyls and certain brominated flame retardants, pose significant threats if WEEE is not adequately treated. Thus, illegal handling of such hazardous substances can lead to severe environmental and human health repercussions globally.

Given the immense volume and rapid growth rate of WEEE, it is imperative to recognize the impacts and potential hazards associated with its recycling and the pressing need for discussion on sustainable WEEE management and recycling technologies to formulate comprehensive solutions.

1.1.2 Flame retardant plastic

WEEE plastics, such as those from display equipment housing, printed circuit boards and cable insulation among other, contain hazardous and persistent compounds such as flame retardants (FRs). When products containing flame retardants reach the end of their usable lifespan, they are typically subjected to recycling, incineration, or disposal in landfills. Recycling procedures have the potential to inadvertently introduce contamination to workers and communities residing near recycling facilities, as well as to newly processed materials, through the presence of halogenated flame retardants and their degradation products. For instance, the melting of WEEE, vehicles, and other products for the recovery of their metal components can lead to the production of toxic dioxins and furans due to elevated temperatures (BSEF, 2024).

From a materials point of view, FRs may alter the physical properties of plastics (i.e., hardness, tensile strength, impact resistance, chemical resistance), resulting in suboptimal performance of recycled products. Furthermore, the incineration of such materials similarly leads to the generation and release of substantial quantities of toxic degradation products. On the other hand, controlled incineration of materials containing halogenated flame retardants, despite its associated costs, substantially mitigates the release of toxic by-products (Matsukami *et al.*, 2014; Ma *et al.*, 2022). Thus, the presence of FRs in polymers can be detrimental to the recycling of materials inhibiting progression towards a circular economy (Bifulco *et al.*, 2024). It is estimated that 9% of the total volume of WEEE plastics generated per year (234 kt/year) contain halogenated FRs of which only a small fraction corresponds to restricted BFRs such as octa-BDE or decaBDE.

Another potentially hazardous additive commonly found in WEEE plastics used as a synergist to certain BFRs is Sb_2O_3 (antimony trioxide). The Basel Convention establishes criteria for classifying waste as hazardous based on its chemical composition and potential environmental and health impacts. Specifically, antimony and its compounds are listed in Annex I of the Convention as waste to be controlled due to their toxicological properties. Because of constraints imposed on the use of restricted BFRs, concentrations are rapidly and steadily decreasing (octa-BDE use was restricted in 2003 and decaBDE in 2008, in the EU) and consequently so are those of Sb_2O_3 . However, given that EEE is estimated to have a useful life of approximately 12-15 years, EEE containing these compounds are still being disposed of. (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2020)

In developing countries, it is common to dispose of a multitude of products containing halogenated flame retardants in landfills. As previously mentioned, this is associated with the lack of separate waste collection and treatment infrastructure which results in items being disposed of with domestic waste regardless of their category. In certain countries, BFRs have been observed to leach out of landfills, thus the design of landfills must account for the capture of leachate, requiring subsequent treatment. However, it is imperative to acknowledge that these landfill designs are susceptible to degradation over time (Kim, Osako and Sakai, 2006; Kajiwara *et al.*, 2014; Stubbings and Harrad, 2014; Cristale *et al.*, 2019).

1.1.3 Sorting

In the EU and the UK, regulatory requirements are in place for the classification and management of materials containing POPs (Regulation EU 2019/1021) and/or Sb_2O_3 (Regulation EC 1272/2008). The WEEE management sector faces the challenge of managing plastics in an environmentally sound and legally compliant manner, while minimising the negative impact on business profitability. In order to improve the efficiency of plastic sorting processes and its recycling rates, it is necessary to develop techniques and methods by which recyclable and non-recyclable plastics are reliably identified and separated, ensuring the correct management of the hazardous fraction.

Different techniques have been studied for the characterisation of BFRs and Sb_2O_3 in WEEE plastics. For measuring BFRs, reliable methods include gas chromatography with electron capture detection or mass spectrometry as well as liquid chromatography with different coupled detectors (Aldrian, Ledersteger and Pomberger, 2015; Zhan *et al.*, 2019; Strobl *et al.*, 2021; Yli-Rantala *et al.*, 2021). On the other hand, the method generally used for the determination of Sb_2O_3 is the analysis by Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP/OES) after chemical extraction of Sb from the matrix (Stenvall *et al.*, 2013; Puype *et al.*, 2015; Gazzellone, 2018; Alassali, Abis, *et al.*, 2019). Considering this compound as the only source of Sb present in WEEE plastics, all the Sb measured is attributed to it.

These conventional methods to determine compliance regulation are technically and economically demanding, with analysis times incompatible with the throughput required at industrial level. For this reason, during the past decade research has increasingly focused on more practical alternatives such X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) as a fast, non-destructive and effective technique, by which it is possible to rapidly determine total concentrations of Br and Sb as tracers of BFRs and Sb_2O_3 , respectively (Sharkey, 2019; Alghamdi, Abdallah and Harrad, 2022).

Other potentially viable techniques include FTIR spectroscopy (Fourier-Transform Infrared, DART-HRMS (Direct Analysis in Real Time – High Resolution Mass Spectrometry), Raman spectroscopy, LIBS (Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy) and HSI (Hyperspectral Imaging). These will be discussed in more depth in **CHAPTER 2**.

1.2 RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

Worldwide, WEEE management presents significant impacts both positive and negative, requiring a comprehensive understanding of its generation and management. Disparities between countries associated with contrasting economic development and regulatory frameworks, accentuate these impacts. Bridging these gaps requires tailored strategies that consider the unique contexts of each country, emphasizing equitable access to resources and technologies for sustainable WEEE management.

Among the challenges posed by WEEE, the presence of BFRs stands out. The global regulatory and economic frameworks, demand for the development and application of cost-effective methods for the identification and sorting of WEEE plastics.

Current efforts are focused on the application of spectrophotometric techniques (XRF, X-Ray Transmission) or the sink and float method, for recovering the recyclable from the non-recyclable fraction of WEEE plastics. In all cases, previously shredded plastics are treated, which adds to pre-processing time and costs. Extensive research has been conducted on the application of handheld XRF (h-XRF), however, the results presented do not evaluate the potential of the methodology for its industrial use or are not specifically applicable to all WEEE streams. Assessed matrixes include

varied mixes of plastics from different products (Taurino *et al.*, 2014; Harrad, Drage, M. A.-E. Abdallah, *et al.*, 2019), low number of samples (Guzzonato, Puype and Harrad, 2016; Alassali, Abis, *et al.*, 2019; Jandric *et al.*, 2020; Kousaiti *et al.*, 2020; Strobl *et al.*, 2021; Drage *et al.*, 2022) and in many cases samples collected after shredding (Hennebert, 2020) or recycling (W.A. Stubbings *et al.*, 2021). It is still necessary to evaluate its application on a larger scale in order to meet industry processing requirements. The development and implementation of a validated method for the analysis of whole WEEE plastic casings, using spectrophotometric techniques such as h-XRF, can significantly improve the efficiency of sorting the recyclable fraction of plastics on an industrial scale by minimising the pre-processing times and costs associated with shredding. It is postulated that, by developing an approach that is both technically feasible and economically viable, and that is adapted to the manual disassembly processes in traditional recycling plants, more accurate and efficient sorting will be achieved, thus meeting the processing requirements of industry and optimising resource recovery in the handling of WEEE.

On the other hand, characterising the managed material by collecting revealing information on each item (i.e., type of polymer, year of manufacture, manufacturer, type of device, size, origin, and Br and Sb content), it could be possible to establish a model that provides clarity on the composition of the waste and therefore allows recyclers to define strategies and technology required to optimize its management from an economic, environmental, and social point of view.

International collaboration and knowledge sharing in the management of plastics from WEEE has the potential to significantly improve the capacity of countries to manage this waste in a sustainable manner, facilitating the adoption of cost-effective and environmentally sound practices. Furthermore, by assessing and understanding the disparities in the quality of plastics used in different countries, specific challenges could be identified and effective interventions developed to optimise WEEE plastics management strategies, increasing recycling efficiency and mitigating associated environmental risks.

In conclusion, addressing the complex challenges of WEEE management requires a multifaceted approach that integrates technical, regulatory, economic, and social dimensions. By identifying and mitigating environmental and health risks, promoting technological innovation, assessing regulatory frameworks, and promoting international cooperation, a more sustainable and equitable future for WEEE plastics management can be achieved.

1.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The aim of this research is to determine and evaluate the characteristics and management of WEEE plastics to identify the potential for reducing the current associated health and environmental impacts. For this, FPD casings were the targeted category due to its reported significant BFR content,

considering and comparing legal, geographical, social, and economic frameworks as well as operational infrastructure in different case study locations.

Objectives are presented below:

- I. Assess current management practices and treatment of WEEE plastics containing BFRs considering regulations/legislation in force and examining the health and environmental impacts of BFRs in WEEE plastics treatment, as well as potential sources of exposure to these compounds.
- II. Develop fast and robust h-XRF technique for hazardous components of WEEE plastics
- III. Evaluate the effects of different regulatory environments on WEEE plastics management.
- IV. Application of data science to WEEE plastics recycling by developing a comprehensive database that provides statistically validated data for characterizing FPD plastic casings, focusing on total Br and Sb concentrations, polymer types, and other relevant features.
- V. Generate predictive models to classify FPD plastic waste.
- VI. Validate the applicability and robustness of the best-performing model in an international context, using a case study in Spain.
- VII. Develop recommendations to improve the sustainable management of WEEE plastics by integrating insights from regulatory assessments, health and environmental impact evaluations, and data-driven classification models.

These aims and objectives were achieved through a programme of work in the framework of a KTP Project (Knowledge Transfer Partnership) between the University of the West of Scotland and RESTRUCTA LTD. Research was based on the application of h-XRF for the classification of FPD plastics into recyclable and non-recyclable according to their Br and Sb concentrations as tracers of BFRs, while also determining and evaluating the characteristics and management of WEEE plastics to identify opportunities for reducing associated health and environmental impacts. Through case studies in Scotland and Uruguay, this research compares material recovery processes and operational infrastructures to assess specific challenges faced by WEEE recyclers. Furthermore, predictive models were developed using binary logistic regression and Random Forest aimed at classifying FPD plastic waste by type and recyclability. These were validated with data from Spain to ensure robustness and generalizability. The results are intended to support industry, policymakers, and recyclers in reducing environmental and health risks associated with WEEE plastics while maximizing resource recovery and operational efficiency.

1.4 RESEARCH SIGNIFICANCE

In Scotland, WEEE regulation places take-back obligation on retailers and other distributors who sell EEE, and collection is conducted via collection points, producers and retailers or through dedicated pick-up arrangements. Items of WEEE collected are transported to specialised treatment

facilities, where they are treated for the recovery of valuable materials in an environmentally controlled manner.

This project was centrally based on a case study carried out throughout 2021-2022 at RESTRUCTA LTD, the main FPD equipment recycling company in Scotland, located in Irvine, UK. Unlike other WEEE recycling companies in the UK, RESTRUCTA LTD operates with traditional manual dismantling processes, allowing for a more exhaustive material extraction.

Of the materials recovered from the dismantling process, 13% in weight corresponds to plastic casings which have been subject of new regulation in recent years. Changes in regulation regarding POPs put in place by both the Environmental Agency (EA) in England and Wales and guidance released by the Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA) in Scotland had a negative effect on the profitability of the company as management costs of this material increased. Therefore, this work is strategic to the WEEE plastics recycling business as developing a robust, validated and efficient technique for rapid sorting of plastic in-situ is key to improve plastics processing while complying with legal requirement.

Regarding the regulatory framework in Scotland at the time of the study, the last communication from SEPA regarding WEEE POPs/HAZARDOUS plastics management was sent out to WEEE recyclers in December 2020. Since then, a series of meetings took place with the different stakeholders involved in WEEE management in both Scotland and England to define the requirements to be included in the forthcoming regulation. While SEPA has not yet communicated the definitive version of this document, it is the industry's understanding that the requirements that will apply will be the same as those currently implemented by the EA in England and Wales. By characterising plastics from display equipment this project aims to gather and potentially provide useful information to policy makers for its consideration for guidance development, adapting requirements and validating management options.

Such characterisation will provide valuable and detailed information on equipment managed in Scotland, including information on polymers and substances, makes, years of manufacture and origin among other. The methodology for the generation of this database, and the database itself, can be replicated in other models and used to understand the differences and similarities in WEEE management according to the geopolitical, economic, and environmental context between two or more countries.

Another relevant aspect to consider on the management of WEEE, is its diversity and disparity around the world, ranging from countries where collection systems are well defined, regulated and implemented, to countries where there is no legislation, control, or system in place to cover this particular waste stream. Considering this, the opportunity was sought to collaborate with the Environment Ministry and a WEEE recycling company in Uruguay were regulation and management

of WEEE have yet not been defined. Furthermore, Uruguay was selected based on its demographic characteristics, specifically population density (inhabitants per km²), and because it was the only country within an international capacity-building project on WEEE management (PREAL project) that opted not to adopt h-XRF technology for plastics sorting. This allowed to compare and contrast the impact of regulation on materials being generated as WEEE as well as management options and their potential consequences.

Furthermore, combining the data gathered on the characterisation of the material with programming tools to produce a predictive classification model for wFPD plastics generation, would be highly valuable due to its potential to inform and optimize waste management strategies. By providing insights into the composition of waste generated, such a model would enable the development of real and efficient management plans tailored to specific needs and contexts. In addition, the lack of reliable information on WEEE generation and the characterization of WEEE plastics poses challenges to waste management and material recovery efforts, thus by addressing these gaps, a predictive model can enhance decision-making processes and improve the performance of sorting methodologies. Ultimately, the development of such a model could contribute to the optimization of infrastructure, resource allocation, and waste management practices, ensuring more sustainable and environmentally responsible outcomes where applicable. Different locations will be considered to assess its validity and applicability.

Overall, the research project serves as a catalyst for innovation and improvement in WEEE management practices, with the potential to drive positive environmental, economic, and social outcomes both locally and globally. Through its comprehensive approach and collaborative efforts, the research aims to promote sustainable solutions to the complex challenges associated with WEEE plastics management, ultimately benefiting stakeholders across various sectors and regions.

1.5 THESIS STRUCTURE

This thesis comprises six chapters, outlined as follows:

Chapter 1: Introduction. Provides an overview on Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment management and the research study. Flame Retardants potentially as hazardous components of WEEE plastics are presented as well as commonly used sorting techniques and related challenges for the industry, environmental and public health. The research objectives are defined providing a comprehensive description of the relevance of the study outlining the scope of the research and the tasks carried out to complete it.

Chapter 2: Literature Review. Discusses a comprehensive range of different aspects related to the management of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment plastics including the current legal framework, by region and country. Furthermore, this section includes and identification of the most relevant methodologies within present industrial processes for the determination of Brominated

Flame Retardants and the related challenges. The predominance of BFRs and their potential substitution by Novel Brominated Flame Retardants is reviewed with emphasis placed on discussing the health and environmental impacts associated with the presence of BFRs and novel BFRs in waste, consumer products, and WEEE recycling facilities. Noteworthy knowledge and research gaps in this field are highlighted. Lastly, a discussion on current trends and proposed strategies to address this critical issue is provided.

Publication: Chaine C, Hursthouse AS, McLean B, McLellan I, McMahon B, McNulty J, Miller J, Viza E. Recycling Plastics from WEEE: A Review of the Environmental and Human Health Challenges Associated with Brominated Flame Retardants. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. **2022** Jan 11;19(2):766. (<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19020766>)

Chapter 3: “Optimized industrial sorting of WEEE plastics: development of fast and robust h-XRF technique for hazardous components”. This chapter presents a study examining plastic casings of flat panel display equipment using handheld X-ray fluorescence to detect bromine and antimony as indicators of Brominated Flame Retardants and Sb_2O_3 additive, respectively. This chapter focuses on the development and validation of an analysis methodology to establish optimal analysis conditions for efficient large-scale processing. A ring trial involving 100 samples conducted to assess measurement validity is included.

Publication: Chaine, C.; Hursthouse, A.S.; Jandric, A.; McLean, B.; McLellan, I.; McMahon, B.; McNulty, J.; Miller, J.; Salhofer, S.; Viza, E. Optimized Industrial Sorting of WEEE Plastics: Development of Fast and Robust h-XRF Technique for Hazardous Components. *Case Stud. Chem. Environ. Eng.* 2023, 7, 100292. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscee.2022.100292>)

Chapter 4: “The challenge of plastics management for WEEE recycling in the global south: A case comparison between Europe and Latin America”. This chapter covers a baseline study conducted to evaluate WEEE plastics in Scotland and Uruguay. By application of the developed method described in Chapter 3, the section discusses the presence of Brominated Flame Retardants in WEEE plastics across two different processing operations, both conducting manual dismantling of FPD equipment. Furthermore, a focus was placed on assessing the impact of developed and emerging regulatory systems on the quality of recovered WEEE plastics and available management infrastructures. Recommendations on future actions for policymakers to adopt a more sustainable regulatory are included.

Publication: Chaine, C.; Hursthouse, A.S.; McLellan, I.; Viza, E.; Miller, J. The Challenge of Plastic Management for Waste Electrical and Electric Equipment Recycling in the Global South: A Case Comparison between Europe and Latin America. *Recycling* **2023**, *8*, 71. (<https://doi.org/10.3390/recycling8050071>)

Chapter 5: Characterization and statistical binary logistic regression for modelling WEEE plastics. This chapter presents a comprehensive characterization of Flat Panel Display casings plastics, examining the following variables: type (LCD/LED), size, manufacturer, year of manufacture, origin, polymer, and category (RECYCLABLE/NON-RECYCLABLE). Utilizing this dataset, a statistical analysis by binary logistic regression was conducted to explore the relationships between these variables and assess the feasibility of developing a predictive model for the material.

Chapter 6: Cracking the code: improving WEEE plastics modelling using Python

Building on the results obtained from applying binary logistic regression to WEEE plastics modelling, this chapter examines the effectiveness of computer programming and modelling tools. Specifically, the implementation of the Random Forest algorithm in Python for machine learning and data analysis was evaluated to create a categorization model for predicting recyclable and non-recyclable plastics in the FPD plastics stream using the least necessary information. The model was validated through its application to WEEE plastics generated in Spain.

Chapter 7: Conclusions and recommendations for future action. This chapter comprises an exhaustive compilation of relevant findings and recommendations for future research actions on WEEE plastics managements in developed and developing countries. The main findings include the identification of environmental and public health risks associated with the presence of BFRs in WEEE plastics, the impact of regulation on the quality and recyclability of such materials, and the determination of optimal operating conditions for plastic segregation using h-XRF and the characterization and modelling of FPD plastic waste. Recommendations are based on the results obtained and conclusions of the different studies carried out. These recommendations are based on knowledge gaps and needs identified of both industry and policy makers, with a focus on the optimization of WEEE plastics management.

Figure 1.2 illustrates a diagram including the research gaps identified and the corresponding objectives associated with the chapters of this thesis where the outcomes are presented.

Figure 1.2 Thesis organization diagram

CHAPTER 2 Recycling Plastics from WEEE: A Review of the Environmental and Human Health Challenges Associated with Brominated Flame Retardants

This chapter is an accepted manuscript version of the below cited article:

Chaine C, Hursthouse AS, McLean B, McLellan I, McMahon B, McNulty J, Miller J, Viza E. **Recycling Plastics from WEEE: A Review of the Environmental and Human Health Challenges Associated with Brominated Flame Retardants**. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022 Jan 11;19(2):766. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19020766>

2.1 ABSTRACT

Waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) presents the dual characteristic of containing both hazardous substances and valuable recoverable materials. Mainly found in WEEE plastics, brominated flame retardants (BFRs) are a component of particular interest. Several actions have been taken worldwide to regulate their use and disposal, however, in countries where no regulation is in place, the recovery of highly valuable materials has promoted the development of informal treatment facilities, with serious consequences for the environment and the health of the workers and communities involved. Hence, in this review we examine a wide spectrum of aspects related to WEEE plastic management. A search of legislation and the literature was made to determine the current legal framework by region/country. Additionally, we focused on identifying the most relevant methods of existing industrial processes for determining BFRs and their challenges. BFR occurrence and substitution by novel BFRs (NBFRs) was reviewed. An emphasis was given to review the health and environmental impacts associated with BFR/NBFR presence in waste, consumer products, and WEEE recycling facilities. Knowledge and research gaps of this topic were highlighted. Finally, the discussion on current trends and proposals to attend to this relevant issue were outlined.

Keywords: WEEE; brominated flame retardants (BFR); electrical and electronic equipment; waste; WEEE plastics

2.2 INTRODUCTION

Whether it is to facilitate daily activities, provide comfort, or luxury, electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) have become an essential part of most activities carried out in modern societies. From the use of refrigerators and washing machines, to televisions, mobile phones, and computers, EEE dominates our daily lives. This equipment has a set of associated features, including short lifespans, rapid changes in technologies, and limited repair options for reuse, which result in steadily increasing volumes of waste EEE being generated, mainly in developed countries. Worldwide, generated volumes went from 41.8 Mt in 2014 to 53.6 Mt in 2019, and with a projected annual growth rate of 2 Mt, volumes could reach 74.7 Mt in 2030 (Ahirwar and Tripathi, 2021).²

In Directive 2012/19/EU, the European Union has defined the waste of electrical or electronic equipment (WEEE) as electrical or electronic equipment that is waste within the meaning of Article 3 (1) of Directive 2008/98/EC, including all components, sub-assemblies and consumables which are part of the product at the time of discarding. The directive further defines “electrical and electronic equipment” or “EEE” as equipment which is dependent on electric currents or electromagnetic fields in order to work properly and equipment for the generation, transfer, and measurement of such currents and fields and designed for use with a voltage rating not exceeding 1000 volts for alternating current and 1500 volts for direct current (*Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) Text with EEA relevance.*, 2012).

This equipment contains hazardous components, making WEEE a hazardous waste, and even though highest per capita volumes are generated in Europe and Oceania (16.2 and 16.1 kg per capita, respectively (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2020), their management is currently a matter of global concern. This is because, promoted by the valuable extractable resources found in WEEE, a high proportion of these wastes are illegally exported to Africa and Asia where they are treated by informal workers under inappropriate conditions from environmental, health, and safety points of view. Consequently, the proper handling, treatment, and disposal of WEEE is the key to achieving its sustainable management, minimizing their potential adverse health and environmental effects, and maximizing their value.

Materials found in WEEE mainly include ferrous and non-ferrous metals, glass, and plastics, the latter accounting for approximately 30% of all WEEE volume in weight generated per year (Goosey and Goosey, 2019). Furthermore, different types of EEE contain different types of plastics, with acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polypropylene (PP), high impact polystyrene (HIPS), and polycarbonate (PC)/ABS blends the most frequently found. Other types of polymers found in WEEE are PU (polyurethane), PE (polyethylene) and PVC (polyvinyl chloride).

² In this paragraph the unit Mt indicates Mt/year

As a result of the challenges associated with the complexity of these plastic mixtures, and the limited existing technologies for their adequate sorting, it is estimated that approximately 40 to 50% of captured plastics in WEEE are not being properly recycled (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2020). Adding to these low recyclability rates is the presence of hazardous components found in WEEE plastics, including potentially toxic elements (i.e., lead, cadmium, mercury) and flame retardants.

The circulation of electric currents, heating of internal components, together with the inherent flammability of most plastics and the widespread use of EEE in households and offices, mandates the addition of flame retardants in order to comply with flammability standards. Flame retardants (FRs) include halogenated compounds (organo-halogen flame retardants) with chlorinated and brominated FRs, amounting to 1% and 55% of global use, respectively, according to reports from 2018 (CERESANA, 2019). Furthermore, flame retardants are commonly used in combination with antimony trioxide (Sb_2O_3) as a synergist with the Sb consumption for this use, accounting for approximately half of its total production (Alassali, Abis, *et al.*, 2019; Alassali, Picuno, *et al.*, 2019).

According to the Basel Convention, Sb-containing waste must be classified as hazardous. In Europe and the UK, waste containing Sb should be classified under various regulations. For instance, the European Chemical Classification, Labelling and Packaging Regulations establish that any waste containing Sb_2O_3 at concentrations higher than 0.1% w/w, is to be classified as hazardous. As Sb_2O_3 is the only Sb compound used as a synergist of halogenated FRs, a total Sb concentration limit of 8,400 mg/kg can be considered, making its determination reasonably straightforward. Therefore, even though its presence represents a challenge in WEEE plastic treatment, Sb exceeds the scope of the pre-sent review, which is focused on the challenges associated with FR presence. It is, however, important to highlight that, to date, no comprehensive systematic and quantitative studies for the characterization of the presence of Sb in WEEE have been carried out.

EEE plastics contain chemicals, such as fillers or additives, so that the items meet technical standards, such as those for flammability for which flame retardants like brominated flame retardants are included. These are synthetic additives with a very high efficiency for retarding flames and are comparatively cheaper than other flame retardants. One of the main reasons behind the low recycling rates of WEEE plastics, is their FR content. The most technically relevant brominated flame retardants (BFRs) are polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA), and hexabromocyclododecane (HBCDD), which due to their characteristics of being additive BFRs and easily leach from the polymeric matrix, were classified as persistent, bio accumulative and toxic to the environment. This will be discussed in more depth in the following sections.

Brominated flame retardants have been long used as additives or reactive FRs since the 1980s in the manufacture of EEE (Freeguard *et al.*, 2005), and although their application has been greatly

reduced since 2009 after being listed and are thus restricted by the Stockholm Convention, they continue to be found in WEEE at high concentrations.

Octa-BDE and deca-BDE are among the most frequently used BFRs in electrical and electronic equipment. Being lipophilic and persistent, these compounds can concentrate in animal fat, having potential harmful effects on human health due to their bioaccumulation, biomagnification, long-range transport potential, and their impact on the activity of certain hormones (Roila *et al.*, 2021).

Although the production of penta- and octa-BDEs has been stopped in many developed countries, the concentrations of penta- and octa-BDEs detected in humans have increased. For example, in Australia, although the import of these BFRs was stopped in 2005, the concentrations reported in humans are higher than those determined in Europe or Asia. However, they do not exceed the human concentrations determined in the United States (Toms *et al.*, 2006).

The most common routes of human exposure to BFRs are through ingestion or in-halation of dust in enclosed spaces or workplaces, and dietary ingestion. As with a variety of other pollutants, exposure to BFRs in the occupational environment can be much higher than environmental exposure. In fact, some of the highest BFR exposures that have been determined were in offices and WEEE recycling facilities (Gravel, Aubin and Labrèche, 2019).

Considering the complexity associated with the proper handling of WEEE plastics, due to the presence of specific chemical compounds, it is essential that we evaluate the potential effects that such hazardous substances may have on human health, which will ultimately allow monitoring and the definition of the toxicity limits of plastics and, thus, establish environmentally safe handling and treatment processes.

Numerous studies have been carried out over the last decade to characterize the toxicity of WEEE plastics, e.g., (Puype *et al.*, 2015; Yu *et al.*, 2017; Drage *et al.*, 2018; Turner, 2018; Jandric *et al.*, 2020; W. A. Stubbings *et al.*, 2021). While these studies have provided valuable information on the composition of WEEE plastics, they do not discuss potential human health consequences for either recycling site workers or people in the communities surrounding recycling sites (Singh, Duan and Tang, 2020).

Through the establishment of concentration limits for hazardous BFRs in certain consumer products, there has been a decrease in the use of these BFRs worldwide, which has been accompanied by an increase in the use of novel BFRs (NBFRs) for their re-placement. The most common NBFRs are DBDPE (decabromodiphenyl ethane) and TBBPA-DBPE (tetrabromobisphenol A-bis (2,3-dibromopropyl ether)) which are used to replace deca-BDE, octa-BDE and TBBPA, respectively. A review conducted by (Xiong *et al.*, 2019) gathered the latest information on the presence and distribution of NBFRs, in particular DBDPE BTBPE, HBB, PBEB (pentabromoethylbenzene), and PBT (polybutylene terephthalate) in biotic and abiotic environments,

and identified their human exposure and toxicity. The data collected show that most NBFRs do not pose significant risks to the environment, but more data from different species are required to better understand their health impacts. It was also demonstrated that NBFRs are ubiquitous in different matrices and their concentrations are generally higher in WEEE recycling sites compared to other locations. In terms of toxicity, it was shown that several NBFRs can cause adverse effects through different modes of action, such as endocrine disruption.

Endocrine disruptors (defined by the World Health Organization as “exogenous substances or mixtures that alter function(s) of the endocrine system and consequently causes adverse health effects in an intact organism, or its progeny, or (sub) populations”) are xenobiotics and it is hypothesized that the increase in the number of cases of people presenting conditions linked to their adverse health effects, such as neurodegenerative diseases, thyroid dysfunction, diabetes, and infertility, is due to an increase in the concentrations of endocrine disruptors to which people are currently exposed. However, many authors have evidenced that proposed links between health effects and endocrine disruptors are not robust enough and, therefore, further research is required. In a recent publication, (Pironti *et al.*, 2021) presented a review on endocrine disruptors found in different matrices (water, animals, and human), as well as analytical methods for their detection

To the best of the authors' knowledge, no reviews have been published on challenges associated with recycling plastics from WEEE, which include legal, industrial, environmental, and human health aspects. Therefore, it is necessary to create a collective component of information in the novel emerging research area of WEEE plastic recycling associated with BFRs. Based on (Cronin, Ryan and Coughlan, 2013), an extensive survey of legislation and literature was performed on the latest regulations, WEEE plastic sorting technologies, BFR occurrence, and recent findings on their impacts on the environment and health. The most relevant methods of existing industrial processes for determining BFRs and their challenges were identified. BFR occurrence and substitution by NBFRs was overviewed. An emphasis was placed on reviewing the health and environmental impacts associated with BFR/NBFRs presence in waste, consumer products, and WEEE recycling facilities. The knowledge and research gaps on this topic were highlighted. Finally, the discussion on current trends and proposals to attend to this relevant issue were outlined.

2.3 MANAGEMENT OF WEEE PLASTICS CONTAINING BFRS: CURRENT TRENDS AND CHALLENGES

WEEEs contain various resources, including precious metals (i.e., gold, platinum, copper, silver), as well as other valuable metals, such as iron and aluminium. These high-demand materials make WEEE economically attractive to both informal and formal recyclers. However, their management in the informal sector poses a threat to both the health of the people involved and the surrounding ecosystem due to the presence, generation, or use of toxic substances, including BFRs. This is a worrying matter, particularly in middle and low-income countries where WEEE is usually managed

under poor conditions, causing serious health impacts on workers and children who are usually linked to the activity as workers themselves or by playing close to where WEEE is processed (Forti *et al.*, 2020).

It is estimated that around 2.6 million tons³ of WEEE plastics are currently produced annually in Europe. The mass of this collected material is limited to 700 kt/year of which only approximately 30% (200 kt/year) can be sent for recycling due to current processing capacities. Management of the remaining 500 kt/year of recovered plastics is mainly by incineration for energy recovery or fuel replacement in cement kilns (44%), and land-filling (11%) (Cardamone, Ardolino and Arena, 2021). It is predicted that by 2050 recycling will increase to 50%, energy re-covery to 44%, with landfill being the least selected option decreasing to a projected 6% (Ahirwar and Tripathi, 2021).

Two of the main reasons behind the current low recycling rates are the mix of different polymers and the presence of additives, such as flame retardants. It is estimated that 9% of the total volume of WEEE plastics generated per year (234 kt/year) contain BFRs of which only a small fraction corresponds to restricted BFRs, such as octa-BDE or deca-BDE. Furthermore, because of restrictions imposed on their use, concentrations are rapidly, and steadily decreasing (octa-BDE use was restricted in 2003 and deca-BDE in 2008). However, given that EEE is estimated to have a useful life of approximately 12 years, EEE containing these compounds is currently being disposed of (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2020).

2.3.1 Brominated Flame Retardants (BFRs): Context

BFRs can be reactive or additive components. **Table 2.1** presents characteristic and examples for each type. Additive FRs are considered to be more unstable and volatile than reactive FRs, as a result of their covalent bonds with the polymer matrix.

Table 2.1 BFR classification, based on (Hennebert and Filella, 2018)

BFR Type	Interaction with Polymer	Example
Reactive	The BFR form a chemical bond with the polymer matrix which does not cause a softening effect.	TBBPA ^a
Additive	The BFR is blended in the polymer's matrix. These are more prone to leach as they are known to soften the polymer.	PBDEs ^b HBCDD ^c

Note: ^a tetrabromobisphenol A, ^b polybrominated diphenyl ethers, ^c hexabromocyclododecane.

³ tonne

Polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) are a noteworthy group of additive BFRs commonly found in plastics, foams, fabrics, and upholstery. In particular, PBDEs are widely found in the plastic parts of electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) and consequently need to be considered in WEEE management.

Being synthetic compounds, PBDEs are found marketed in different congeners mixtures, each of which has an exact composition depending on the manufacturer. **Table 2.2** presents average compositions of “penta”, “octa”, and “deca” mixtures.

Tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA) is another BFR commonly used in EEE plastics and is currently the most extensively applied BFR globally, comprising approximately 60% of the market (Zuiderveen, Slootweg and De Boer, 2020). The Globally Harmonized System (GHS) classifies TBPPA as H410: very toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effects. In June 2017, the European Union amended Annex III of Directive 2008/98/EC (Waste Framework Directive), regarding classification of waste as hazardous, setting concentration thresholds for waste containing substances declared as HP14 “Ecotoxic” by the GHS. According to this amendment, WEEE containing substances classified as H410, such as TBBPA, in concentrations higher than 2500 mg/kg are to be labelled as hazardous and their recycling is forbidden (*COUNCIL REGULATION (EU) 2017/997 of 8 June 2017 amending Annex III to Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the hazardous property HP 14 ‘Ecotoxic’, 2017; Öko-Institut, 2019*).⁴

Table 2.2 PBDEs (polybrominated diphenyl ethers) commercial mixtures composition, based on (Kodavanti et al., 2022).

Mixture	Percentage	Congeners
Penta	70%	99 (penta-BDE) 47 (tetra-BDE)
	<10%	100 (penta-BDE)
	<5%	153 and 154 (hexa-BDE)
	10–12%	Hexa-BDE
Octa	43–44%	Hepta-BDE
	31–35%	Octa-BDE
	9–11%	Nona-BDE
	0–1%	Deca-BDE
Deca	98%	Deca-BDE
	2%	Nona-BDEs

⁴ Further details on Flame Retardants are presented in **Appendix 2. Flame Retardants**.

2.3.2 BFRs: Use and Production—Regulatory Scope

Some brominated flame retardants, such as hexabromobiphenyl (HBB), HBCDD, and PBDEs, are known to be toxic and persistent once released into the environment. Globally, there is concern about the potential environmental pollution that BFRs (especially PBDEs) from discarded or recycled WEEE can cause. This has led different countries to take measures to reduce the use of these chemicals in electronic products. Consequently, they have been classified as persistent organic pollutants (POPs) by the Stockholm Convention. This convention is what is known as a multilateral environmental agreement (MEA) overseen by United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP), between 184 parties, of which, to date, 152 have ratified it (*Status of ratifications of the Stockholm Convention*, 2019). This convention establishes that signatory countries must take administrative and legislative measures for its implementation in order to collaborate locally and globally in mitigating the impacts associated with POPs. The target chemicals included by the convention are listed in three annexes: Annex A (Elimination), Annex B (Restriction), and Annex C (Unintentional production). For chemicals listed in Annex A, parties must take measures to eliminate their use and production. For those listed in Annex B, parties must take actions to restrict their use and production and lastly, for those listed in Annex C, parties must take measures to reduce their unintentional release.

There are currently five groups of BFRs listed in Annex A (Elimination) of the Stockholm Convention: HBB, HBCDD, commercial mixture c-decaBDE (decabromodiphenyl ether), and tetra-, penta-, hexa- and hepta-bromodiphenyl ethers. The convention mandates that waste items that contain concentrations of these BFRs higher than those defined as acceptable, must be disposed of by processes that ensure their destruction or irreversible transformation (Idowu *et al.*, 2013).

In some cases, certain parties are allowed to derogate from the established limits, for example, until 2030, penta- and octa-BDE are allowed to be present in waste materials sent for recycling. However, in these cases the restrictions for the production and use of these BFRs are clearly defined in the corresponding guidelines.

While the definition of limits for the production, use, and presence in waste sent for recycling of the POPs listed in the convention helps the removal of POP-BFRs from the environment, one of the most important challenges currently faced is the substitution of these compounds by other FRs, resulting in the legislation established by the signatory countries being only partially effective.

Other MEAs promoted and developed by UNEP include the Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movement of Wastes and their Disposal, and the Rotterdam Convention on Certain Hazardous Chemicals and Pesticides. These conventions encourage international cooperation between signatory countries, which include developed and non-developed countries, to achieve certain goals or to exchange technology, resources, and knowledge.

2.3.2.1 The European Union and the United Kingdom

In the European Union the requirements of the convention are enforced in both Directive 2011/65/EU (RoHS Directive) and Directive EU 2019/1021/EU (POPs Regulation). The first restricts the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment while the latter establishes concentration limits for POPs found in waste. The two directives operate in tandem and between them define concentration limits for certain hazardous substances, including BFRs, in consumer articles and waste.

Following life cycle logic, firstly, the RoHS Directive defines the UTCs (Unintentional Trace Contaminants) concentration limits for consumer articles entering the market including both new articles and articles that have been manufactured from recycled materials. Once the product is disposed of to be classified as waste, concentration limits are defined by Directive 2019/1021/EU, stating that in cases where these limits are exceeded, the materials may not be disposed of by conventional means, such as in landfills or recycling, but must be treated by methods that ensure their destruction (e.g., incineration for energy recovery). If these POP-containing wastes are treated in such a way that the hazardous substances are separated from the article, then it is permissible for such articles to be disposed of by conventional means.

The concentration limit for EEE in the European Union is set at 0.1% by weight for the sum of all PBDE congeners found in the relevant article placed on the market. The POPs regulation states that the concentration limit for the sum of tetra-BDE, penta-BDE, hexa-BDE, hepta-BDE and deca-BDE is 0.1% by weight (1000 mg/kg). Any disposed item exceeding this limit is considered hazardous waste and is required to be either destroyed or irreversibly transformed.⁵ A limit of 50 mg/kg is set for HBB, commonly used as FR in ABS plastics, and 1000 mg/kg for HBCDD, commonly found in XPS and EPS (insulation materials).

In addition, a limit of 10,000 mg/kg is defined for wastes from thermal/incineration processes, metallurgical processes, construction and demolition, or industrial processes.

In the UK, administrative and legal requirements relating to the convention are enforced by the POPs Regulations 2007, which regulated the management of WEEE containing levels of POPs above set limits (*The Persistent Organic Pollutants Regulations, 2007*). As this regulation implements Directive 2019/1021/EU, said limits are the same as those applicable in the European Union.

⁵ Since June 10th 2023, the POPs regulation establishes that the acceptable concentration of tetra-BDE, penta-BDE, hexa-BDE, hepta-BDE and deca-BDE at 0.05% by weight (500 mg/kg). This will be maintained until December 2025. Considering the decreasing concentrations of PBDEs observed in specific waste due to current restrictions on their market availability and utilization, and anticipating potential advancement in pertinent analytical and separation techniques, the EU has suggested that the limit be lowered to 350 mg/kg and ultimately reduced to 200 mg/kg from December 2027 on.

2.3.2.2 *The Americas: South and North*

The country with the highest WEEE generation volumes in South America is Brazil, a signatory of the Stockholm Convention. This country is currently benefiting from several exemptions for the application of PBDEs. For instance, the use of tetra-, penta-, hexa- and hepta-BDE is included as an exception in accordance with the provisions of Part IV of Annex A of the Stockholm Convention, thus, articles containing these compounds may still be marketed and/or recycled in Brazil (*Stockholm Convention Specific Exemptions*, 2019). To date, there are no legal requirements in place in Brazil regulating the application, import, or export of these POPs, and neither is the management of waste containing them.

As for North America, the United States of America stands out as the largest WEEE generator of the region; however, there are currently no federal restrictions related to BFRs. There are, nevertheless, state restrictions implemented in 13 states (Sharkey *et al.*, 2020).

2.3.2.3 *Asia*

China, Japan, and Indonesia, three of the major EEE producers in Asia, have adopted all the annexes relating to BFR-POPs in the Stockholm Convention. While Indonesia has not put in place any national regulations or policies limiting POP concentrations in goods, both Japan and China have established strategies aligned with the convention requirements to cut back on the use of these chemicals.

In China, the government has established various regulations that promote and standardize requirements for proper recycling processes of WEEE, including defining where they should be located and what pollution control measures should be put in place, such as dust removal or negative pressure workbenches to prevent their dispersion (Die *et al.*, 2019).

As for India, the other great EEE producer in this region, it has ratified only the first 12 listed POPs. Nevertheless, this country has banned use and trade of certain PBDEs (penta- and octa-), HBB, and HBCDD. Additionally, a concentration limit of 0.1% wt. is legally enforced on certain EEE (Sharkey *et al.*, 2020).

2.3.2.4 *Africa and Oceania*

To date, 53 countries in Africa are signatories to the Stockholm Convention, many of which have limited capacity, both technical and economical, to address and battle the health and environmental issues related to POP-BFRs. No policies or regulations are currently in place in any of the signatory countries. In the case of Oceania, all 14 countries are signatories to the convention.

2.3.2.5 Limitations

The increase in the use of NBFRs may be perceived as a limitation to the effectiveness of the Stockholm Convention and the legislation established thereunder. In order to meet flammability standards, new chemicals not currently included in the relevant legislation will enter the market. These replacements may themselves be classified as hazardous in the future due to the similarity of their chemical characteristics to those of the currently banned compounds.

The WEEE and RoHS Directives have triggered the substitution of BFRs by other alternative Br-free flame retardants such as aluminium, magnesium, or phosphorus-based additives. Currently no legislation regulates the replacement of compounds, which in addition to creating a loop in the presence of hazardous compounds in consumer articles and later in waste, directly affects the development of detection and removal methods for POP-BFRs, as these will need to be effective for both the legacy and novel BFRs present.

2.3.2.6 WEEE Management ⁶

There is currently no global agreement on WEEE management policies, however, in top generating countries/regions, WEEE is regulated according to legislation summarized in **APPENDIX A. WEEE Legislation Worldwide**.

2.4 DETERMINATION OF THE BFR CONCENTRATION IN WEEE PLASTICS

The use of currently restricted BFRs has been extensive in a wide variety of applications in the past. Consequently, there is a growing inventory of materials containing POPs-BFRs that have been or will be disposed of as waste, and therefore require the development of systems that allow for their proper and sustainable management.

Agreements, such as the Stockholm Convention, address this issue; however, although treatment and concentration limits are defined, the available technology for effectively screening consumer or waste articles in many cases is not adequate due to the precision required for their correct sorting.

Techniques such as GC/MS or LC/MS are very precise and specific, but nevertheless require extensive preparation of samples, making them slow and expensive, so they would not be operable on an industrial scale. On the other hand, there are cheaper and faster technologies, such as handheld X-ray fluorescence (h-XRF) or Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Neither of these techniques allow the determination of the concentration of the different species of BFRs found in the sample; however, they have shown potential for the screening of materials based on total

⁶ For complementary information refer to **Appendix 1. Management of WEEE Plastics Containing BFRs: Current Trends and Challenges**

bromine concentration with a high degree of certainty. In addition, h-XRF currently has limited potential for wide application due to the sources of error associated with the lack of commercially available calibration materials for different polymers and Br concentration ranges.

As industrial scale recycling of WEEE plastics is usually done at a rate of 1 ton⁷ per hour of plastic processed, h-XRF would not be able to comply with the screening requirements of such processes. For large-scale use, both technologies raise considerations that must be examined: FTIR in an online system does not require many operators for its use but is more expensive than h-XRF whilst h-XRF will probably require more than one unit and a number of operators trained in the use of the instrument to provide a local system to physically analyse the articles.

Improvements are continuously being made to the technologies and methods used for screening in order to increase their performance. The method most commonly used at the industrial level to separate BFR-rich from BFR-poor fractions of WEEE plastics is the sink/float method. These density separation processes are applied, whereby high-density fractions containing dense plastics and plastics containing various additives are separated from the low-density fraction with low percentages of additives. The latter fraction is subjected to further separation processes, e.g., electrostatic separation, through which the production of purer fractions of different polymers, e.g., ABS, PS, PP, and PE, is achieved. It is estimated that in the high-density fraction, more than 95% of the BFRs are contained together with other additives and intrinsically heavy plastics, such as PET, PC, PVC, etc. (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2020).

In a recent study, (Strobl *et al.*, 2021) assessed the efficiency of a density-based process (sink/float) to separate plastics from cathode ray tube (CRT) TVs and liquid crystal display (LCD) TVs into the two BFR fractions using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis. Results showed that, at the lab scale, an effective separation of the halogenated (Br-rich) from the non-halogenated (Br-poor) fractions was possible by density separation. Additionally, it was determined that the halogenated fraction of CRT TVs plastics corresponded to approximately 70% while a different trend was observed for LCD TVs with halogenated fractions varying between 47 and 72%.

In order to be recycled, plastics need to be segregated into classes according to the BFRs they contain and their concentrations, however, current plastic sorting technologies such as X-Ray Transmission (XRT) or XRF are not capable of distinguishing between, and therefore quantifying, the different types of BFRs present to determine compliance with regulation. At most, these methods allow the determination of total Br concentration⁸. To address this challenge, in the EU the European Commission requested CENELEC to develop a standard setting requirement for collection, transport and treatment of WEEE. The result was the EN 50625 standard, which is currently legally binding in Belgium, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, and France (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2020).

⁷ tonne

⁸ Refer to **Appendix 3. X-Ray Fluorescence** for further information on this technique

In the UK, the same requirements are established in Standard BS EN 50625 but are not legally binding. In TS 50625-3-1 (and PS CLC/TS 50625-3-1:2015 in the UK) it is established that, for plastics fractions from CRT screens, flat panel display (FPD) screens, and small appliances, the threshold to segregate BFR-rich fractions is set at 2,000 mg/kg of total Br.

Nevertheless, the EN 50625 concentration limit was statistically determined and therefore might be inaccurate. Consequently, other sorting technologies are being evaluated that allow for a segregation of plastics both by BFR concentration and polymer type. These include methods such as Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), direct analysis in real time–high resolution mass spectrometry (DART–HRMS), Raman, la-ser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS), multi-wavelength spectroscopy coupled with multivariate statistical analysis (MWS-MVSA), and, more recently, hyperspectral imaging (HSI). **Table 2.3** includes a brief description of each of these methods.

Table 2.3 Methods for sorting WEEE plastics according to their BFR contents.

Method	Characteristic Features	Reference
FTIR	Potential to provide information on BFR presence in real time. No considerable alteration of the sample is required.	(Taurino <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
DART-HRMS	Faster than common extraction/analysis. Targets molecular species: able to screen a wide number of BFRs including novel BFRs. Allows for desorption-ionization directly off the surface of the sample. Unclear if detection of BFRs is possible at relevant concentrations. Unclear if its specificity is sufficient.	(Puype, Ackerman and Samsonek, 2019)
RAMAN	Potential as an effective tool for rapid BFR detection in plastic when coupled with XRF.	(Taurino <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
LIBS	Elemental analysis technique. High analytical speed. Does not require excessive sample preparation. Adapts to harsh industrial environments. Intrinsic drawbacks do not allow for a thorough BFR measurement. This could be improved by combining it with XRF or inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry.	(Zeng <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
HSI	Able to measure a whole spectrum in every pixel in which the sample is divided. Linked to data analysis (chemometrics). Identification and segregation of polymer and flame retardants in plastic samples.	(Caballero, Bevilacqua and Amigo, 2019)

2.4.1 The Challenge of WEEE Classification according to Br Content

In several recent studies carried out in Australia (Gallen *et al.*, 2014), Austria (Aldrian, Ledersteger and Pomberger, 2015), the Czech Republic (Puype *et al.*, 2015), and the UK (Guzzonato, Puype and Harrad, 2016; Turner and Filella, 2017b, 2017a), authors agree that the classification of WEEE plastics by defined EEE categories is unlikely to be feasible. Thus, it was suggested that the best approach would be to separate and sort the plastics in order to avoid misclassifying BFR-free plastic parts as BFR-rich, and vice versa. Contrary to these conclusions, in the UK, the Environmental Agency published a guideline based on (Keeley-Lopez, Turrell and Vernon, 2020) where WEEE are classified as POPs/hazardous waste according to their EEE categories.

In Europe, the current capacity to separate and dispose of BFR plastics collected by official means is 215 kt/year (92% of the total WEEE/BFR plastics generated annually); however, it is estimated that around 120 kt/year are incorrectly managed in sub-standard recycling facilities, exported, or disposed of in bins with other general waste. Thus, the low volumes of treated WEEE/BFR plastic and, in contrast, the high volumes that are potentially released into the environment, are not linked to the installed processing capacity, but rather to inadequate sorting of WEEE by consumers and sub-standard recycling practices.

A common practice in the recycling industry is to shred mixed WEEE plastics, which might be then pelletized and later separated by density in a sink/float process. To assess the possibility of using h-XRF for Br determination and plastic sorting, (W.A. Stubbings *et al.*, 2021) studied extruded polymer pellets which were sorted by density separation into three fractions: light/medium/high. Each fraction was characterized for 28 legacy and novel BFRs; handheld XRF was used to determine total bromine concentration in 120 individual chips of various polymer types. A very important observation was made as Br concentration within different density classes was determined to be linked to the heterogeneity of the process's material. This means that each pellet consisted of melted plastic from many sources, thus the concentration of BFRs present in a pellet is an integration of the BFRs present in the individual plastic parts of each individual original item. Consequentially, plastics with low BFR concentrations (compliant with regulation) are mixed with plastics with high BFR concentrations resulting in pellets that do not comply with POP concentration limits. Therefore, the plastics are classified as POP waste, resulting in the loss of recyclable materials.

Considering the above, it can be concluded that, while the classification of WEEE by EEE categories might not be the most effective approach for a proper classification of plastics according to their BFRs content, resorting to their classification from mixed shredded and extruded WEEE plastics needs careful design for it to be accurate. This highlights the importance of sorting plastics at a primary stage, prior to or after shredding but before palletization to increase the volumes of plastics plausible of being sent for recycling according to the POP concentration limits defined in the relevant regulation.

In addition to the efficiency of the separation method and the quality of the separated material, costs are one of the most important factors in determining the viability of WEEE plastic recycling operations. The costs of this process have different inputs, including those related to sorting, processing, and disposal. As a counterpart, there are profits resulting from the sale of the materials, which increase with the efficiency of the overall treatment process.

As previously discussed, in order to comply with current regulations, it is mandatory to separate the regulated BFRs plastics, which entails separation and disposal costs for the fraction that cannot be sent for recycling. However, separation processes are key to recovering both homogeneous polymer fractions and those with low additive concentrations, therefore the investment and costs associated with separation processes cannot be allocated solely to the separation of BFR plastics. Likewise, the costs associated with the disposal of the high-density polymer fraction (containing high concentrations of BFRs) also cannot be attributed solely to the BFR content, as this fraction is already not suitable for recycling. On the contrary, if the BFRs present are POPs, then there will be additional costs as the material must be sorted and therefore treated as hazardous.

Furthermore, to add value to the material sent for recycling, WEEE plastics should not only be sorted into BFR/non-BFR fractions but also by polymer type and colour (black/clear). Depending on what methods are applied and in what order, the efficiency of the process varies and so do the costs. The challenge is to design a process producing high quality material, compliant with regulations, that can be sold at higher prices with costs below revenue.

2.5 BFRs DISTRIBUTION IN WEEE PLASTICS

Several studies have been carried out over the past decade to determine the BFR concentration in WEEE plastics. For instance, in a study by (Hennebert and Filella, 2018), the concentration of total Br and specific BFRs were determined in EEE and WEEE samples taken between 2009–2013 (EEE) and 2014–2015 (WEEE), for their regulatory classification. It was determined that the most concentrated BFRs found in WEEE were deca-BDE and TBBPA (3,000 mg/kg and 8,000 mg/kg, respectively), with 86% of total Br found in small household appliances (older waste) and 30–50% of total Br found in flat screens (younger waste) corresponding to regulated brominated substances.

An assessment of Irish waste polymers, carried out by (Drage *et al.*, 2018) considered four waste streams that were defined as most likely to contain BFRs, including WEEE. A total of 239 WEEE samples were analysed to determine their content of PBDEs (penta- and octa-), HBCDD and BDE-209 (decabromodiphenyl ether) in order to establish what percentage of the samples exceeded the LPCLs (low POP concentration limits) established by regulations. In addition, information on the volumes of waste annually generated in Ireland was collected. To estimate the volumes of waste that would annually re-quire treatment for the removal of POPs-BFRs or treatment that ensures their destruction, the volumes of generated waste were paired with that obtained from the BFR content

analyses. It was concluded that approximately 2,200 tons/year⁹ of waste generated in Ire-land contained levels of POPs-BFRs higher than the LPCLs set out in the regulation, with 13% being WEEE. It should be noted that at the time of the study BDE-209 had not been included in the POPs Directive (Directive 2019/1021) and a threshold value of 1,000 mg/kg BDE-209 was taken as set out in the Stockholm Convention. Currently BDE-209 is included within the limit of the sum of PBDEs (together with tetra-, penta-, hexa- and hep-ta-) that cannot exceed 1,000 mg/kg, so it is likely that the percentage of WEEE that exceeds the LPCL and cannot be directly recycled is currently higher.

A later study by (Jandric *et al.*, 2020) evaluated six types of WEEE devices which were manually dismantled, and their parts analysed to determine the different types of polymers, as well as total Br concentration. Results on Br concentrations were presented as a function of the device type, the polymer type and the year of manufacture. It was determined that 35% of the samples contained Br concentrations exceeding RoHS limits (0.1% of PBBs and PBDEs). It is worth noting that as a limitation to this study a conversion factor was determined by (Aldrian, Ledersteger and Pomberger, 2015) to convert total Br concentration into PBDE or PBB concentrations. In the latter, other BFR types (TBBPA, HBCD, compound mixtures) were not considered.

In the same year, (W.A. Stubbings *et al.*, 2021) published an assessment of BFRs in small mixed WEEE where pellets of extruded mixed polymers were analysed to determine the presence of legacy and NBFRs in the different types of polymers. The aim of the study was to determine which are the polymer types that may not comply with Directive 1021/2019 in the EU and POPs regulation in the UK. It was determined that BDE-209 and TBBPA were the main BFRs found, and they were present in all samples, with concentrations ranging between 68–37,000 mg/kg and 17–120,000 mg/kg, respectively. It is relevant to remark that 22% of the samples were misclassified as POP waste. This result was higher than that obtained by the study carried out in Ireland, (Drage *et al.*, 2018). It is suggested that the error might be related to the lack of calibration reference material for the higher concentration range.

A summary of the studies presented above is included in **Table 2.4**.

⁹ tonnes/year

Table 2.4 Summary of recent studies on the determination of BFR concentration in WEEE plastics

WEEE plastic sorting for bromine essential to enforce EU regulation (Hennebert and Filella, 2018)	Aim	Determine the concentrations of total Br and specific BFR
	Sample	EEE samples taken between 2009–2013 from a service laboratory for commercial products WEEE samples collected between 2014–2015 from processing facilities before and after shredding
	Methodology	ICP/OES (ISO 11885) for Sb determination, combusted oxygen in a closed system (EN 14582) and ionic chromatography for Br quantification, and GC/MS (IEC 62321-6) for determining the concentration of different BFRs
	Results	A 2000 ppm limit for total Br concentration can be used to classify POPs and non-POP WEEE plastic waste at laboratory scale. The contribution of BFRs to total WEEE plastic waste in weight was estimated to be about 25%
Brominated flame retardants in Irish waste polymers: Concentrations, legislative compliance, and treatment options (Drage <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	Aim	Measure the concentrations of PBDEs and HBCDD Estimate the mass of waste material and associated POP-BFRs that would be removed from circulation by effective enforcement of current LPCLs (low POP concentration limits) defined in EU Directive 2019/1021
	Sample	538 samples of WEEE, soft furnishings, construction and demolition waste, fabrics and PUF from ELVs in Ireland. Construction and demolition (EPS/XPS) = 62 ELV fabrics and PUF = 135 Soft furnishings = 123 WEEE = 239
	Methodology	Quantitative analysis: GC/MS and LC-MS/MS
	Results	Approximately 2,200 ton ¹⁰ s/year of the waste generated in Ireland contains POPs-BFR level higher than those set as LPCL in EC regulation (1000 mg/kg of PBDE excluding BDE-9209 and 1,000 mg/kg of HBCDD). Articles exceeding LPCLs: 44% building insulation 41% furniture foams and fabrics 13% WEEE and 1.7% end of life (EoL) vehicle waste

¹⁰ tonnes

Investigation of the heterogeneity of bromine in plastic components as an indicator for brominated flame retardants in waste electrical and electronic equipment with regard to recyclability (Jandric <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Aim	Determine the distribution of Br in plastics from WEEE
	Sample	882 components (369 different devices). Mixed WEEE (6 types of devices: personal computers, computer mice, keyboards, power supply units, vacuum cleaners, electrical toothbrushes)
	Methodology	Manual dismantling. Handheld XRF to determine total concentration of Br in different devices and different plastic components. FTIR spectroscopy to determine different polymers.
	Results	Br content represented by type of device, type of plastic and year of manufacture 35% of samples contain Br and 5% exceeded RoHS limit (mainly older devices). 18 different types of polymers were identified with ABS accounting for 44% of samples
Assessment of brominated flame retardants in a small mixed waste electronic and electrical equipment (WEEE) plastic recycling stream in the UK (W.A. Stubbings <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	Aim	Identify the presence of legacy and novel BFRs in individual polymer types from WEEE, to determine which polymers may be the ones not compliant with the LPCL (low POP concentration limits) established in regulation.
	Sample	217 individual polymer chips
	Methodology	Extruded polymer pellets were sorted by density separation into 3 fractions: light/medium/high. Each fraction was characterized for 28 legacy and novel BFRs. Portable XRF was used to determine total bromine concentration in 120 individual chips of various polymer types. If the concentration of total Br in the pellet was higher than 2,500 mg/kg, the pellet was further analysed by mass spectrometry (GC-MS, LC-MS/MS). 27 of which were further analysed by MS for BFRs. 97 chips: analysed by MS
	Results	BDE-209 (68–37,000 mg/kg) and TBBP-A (17–120,000 mg/kg) were determined to be predominant and ubiquitous. 22% of chips analysed were misclassified as POPs waste by XRF. The presence of NBFRs DBDPE and BTBPE (1,2-Bis(2,4,6-tribromophenoxy)ethane) was identified in WEEE plastics Colour sorting resulted in significant reductions in the concentrations of BFRs in the clear fraction, however, white polymers still did not comply with LPCL. ABS and PS-HIPS are the major contributors to the overall BFR concentration in the “medium” fraction. TBBP-A is known to be extensively used as an additive in HIPS and ABS for EEE. Heavy fraction: ABS, PC-ABS, PA, P, PVC, POM and PET. ABS, PC-ABS and PET were the only polymers containing BFRs in the heavy fraction

2.6 WEEE PLASTICS TREATMENT : THE STATE OF THE ART

Efforts are being made to address the issue of BFRs presence in WEEE plastics to increase the recyclability volumes and economic benefits. There appear to be two different approaches to researching and developing solutions to this challenge. On the one hand, the focus is on replacing legacy BFRs with novel FRs that are not currently restricted, while on the other hand, work is being done on the development of processes for the efficient extraction and recovery of BFRs and hazardous synergists, and on the recycling of clean plastic.

The approach by FR substitution has raised concerns in the plastics manufacturing and recycling industries as these new additives, even though complying with current legislation, may affect the quality of the material by deteriorating the polymer structure and could potentially result in the plastic no longer being recyclable (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2020).

As for WEEE plastic cleaning and additives recovery, there are three projects underway in Europe: CREAToR (1 June 2019–30 November 2022), Plast2Bcleaned (1 June 2019–23 May 2023) and NON-TOX (1 June 2019–31 May 2022). The three projects are funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and aimed at removing hazardous flame retardants from plastic waste. In the CREAToR project, materials targeted are ABS/PC, ABS, and HIPS plastics and treatment is to be performed by wet material handling of particles sized between 40 to 60 mm. Targeted elements are heavy metals, including Cd, Pb and Cr, BFRs and chlorinated flame retardants (CFR). The aim of this project is to reduce dependency on petroleum sources, generate job opportunities in the sector, and turn waste into non-hazardous resources. Challenges identified include seeing black plastics due to their low reflectance in the NIR region (being these the method most commonly used at industrial scale for polymer sorting), development of automated sorting processes and achieving a good ratio of purity/efficiency. Attending to these challenges, solutions proposed include using density baths to separate heavy from light plastic fractions, polymer sorting using multi-wavelength infrared radiation (MWIR) and the use of LIBS combining polymer and element detection of Br, Cl, Pb, Cd, and Cr (*CREAToR – COLLECT – PURIFY – REUSE*, 2020).

The objective of the PLAST2bCLEANED project is focused on HIPS and ABS plastics. Its aim is to develop a mechanical process using LIBS and Raman spectrometry that will lead to identifying several polymers of any colour, which contain different additives like BFRs or pigments to separate HIPS and ABS fractions. BFRs and Sb_2O_3 will be re-covered from separated plastics using superheated solvents. This project is looking at closing the polymer-Br- Sb_2O_3 loop by integrating processes and scaling them up, aiming to achieve 80% recovery yields and 8% increase in recycling rates while eliminating 40% of CO_2 emissions

In the NON-TOX project, an automated highspeed sensor (AHS) is used for sorting plastics (80% efficiency has been achieved in classifying BFRs). The main recycling fraction is the treated by two processes:

1. Subjected to Creasolv® and Extruclean® technologies for the extraction additives, while maintaining the polymer's properties. Three different streams are obtained with this process: targeted polymers with halogen concentrations below 1,000 ppm, a halogen concentrate, and a mix of all the other plastics.
2. Subjected to thermochemical conversion where, at appropriate temperatures, halogenated polymers release the halogens contained in them.

The expected impact of this project is to increase the EU recycling capacity by 74%, reaching 2.18 Mt of plastics processed per year, while creating jobs and reducing emissions.

A positive outcome of these projects would mean a significant improvement for the WEEE plastics recycling industry in the EU, increasing processing capacity, job opportunities, and reducing the associated negative environmental impacts.¹¹

2.7 BFRS EXISTENCE IN CONSUMER PRODUCT PLASTICS

Several studies have determined the presence of BFRs in consumer products (CPs) and in other products, through which humans may be exposed such as toys and jewellery. The presence of these compounds in CPs plastics is explained because of improper handling of WEEE plastics that are mixed with virgin polymers. In Europe this constitutes a violation of the regulation (Regulation EU 10/2011). However, the use of recycled polymer for the manufacture of CPs is allowed in the European market but only under strict conditions that include a careful and efficient separation of the materials to be re-cycled. Particularly in the case of black plastic, the plastic sorting processes currently implemented in the industry are not able to separate them as most of them are based on IR.

Consumer products containing BFRs, particularly items that come into contact with food (food contact articles—FCAs) or small toys that children can put in their mouths, compromise consumer safety as these plastics directly affect the quality of the item and can release certain levels of different chemicals through migration, thereby exposing the consumer. A number of studies have determined farther sources of exposure to these hazardous chemicals. For instance, in a study by (Yu *et al.*, 2017), the content of PBDEs and TBBPA in household waste was quantified to identify the sources and trends of these compounds and understand the potential for migration of PBDEs and TBBPA into consumer products via plastic recycling processes. It is reported that results support conclusions from previous studies about the importance of separating WEEE plastics containing BFRs from other

¹¹ Refer to **Appendix 4. State of the art of WEEE plastics treatment** for further information

plastics that can be recycled to be safely used in consumer goods. Furthermore, disposing of WEEE plastics in the municipal waste stream in landfills or through incineration, constitute a means for BFRs, Sb, Cd, and Pb to be released into the environment.

Based on a previous study by the same authors, the work in (Puype *et al.*, 2015) investigated the potential contamination with WEEE stream polymers of polymeric FCAs in more detail by using different techniques to prove the illegal use of recycled WEEE plastic in black plastic. According to European Commission Regulation (EC) No. 10/2011, this is an illegal practice within the European Union. The study confirms the indication that black polymer FCAs manufactured using recycled WEEE plastic circulate in the European market. Two years later, the same author published in (Puype *et al.*, 2017) a study linked to that of 2015, aimed at proposing a method based on levels of significance for an efficient in situ assessment of the presence of WEEE plastics in FCA plastics by determining Br and Sb (level 1), BFRs (level 2) and WEEE-related elements and additionally the purity of the polymers (level 3).

Another study by (Turner and Filella, 2017a) assesses the ubiquity of Br in consumer products' plastics including electronic, electrical, and non-electronic items. Total Br concentration was determined by XRF spectrometry as an indicator of BFRs presence in these plastics. It was concluded that high concentrations of Br are found in consumer products which could potentially results in human exposure to BFRs (as well as Sb and Pb usually found associated with Br in plastic items). Determining the presence of Br and Sb in plastics of items that do not require flame retardants suggests that the plastic components of the old items were and/or are being recycled into consumer products.

Consistent with previous studies, Turner and Filella found that most Br-contaminated consumer products are black in colour, even though BFRs are added to plastics in electronic goods in a range of mostly neutral colours. The authors conclude that this is linked to the practical difficulties and costs associated with recycling plastics pigmented with black carbon. Particularly, black plastics cannot be sorted according to polymer type by optical means as the black pigment absorbs infrared radiation. This results in a limited recyclability of black plastic in contrast to the high demand for black plastic items, which may lead to manufacturers using (intentionally or unintentionally) black plastic from WEEE containing BFRs, Sb, and Pb as an alternative source of this material for the manufacture of different consumer products.

Further research on the issue of WEEE black plastic recycling for the manufacturing of consumer products was carried out by Turner, who in 2018 (Turner, 2018), published a literature review in which it is identified that, while the manufacture of plastics in general already generates environmental and health impacts, the production of black plastics in particular has greater and more serious risks associated with it. It was then stated that such impacts are a direct consequence of the low separation efficiency of these plastics in the industry, related to the sorting and separation methods that are

currently in place. In the same review, the linearity or circularity of the WEEE black plastics economy is assessed. It is determined that black plastics are embedded in a quasi-circular economy model, in which the material is inefficiently sorted while being highly demanded by the manufacturing industry to partially cover black plastic requirements for the production of consumer materials. As the plastic is not properly sorted, the material that is recycled does not meet the requirements regarding the content of BFRs and these hazardous additives end up being present in consumer goods, which significantly increases the exposure of humans to these compounds and thus affect their health.

Another source of exposure to BFRs through CP plastics are toys. To assess this, (Fatunsin *et al.*, 2020) carried out a study in the UK, selecting 23 plastic toys components dating between 1997 and 2017. The aim was to confirm previous evidence of WEEE plastic recycling into consumer products and children potential exposure to BFRs (including PBDEs, TBBPA and HBCDD) by accidental ingestion. Results of the study confirmed the presence of BFRs in 20 of the 23 analysed samples, which, as components of consumer products, are not included in the regulations for flame retardants. This evidence adds to previous studies indicating that the presence of BFRs in consumer product plastics must be linked to the recycling of WEEE plastics. On the other hand, the evaluation of the exposure of children to BFRs through accidental ingestion indicates that, in some cases, the exposure is considerable, being for some individuals the most significant route of exposure to BFRs. These observations disclose the need for stricter controls in the recycling industry to ensure the removal of BFRs from WEEE plastic streams sent for recycling, as well as a probable lack of efficiency in the processes currently applied for the separation of plastics containing BFRs. Furthermore, the fact that children can potentially be exposed to these hazardous compounds through their contact with toys highlights the importance of further controls, research, and development in the processes WEEE plastics recycling.

Despite the increase in the use of NBFRs there is currently not enough knowledge on the potential cumulative effects of any NBFRs and no analytical methods have been determined to measure these compounds, with a research gap so large that according to a review by (Zuiderveen, Slootweg and De Boer, 2020), 28 out of the 63 NBFRs studied are not even included in monitoring programs or studies exposing the need for further research on the toxicity and fate of NBFRs, for which their presence in consumer goods has already been determined.

2.8 WEEE RECYCLING AS A SOURCE OF EXPOSURE TO BFRS: HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENTAL HAZARDS

In most countries, WEEE generated at the household level is managed either through disposal in waste bins, through informal collection by private companies or governmental organizations, or through collection outside the formal system by informal waste management companies. WEEE collected through the formal system is generally treated through processes that ensure safe treatment for the environment and health. On the other hand, those who manage these wastes

illegally mostly process them under basic technological conditions and without measures to prevent emissions of hazardous compounds such as BFRs. The persistence over time of these informal activities combined with the persistence of BFRs in the environment increases the level and risk of exposure of both the workers involved and those living nearby, and consequently represents a potential health hazard. In the developing world, which is the largest generator and recycler of WEEE, a vast majority of such recycling units are in the informal sectors that usually lack advanced technology for WEEE recycling and are not able to take effective measures for mitigating environmental pollution associated with inefficient WEEE recycling.

Particularly, in China and developing countries where informal recycling of WEEE is common, due to the high degree of application of BFRs in EEE plastics, and as a consequence of dismantling, acid treatment, and open burning of WEEE, these hazardous compounds are being released uncontrollably into the environment. Concentrations of TBBPA and PBDEs have been detected in vegetables, rice plants, and other wetland plantations, indicating that these BFRs may enter the food chain through accumulation in plants and soil. In addition, their presence has been detected in molluscs, birds, and humans (blood, adipose tissue, and breast milk). This highlights the importance of addressing the management of WEEE plastics to prevent these hazardous compounds from affecting the environment and health.

Even in an organized sector, WEEE recycling poses several environmental and occupational health hazards which also partly stem from the fact that WEEE recycling technologies have not kept pace with the technological advancements in the field of production of electronic and electrical equipment.

Recently, several studies were carried out to assess the sources of exposure to BFRs and related impacts to the environment, animals, and humans, with a particular focus on people working at either a WEEE recycling site or residing in nearby areas. The first re-reported flame retardant exposure study was carried out at four WEEE recycling sites in Finland between 2008 and 2009 by (Rosenberg *et al.*, 2011). For the assessment, air concentrations of five brominated flame retardants were measured in breathing areas. It was observed that the most abundant FRs in the personal air samples were PBDEs, TBBPA and DBDPE, and it was found that in two of the four study sites, emission control measures (such as improvements in ventilation and changes in maintenance and cleaning habits) had positive results in decreasing the levels of RFs present in the air.

In 2020, (Cai *et al.*, 2020) published a systematic review addressing the current status of human exposure to PBDEs in WEEE recycling areas in different countries and identifying their effects. The review includes studies from different geographic areas in various countries around the world, such as China, India, Vietnam, Thailand, Nigeria, Ghana, Canada and the United States. It was then determined that risks of long-term exposure of humans to PBDEs due to improper handling and recycling of WEEE have existed in the past and that particularly in China, exposure levels in informal WEEE management areas are at least an order of magnitude higher than in other areas.

An important conclusion was drawn relative to the route of exposure to PBDEs, where ingestion through food was considered the most relevant source, while air inhalation and dust ingestion are also important mainly in workers in the sector. Furthermore, evidence show that those residing in WEEE recycling areas for longer periods of time, would have been exposed to considerable levels, and children are likely to face higher exposure due to a wider variety of exposure pathways including placental metastasis, ingestion through breast milk, behaviours such as ingestion of soil or putting objects in the mouth, among others. WEEE recycling workers are also in the high-risk group, as they are exposed to higher levels of PBDEs and for longer periods of time, which could be determined through studies of hair, serum, and some tissues. In sum, it is concluded that exposure to PBDEs is higher in WEEE recycling areas.

In a previous study by (Die *et al.*, 2019), similar observations were made and more de-tails about sources of exposure were determined. The study aimed to determine the concentration of PBDEs in air, soil dust and fly ash samples obtained from a bag-type dust collector in different WEEE recycling plants, and to estimate the daily intake of PBDEs by workers through inhalation or ingestion of dust. The results showed a high concentration of PBDEs in all three monitored matrices in TV and plastic WEEE recycling plants. It was also found that the concentration of PBDEs in the air decreased with in-creasing efficiency of the dust removal equipment installed in the different facilities. However, the exposure of workers to PBDEs was found to be within safe levels, and in some cases up to two orders of magnitude lower than those defined by US EPA as reference doses. These results highlight the need for strict pollution control measures to be put in place in WEEE recycling plants, mainly dust collectors to help reduce worker exposure to hazardous compounds, such as PBDEs.

It was also found that daily exposure of PBDE of workers from these plants was lower than that found for workers of other recycling facilities. Additionally, it was determined that the ingestion of dust was the main route of exposure for workers doing manual recycling, while inhalation was the main source for workers in charge of waste transportation.

Overall, it was concluded that the emissions of PBDEs and the associated risks, are lower in modern formal WEEE recycling plants where effective pollution control measures are in place. Nevertheless, it was highlighted that further research is under-stood to be necessary to determine how effective these controls are in plastic crushing areas where dust is found to have the highest PBDEs concentrations.

This was in line with that exposed in a more recent review by (Cai *et al.*, 2020), who determined that the three main routes of external exposure to halogenated FRs in humans at informal WEEE handling sites are ingestion of dust and food, inhalation, and dermal absorption. However, there is currently little research on exposure through dermal ab-sorption. It also agrees with the conclusion that workers in informal WEEE recycling plants, children, infants, and foetuses, are subject to the highest exposure compared to adults who reside in the plant area but do not work in this activity. In

this review further observations were made as it was noted that some studies report on existing differences in internal exposure to BFRs according to gender, with higher concentrations of BFRs found in serum and hair of females compared to those found in males. However, the cause of this is still unclear.

As hair is one of the non-invasive matrices for the study of biomarkers in humans, as well as being easy to sample and inexpensive to store and transport, several studies are based on the study of hair samples and have shown that hair samples can be used to differentiate between study subjects and exposure levels. It is important to note that particularly in hair, the contaminant can enter via internal (through the blood) or external (through exposure to dust, air, or chemicals applied to the hair) routes. In a study carried out in 2015 by (Qiao *et al.*, 2019) hair samples from 31 female employees of WEEE recycling facilities were analysed to determine the impact on the body of their exposure to legacy and novel FRs, and to analyse the accumulation of these compounds in hair by identifying which factors promote or prevent such accumulation. The results of the hair analysis indicated a mean concentration of the sum of PBDEs of 154 ng/g, 92.8% of which corresponded to BDE-209. Additionally, samples were taken from the hands of 10 workers during their working hours and 10 samples of dust from the floor inside the facility in order to characterize the external sources of exposure. However, the floor dust samples represent a single external exposure pathway, while samples taken from hands reflect exposure through contact with dust and WEEE. Although high concentrations of contaminants were determined in the wipes, a relationship between the contaminants determined in the wipes and the hair could not be determined.

In a review by (Gravel, Aubin and Labrèche, 2019) peer-reviewed publications of quantitative air, dust, and biological fluid studies assessing the occupational exposure of formal workers from different industries to organic compounds, including BFRs were critically collected and compiled. Evidence showed the most studied compounds were PBDEs and NBFRs, while the most studied sites were offices and WEEE recycling facilities, the latter reporting the highest exposures. Nevertheless, most of the studies concerning the health effects of FRs have been carried out in children, animals or in vitro studies, so, as the effects of exposure in adults have not been studied in depth, the evidence is scarce and no OELs (occupational exposure limits) have been defined. A study by (Shen *et al.*, 2019) assesses the gap in toxicity data of NBFRs discussing the neuro (endocrine) toxic effect of NBFRs both in vitro and in vivo. Data from this article indicate that, particularly during early neurodevelopment, exposure to NBFRs could cause unwanted neurobehavior with potential to damage the neuroendocrine system including affects to thyroid/sex hormone levels. Current data and published studies on the health effects of NBFRs suggest that it is imperative to further study their impact on behaviour and brain function, as well as the changes in structure that result from exposure to NBFRs, as well as the neurotoxicity of their metabolites and related breakdown products (Dong *et al.*, 2021). A similar observation was made by (Li *et al.*, 2019), who also identified a research gap on the evaluation of the effects of NBFRs to humans as studies

are mainly in vitro and in vivo animal studies, where their health effects were studied through acute toxicity, endocrine disrupting activity, reproductive, and developmental toxicity, among others. It was determined that airborne particles are the main carriers of FRs and therefore contribute significantly to their inhalation. On the other hand, it was found that dermal absorption of FR particles also contributes considerably to the overall intake of these compounds. This is in line with previous studies of legacy BFR exposure of WEEE recycling workers. However, in most of the cases evaluated, the FR intake doses were estimated to be substantially below the reference values. In a recent study carried out by (Ling *et al.*, 2021), the contamination of water and sediments by legacy and novel BFRs was evaluated at two of the world's largest e-waste dismantling sites located in the Chinese city of Taizhou. According to the results it was found that the concentration of BFRs and NBFRs in the water of both sites were comparable and at the upper end of the global range, while in the sediments there were differences with high concentrations at one site and relatively low concentrations at the other. It could, therefore, be proven that the WEEE dismantling activity has posed an unacceptable risk to animals living both in the water and sediments surrounding the sites. This shows that even in developed countries, such as China, it is necessary to reinforce the legislation on BFRs in order to define risk control standards for the environment, including water, sediments and other matrices that may be affected and have not yet been studied. At the same time, the high levels of BFRs and NBFRs concentration in the surrounding areas show that measures should be taken to optimize the e-waste dismantling process carried out there, seeking to eliminate the informal management of these wastes. It is also of utmost importance to continue studying the risk to the health of the workers as well as the population in the area.

It should be noted that most of the studies of human exposure to BFRs have been carried out in China and considering this country banned the import of WEEE in 2018, it is likely that these wastes are being directed to other countries or regions, which will have a corresponding environmental and health impact if they are improperly treated. It is therefore important that studies are carried out on the informal treatment of WEEE in low- and middle-income countries.

2.9 KNOWLEDGE AND RESEARCH GAPS

The issue of BFRs in WEEE plastics has been addressed by different projects and authors in the past decade. As previously discussed, according to the Stockholm Convention, a number of PBDEs and HBBC are identified as POPs and are therefore restricted. However, there are currently alternative BFRs being used with similar chemical characteristics to those restricted which could thus be later classified as POPs.

In addition to this gap in regulations which will likely result in larger volumes of currently unregulated BFRs being found in WEEE plastics in future years when EEE currently manufactured become waste, most studies are not considering the presence of novel BFRs in WEEE plastics arriving to misleading conclusions on the presence of these additives. Furthermore, studies in which a total Br

concentration threshold is determined need to be carefully considered as in most cases not all Br components are evaluated and therefore the baseline is not accurate. For instance, a conversion factor was determined by (Aldrian, Ledersteger and Pomberger, 2015) to convert total Br concentration into PBDE or PBB concentrations, however in the study other BFR types, such as TBBPA, HBCD, or compound mixtures, were not considered.

A possible solution to this could be to generate a statistically validated and comprehensive data base containing detailed information on BFR concentrations by WEEE category, device and plastic types, functionality of the components and year of production. To achieve this, the collaboration of the manufacturing industry would be key. Additionally, FRs recently incorporated to consumer products need to be studied in more depth and amplitude.

Regarding techniques and technology available for the determination of BFRs in plastics at industrial level further research into, and the development of methods to screen for hazardous chemicals in end of life materials, is of the utmost importance. This should include an assessment of the economic, environmental and health benefits of manual dismantling as pre-processing method taken to enable the production of more homogeneous and Br-free plastics fractions. In particular, the determination of the pathways of occupational exposure and the distribution of airborne FR particles in WEEE processing facilities needs to be studied in more depth.

The restriction of BFRs in WEEE plastic respond to the fact that certain BFRs may have severe impacts on both the environment and human health and should therefore be removed from the recycling stream. However, from published literature reviews on BFRs and health, it becomes obvious that more investigations are needed to monitor potential cross-contamination when BFRs are unintentionally transferred from one product to another through recycling process. Especially, in terms of black plastic from consumer goods where further research is needed to assess the migration of the hazardous compounds introduced in consumer goods via black WEEE plastic recycling, the sources of exposure and impacts on human health.

2.10 DISCUSSION

Directives such as RoHS and POPs, which define limits on the concentrations of BFRs accepted in products and waste respectively, have as a direct consequence that high percentages of the plastic volumes arriving at recycling facilities cannot be effectively recycled, as this requires the irreversible destruction of the BFRs contained in the material, processes that are still under development. This leaves companies with no alternative but to incinerate the plastic. As a measure to optimize the volumes of plastic that is recycled, one option would be to replace the currently used BFRs with bromine-free FRs. However, the proposal to migrate to the use of bromine-free FRs may not help to increase the percentage of WEEE plastic recycled as these would also be sorted with the high Br concentration fraction. Additionally, the effect of bromine-free FR on plastic recyclability needs to be

further studied as it is still undetermined how do they affect the quality of the material regarding the purity and other characteristics of the polymer.

An alternative approach could include development and approval of pro-active legislation that eliminates the need for using such persistent and potentially harmful chemicals in the future, and/or evaluating the flame retardancy requirements established in regulation considering the changes in materials, lifestyles, and safety measures put in place in a wider number of households and offices, such as CO₂ and smoke detectors.

Overall, the presence of BFRs in WEEE plastics is a matter of concern when it comes to their management and focus must be put on aiming to prevent potential negative impacts to both the environment and public health. That is why it is imperative that knowledge on the subject continues to be developed and deepened in order to provide all actors involved in WEEE management with the necessary tools to develop strategies to prevent any harmful impacts. Adequate concentration limits need to be defined that, in addition to protecting health and the environment, allow the treatment of these plastics by means that favour the circularity of the material, i.e., recycling as opposed to incineration. Currently, the industrial processes developed and in place present low levels of recyclability, which is explained by the difficulty of determining the content of restricted BFRs. It would therefore be positive to work on defining regulated limits based on total Br concentrations that favour the sorting of the material using simple and therefore less costly and more efficient methods.

In any case, it is always important to define whether the screening and characterization methods are robust enough to comply with the regulation, as well as to assess whether the defined thresholds are sufficiently conservative.

Considering the current conditions and challenges of handling WEEE plastics containing BFRs, the substitution of restricted BFRs by other compounds that potentially need to be further restricted as well (i.e., NBFRs), or the substitution by non-brominated materials that may affect the quality of the recycled material, it is inevitable to ask whether the solution can be found in another alternative. For example, could a material be produced with the same physico-chemical characteristics as petroleum-based plastics, which is also economically feasible and replaces plastic in the manufacture of EEE? Could bioplastics be considered for this purpose? And would these materials also need to contain FRs?

In the long term, the answer to the problem of BFRs and the recycling of plastics from WEEE may lie not in finding effective processes for their detection and removal, but in finding alternative materials to eliminate the need for their presence in electrical and electronic equipment.

CHAPTER 3 Optimized industrial sorting of WEEE plastics: development of fast and robust h-XRF technique for hazardous components

This chapter is an accepted manuscript version of the below cited article:

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3.1 GRAPHIC ABSTRACT

Keywords: Innovation, hazardous waste, h-XRF, Brominated Flame Retardants, Flat Panel Display, Manual dismantling

3.2 ABSTRACT

Waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) are a source of both hazardous and valuable materials that must be segregated for treatment. Previous studies addressing the use of hand-held X-Ray fluorescence (h-XRF) as a sorting tool for WEEE plastics through the identification of hazardous components include plastics from mixed WEEE streams, processed material (shredded

or treated plastics) and low number of samples not allowing to consider their findings for application on an industrial scale. Thus, further research is needed to establish scalable robust methods for sorting this material. We describe a study carried out on whole flat panel display equipment (FPD) plastic casings using h-XRF for the detection of total bromine (Br) and antimony (Sb) as tracers for Brominated Flame Retardants (BFRs) and Sb_2O_3 additives. The aim being to characterize the targeted material and to define the optimal analysis conditions to meet large scale throughputs. A ring trial exercise comprising 100 samples was conducted to evaluate the validity of the measurements. Results indicate that: 1) the use of h-XRF under the conditions determined in this study offers a valid technique to screen total Br and Sb in whole FPD casings at industrial scale with low uncertainty, 2) Br and Sb are found to be homogeneously distributed within the casing, 3) an optimal h-XRF analysis time of 10 seconds is suitable from both accuracy and practical implementation for $\text{LOD} < [\text{Br}] \leq 830 \text{ mg/kg}$ and $\text{LOD} < [\text{Sb}] \leq 8,400 \text{ mg/kg}$, and 4) the presence of dust deposited on the casings was excluded as a factor affecting h-XRF results. To our knowledge this is the first evaluation of optimal sorting conditions for whole display casings using h-XRF, within a manual dismantling process.

3.3 INTRODUCTION

Waste electrical and electronic equipment is the fastest growing waste stream worldwide. According to reports published in 2020, 11.8 Mt were generated between 2014 and 2019 and considering the projected annual growth rate of 2 Mt, WEEE volumes could exceed 74 Mt by 2030 (Ahirwar and Tripathi, 2021).

The priority characteristic of WEEE is the presence of potentially toxic chemical compounds which makes it hazardous waste. Including a wide variety of materials such as ferrous and non-ferrous metals, plastics account for approximately 30% of the volume of WEEE generated annually, comprising a wide variety of polymers. ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene), HIPS (High Impact Polystyrene), PC+ABS (Polycarbonate + Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene) and PPE (Polyphenyl Ether) are the most frequently found (Goosey, 2012).

As a consequence of this diversity, sorting plastic is complex resulting in low recycling rates with estimates suggesting that between 40-50% of recovered volumes are not being adequately recycled (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2010). Adding to this challenge is the presence of certain additives such as flame retardants, which, if not treated properly, may be released from the polymer matrix as primary pollutants (Skjevrak *et al.*, 2003; Kim, Osako and Sakai, 2006) or function as catalysts for a variety of different dioxins and furans and therefore have a significant impact on health and the environment as secondary pollutants (Weber, 2003).

According to an early study by Dawson and Landry, 2005 (Dawson and Landry, 2005) TV-related fires are identified amongst the most frequent during electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) use,

with the introduction of flame retardants resulting in a significant reduction of these incidents. DecaBDE (Decabromodiphenyl ether), EBP (ethane 1,2 bis (pentabromophenyl)) and EBTBP (ethylene 1,2 bis (tetrabromo phthalimide) EBP) were identified as the most commonly used BFRs. Two years later, Herat, 2007 (Herat, 2008) presented an analysis on the use of brominated flame retardants (BFRs) in EEE, reporting in addition the presence of TBBPA (Tetrabromobisphenol A), HBCDD (Hexabromocyclododecane) and octa-BDE (Octabromodiphenyl ether).

Regulations have been imposed with the aim of reducing the use of these and other BFRs in EEE plastics. For instance, since 2004 and 2008 the use of octa-BDE and deca-BDE respectively, was banned. However, (Schlummer *et al.*, 2007) reported only a slight decrease in the fraction of materials containing BFRs compared to that reported for the year 2000 by (Leisewitz, Kruse and Schramm, 2001). More recent studies indicate that the content of BFRs depends on the type of plastic analysed. (Peeters *et al.*, 2014) reported that HIPS and ABS EEE housings generally contain BFRs and only 8.5-14% contain phosphorous flame retardants and/or other additives. Furthermore, a study by (Gripon *et al.*, 2021) focusing on ABS shows significant concentrations of TBBPA were found in 88% of the plastics analysed and PBDEs (Polybrominated diphenyl ethers) were identified in 11% of the samples with the highest concentrations corresponding to deca/octa/hepta-BDE. In addition, (Zhan *et al.*, 2019) observed that the use of BTBPE (1,2-bis(2,4,5-tribromophenoxy)ethane)) as a substitute for traditional BFRs was increasing despite evidence of its similar characteristics to legacy BFRs including its persistence in the environment and potential for bioaccumulation.

PBDEs, HBB (hexabromobenzene) and HBCDDs are included in the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs). In 2019, (Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on persistent organic pollutants (recast) (Text with EEA relevance.), 2019) was enforced in Europe to implement the limits set in the Convention. It was then decided that if the sum of PBDEs and/or the sum of HBCDDs exceeds 1,000 mg/kg in waste material, it must be classified as POPs waste and treated so that POPs are either destroyed or irreversibly transformed. TBBPA, currently the most extensively applied BFR worldwide, has yet to be declared a POP but the Globally Harmonized System (GHS) classifies it as H410: "very toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effects". In June 2017, the European Union amended Annex III of Directive 2008/98/EC (Waste Framework Directive) (Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives (Text with EEA relevance), 2008), regarding classification of waste as hazardous, setting concentration thresholds for waste containing substances declared as HP14 "Ecotoxic" in the GHS. According to this amendment, WEEE containing TBBPA in a concentration higher than 1,000 mg.kg⁻¹ is to be labelled as hazardous and their recycling is forbidden (COUNCIL REGULATION (EU) 2017/997 of 8 June 2017 amending Annex III to Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the hazardous property HP 14 'Ecotoxic', 2017). In the UK, the legal and administrative requirements defined by the Convention are enforced by the POPs Regulation 2007

(The Persistent Organic Pollutants Regulations 2007, 2007). To date, this regulation applies requirements defined in EU 2019/1021 therefore transferring identical concentration limits.

BFRs are usually used in combination with antimony trioxide (Sb_2O_3) as synergist typically found in TV/Display equipment in concentrations of approximately 20% of the Br content (Harrad, Drage, M. A.-E. Abdallah, *et al.*, 2019). In the European Union (EU) and the UK, waste containing Sb is classified under the Chemical Classification, Labelling and Packaging (European Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008) (*Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures*, 2008) which establishes that any waste containing Sb_2O_3 in concentrations higher than 0.1% w/w (10,000 mg/kg), is to be classified as hazardous.

As a consequence of the above regulatory requirements, the WEEE management sector faces the challenge of managing plastics in an environmentally sound and legally compliant manner within a profitable business model. In the UK there are currently no systems in place to promote co-operation between producers, retailers and recyclers within which information on the substances contained in the different components is disclosed. Therefore, in order to improve the efficiency of plastics sorting processes and thus the maximisation of its recycling rates, it is necessary to develop a technique by which recyclable and non-recyclable plastics are reliably identified and separated, ensuring the correct management of hazardous fraction. Current state of the art of WEEE plastics management is described in (Chaine *et al.*, 2022).

Different techniques have been studied for the characterisation of BFRs and Sb_2O_3 in WEEE plastics. For measuring BFRs reliable methods include gas chromatography with electron capture detection or mass spectrometry as well as liquid chromatography with different coupled detectors (Aldrian, Ledersteger and Pomberger, 2015; Zhan *et al.*, 2019; Strobl *et al.*, 2021; Yli-Rantala *et al.*, 2021). On the other hand, the method generally used for the determination of Sb_2O_3 in plastics is the analysis by ICP/OES after Sb chemical extraction from the matrix. Considering this compound as the only source of Sb present in WEEE plastics, all the Sb measured is attributed to it.

These conventional methods to determine the compliance of WEEE plastic with regulation for its recycling are technically and economically demanding, with analysis times incompatible with the throughput required at industrial level. For this reason, during the past decade research has increasingly focused on more practical alternatives such X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) as a fast, non-destructive and effective technique, by which it is possible to rapidly determine total concentrations of Br and Sb as tracers of BFRs and Sb_2O_3 . (Sharkey, 2019; Alghamdi, Abdallah and Harrad, 2022).

The current global regulatory and economic frameworks, demand for the development and application of cost-effective methods for the identification and sorting of WEEE plastics. Extensive research has been carried out on the application of handheld XRF (h-XRF), however, the results

presented do not evaluate the potential of the methodology for its industrial use and are not specifically applicable to all WEEE streams. Assessed matrixes include varied mixes of plastics from different products (Taurino *et al.*, 2014; Harrad, Drage, M. A.-E. Abdallah, *et al.*, 2019), low number of samples (Guzzonato, Puype and Harrad, 2016; Alassali, Abis, *et al.*, 2019; Jandric *et al.*, 2020; Kousaiti *et al.*, 2020; Strobl *et al.*, 2021; Drage *et al.*, 2022) and in many cases samples are collected after shredding (Hennebert, 2020) or recycling (W.A. Stubbings *et al.*, 2021). Thus, it is still necessary to evaluate its application on a larger scale in order to meet industry processing requirements. For this, it is essential to thoroughly characterize the targeted materials as recovered after disassembling and define the best analysis conditions with an emphasis in reducing analysis times to an optimal minimum to maximize process efficiency, without compromising results.

Addressing this we present the development and validation of a technique for sorting whole Flat Panel Display Equipment (FPD) plastic housing using h-XRF. Samples were taken directly from the manual dismantling line at a plant located in the UK. The total concentration of Br and Sb in each sample was determined by two parallel analyses of 100 samples using h-XRF carried out at the base company and the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU). In addition, 10 samples were analysed for identification of specific BFRs by Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (GC/MS) at the University of Birmingham and the determination of total Sb was performed by Inductively Coupled Plasma/Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP/OES) at the University of the West of Scotland.

3.4 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Br and Sb measurements carried out at the base company were made using the VANTA™ X-Ray Fluorescence Analyser – C Series with rhodium (Rh) anode tube, supplied by Olympus UK, set on RoHS method. The h-XRF analyser was placed on a stand and remotely operated using the Vanta™ Desktop App placing the window of the analyser directly on the surface of the plastic. This allowed for triplicate analysis of each point to be performed without moving the analyser and analysing the exact same point on the sub-sample, generating consistent replicates.

3.4.1 Sample conditions

In WEEE manual dismantling facilities dust build up is significant, and in particular in CRT dismantling processes it is likely to contain trace levels of lead (Pb) (Lecler *et al.*, 2015; Ruan *et al.*, 2016; Papaoikonomou *et al.*, 2018; Gong *et al.*, 2020).

To determine whether the presence of dust settled on the casings has an impact on h-XRF results, 20 samples were randomly selected from the dismantling process and analysed using $t_{\text{analysis}}=30\text{s}$. Casings were placed on a stand leaving a gap of approximately 6cm of air behind the analysed area. The surface of the table was cleaned with a lint free cloth dumped in isopropanol at the start and end of the workday.

Figure 3.1 shows the layout of sample analysis on site.¹²

Each sample was analysed in two different marked areas where dust was most noticeable according to subjective judgement of the analyst. After completing the first analyses dust was removed using a lint-free electrostatic cloth, and the marked areas re-analysed three times under the same h-XRF operation conditions¹³.

Forty samples were analysed comprising 20 front casings and 20 back casings.

3.4.2 Optimal analysis time

In the use of XRF as a waste screening tool for compliance with regulatory requirements, it is of utmost importance to define the optimum analysis time as it directly correlates to the results accuracy. Several studies have assessed this parameter for Br determination with analysis times ranging from 10 minutes (Taurino *et al.*, 2014) to as low as 1 second (Jandric *et al.*, 2020). A study by (Aldrian, Ledersteger and Pomberger, 2015) applied on similar conditions to the present study with samples recovered from a manual dismantling process and measured in-situ, analysis times between 5 to 30s were evaluated. As for Sb determination by h-XRF, (Turner and Filella, 2017a) report the application of analysis times between 60 and 200s in a study on plastics in consumer products. All studies conclude that longer analysis time yield lower relative errors. However, there is no consensus on the times defined as optimal.

Our methodology for determining the optimal analysis time comprised of two stages as described below.

Figure 3.1 23" FPD plastic casing being analysed by the remotely operated VANTA™ handheld XRF Analyser (W: 8.3cm, L: 23.3cm, H:28.9 cm)

¹² Refer to **Appendix 5. Analysis conditions: Health and Safety protection measures** for complementary details on the actions taken.

¹³ Additional steps taken for method development regarding sample positioning and selection of the surfaces to be analysed are described in **Appendix 6. Additional steps taken for methodology development.**

Stage 1. Optimal analysis time determined on Certified Reference Material

As certified reference material three discs of 1mm, 2mm and 6mm thickness of BAM-H010/ABS were used. Each disc was measured to determine total bromine concentration. Three different analysis times were used: $t=10s$, $t=20s$, $t=30s$; 20 analyses were done for each analysis time. The discs were placed on a stand as depicted in **Figure 3.2** allowing to have 6cm of air behind the discs. These conditions were chosen as they would be most representative of those under which whole plastic casing measurements are done. The position of the disc was changed in between analyses to ensure that the same area was not analysed two consecutive times. Certificate for BAM-H010 indicates the bromine concentration to be (240 ± 21) mg/kg.

Figure 3.2 Diagram of sample stand for XRF analysis

Stage 2. Optimal analysis time determined on plastic samples

Samples were taken from twelve different FPD rear casings including different polymer types: ABS, HIPS, PC+ABS and PS. From each casing four/five sub-samples were extracted as discs of 6cm of diameter. Each sub-sample corresponds to a different area (**Figure 3.3**): Top Right (TR), Bottom Right (BR), Top Left (TL), Bottom Left (BL) and Centre (C).

Figure 3.3. Diagram indicating sampled areas on FPD rear casing

For h-XRF analysis the subsamples were placed on the stand (see **Figure 3.2**). Five different analysis times were used: 50s, 30s, 20s, 15s and 10s; 20 analyses were done for each analysis time.

3.4.3 FPD Plastic casings characterisation: Assessing Br and Sb homogeneity

To determine the homogeneity of Br and Sb concentrations in a casing, and within a FPD by comparing results for front and rear casings of the same item, sixty-eight samples (68 front and 68 rear casings) were analysed at 9 different areas: Top left, Top right, Bottom left, Bottom right, Centre on rear casings, and Top left, Top right, Bottom left, Bottom right on front casings.

The analyser was placed on the external surface of the sample in all cases, assuming the plastic to be a consistent thickness. Each individual point was measured in triplicate to ensure the reproducibility of the measurement for $t_{\text{analysis}}=10\text{s}$.

3.4.4 Validation of h-XRF results

For validation of Br measurements 100 samples previously analysed on site were sent to the Universität für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU – University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna) for their analysis with h-XRF using a different method. Details are described below.

3.4.4.1 *Technique 1: Industry grade h-XRF analysis*

XRF analyses were conducted as described in Section 2.

To build a reference curve for Br two granulated CRMs (EC680 and EC681) and a disc CRM made of ABS (BAM-H010) were used.

3.4.4.2 *Technique 2: Laboratory grade h-XRF analysis (BOKU)*

Samples were analysed for total Br content using laboratory-grade conditions by sample-specific h-XRF device calibration. First, the individual samples were placed in an h-XRF measurement chamber for consistency and to increase the reproducibility of the measurements. Each sample was analysed three times (sample triplicates) using a Soil mode of h-XRF spectrometer (XL3T950, Thermo Scientific Portable Analytical Instruments Inc., Tewksbury, USA). The analyser is equipped with a gold anode and measures at a maximum voltage of 50 kV and a maximum current of 100 μA .

The optimal measurement time for h-XRF is sample-specific and must therefore be determined empirically by evaluating the spectral peaks for the target elements (Jandric *et al.*, 2020). The maximum Br $K\alpha_1$ peak at 11.92 keV saturation was reached after $t_{\text{measurement}} = 32\text{s}$ therefore the measurement time was set at 35s.

3.4.5 Identification of individual Brominated Flame Retardants

XRF is a reliable method that does not require extensive and destructive sample preparation and is faster and less expensive than GC/MS. However, it only allows to determine total element concentration which is not a problem for Sb_2O_3 measurements as it is assumed all Sb comes from it.

However, for Br there is not a straightforward relation between its total concentration and the brominated compounds found in the polymer. To determine these compounds 10 samples were sent to the University of Birmingham for the identification and quantification by GC/MS of PBDEs, HBCDDs and TBBPA, considered to be the most frequently found BFRs in WEEE plastics (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2010; Jandric *et al.*, 2020; W.A. Stubbings *et al.*, 2021; Drage *et al.*, 2022). Details on the analysis methodology are presented in (Drage *et al.*, 2022).

3.4.6 Sb determination by ICP/OES

Total Sb content was determined in 12 plastic samples by ICP/OES (Perkin Elmer Avio500) after acid digestion. Three aliquots of 0.25g of plastic were accurately weighed and each transferred into a Teflon tube to which 3mL of H₂SO₄ (95%) were added. The tubes were placed in a hot block and the temperature was initially increased from room temperature (~19°C) to 120°C in 40 min and maintained for 30 min. Next, 3mL of HNO₃ (69%) and 1mL of H₂O₂ (30%) were added to the sample and held at 120°C for another 120 min. The digested solution was filtered through filter paper 0.45µm and collected in a 50mL volumetric flask. Solids retained in the filter were dried for 18 hours at 40°C and subjected to a second round of the same acid digestion process. Both digestion products were collected in the same flask and brought to volume with deionized water. To ensure total removal of solids that could interfere with ICP operation, the final solutions were filtered twice through filter paper or syringe filters 0.45µm.

3.4.7 Quality assurance/quality control

Total Br and Sb measurements carried out at the University of the West of Scotland were done using a h-XRF analyser calibrated by the manufacturer using suitable reference materials before the start of the study. During the study a daily check was performed at the beginning of the day by measuring in triplicate two Certified Reference Materials (CRM): EC680m and EC681m. Control charts were kept to identify deviations in the operation of the equipment or errors associated with the analyst. All values were found to be within the control limits of $\pm 3\sigma$, and no systematic patterns were observed indicating the process to be under control¹⁴.

Total Br concentrations measured by h-XRF at BOKU were determined based on the calibration curve derived from a Certified Reference Material BAM-H010 (Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung, Germany) provided in 6 different 1 mm thick ABS discs. The total material composition of the BAM-H010 Certified Reference Material (CRM) discs is shown in **Table 3.1**.

¹⁴ see **Appendix B. Vanta™ Control charts**

Table 3.1 Overview of six Certified Reference Material 1mm thick ABS plates containing RoHS regulated elements in different concentrations (BAM-H010)

BAM designation	Br concentration (mg/kg)	
	Mean	Method error
ABS-6	6	0.42
ABS-8	19	1.33
ABS-5	25	1.75
ABS-3	50	3.5
ABS-7	466	32.62
ABS-4	938	65.66

According to the information from the manufacturer, the BAM-H010 CRM is intended to be used as an analytical control, calibration, or recalibration sample for XRF analysis. Each disc was measured in quintuplet and based on the mean values of fluorescence intensity at the K α 1 peak of Br for different concentrations, a calibration curve was calculated using a linear regression model (see **Figure 3.4**).

For BFR analysis, quality assurance and control is described in (Drage *et al.*, 2022).

For ICP/OES analysis, a 28 multi-element standard (Fisher Scientific, UK) was used for calibration. Additionally, a blank containing 3mL of H₂SO₄ (95%), 3mL of HNO₃ (69%) and 1mL of H₂O₂ was subjected to the digestion process described in **Section 3.5.6**. No Sb was found above the detection limits in this blank therefore results were not corrected for residues.

Figure 3.4 Calibration curve based on six BAM-H010 1mm ABS discs

3.5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.5.1 Sample conditions

To determine the variation of Pb, Br and Sb concentrations after dusting, the median was calculated for each analysed point. The variation in concentration was determined as:

Equation 3-1 Br and Sb percentage of variation

$$\% \text{ variation} = \left(\frac{\text{Median concentration, dusty} - \text{Median concentration, clean}}{\text{Median concentration, dusty}} \right) \times 100$$

Negative values of %variation indicate a decrease in the concentration of the element after cleaning. Positive values indicate an increase of the same parameter.

Results for the 20 samples analysed are presented in **Figure 3.5** showing the element concentration variation for Pb, Br and Sb.

The low percentage of analysis points which presented an increase in Pb concentration is likely explained by cross contamination with the cleaning cloth or dust build-up on the analyser’s plastic window.

Figure 3.5 Element concentration percentile variation comparing Dusty vs. Clean conditions

A decrease in Br concentrations after cleaning was only observed in ~2.5% of the samples. Such a low value suggests that under the conditions used, the presence of dust does not significantly affect Br readings. Sb showed a behaviour consistent with previous knowledge of its association with BFRs (Harrad, Drage, M. A.-E. Abdallah, *et al.*, 2019; Strobl *et al.*, 2021) which was verified by the decrease in concentration after dusting as it was observed for Br.

3.5.2 Optimal analysis time

Stage 1. Optimal analysis time determined on Certified Reference Material

The optimal analysis time was determined by comparing %Accuracy (%) (**Equation 3-2**) for each of the discs at each analysis time.

Equation 3-2

$$\% \text{Accuracy} (\%) = \frac{[Br]_{\text{reference}} - |[Br]_{\text{measured}} - [Br]_{\text{reference}}|}{[Br]_{\text{reference}}} \times 100$$

A %Accuracy level of 90% was defined as acceptable for the application of this technique at an industrial scale. To define this, we analysed the impact of these acceptance levels on measurements for over 5,000 samples and concluded it would result in a sorting error of 0.4% (1 item every 250 could potentially be misclassified as recyclable).

For $t=10s$, the %Accuracy was estimated to be between 94.6% and 97.0%, depending on the thickness of the sample. Detailed results are presented in **Figure 3.6**.

Figure 3.6 Accuracy of Br concentration determined by XRF in CRM vs. Thickness for an analysis time of: A) 10 seconds, B) 20 seconds, C) 30 seconds. D) Compiled results for $t=10s$, $20s$ and $30s$.

Stage 2. Optimal analysis time determined on plastic samples

Based on (Jandric *et al.*, 2020), results for $t=50s$ were considered as reference when calculating the %Accuracy by **Equation 3-2**.

The %Accuracy for $t=10s$ is above 99% for Br, while for Sb percentages vary significantly between 84% for $[Sb] \sim 100$ mg/kg to 99% for $[Sb] \sim 10,000$ mg/kg. As an increase is observed with concentration and the range of interest is $\sim 8,400$ mg/kg, the %Accuracy level was considered to be approximately 99%. Detailed results are presented in **Figure 3.7**.

An analysis time of 10s was determined to be optimal within the following concentration ranges: $LOD < [Br] < 3,500$ mg/kg and $LOD < [Sb] < 10,000$ mg/kg.

Figure 3.7 Calculated Accuracy (%) vs Elemental concentration for Br and Sb (mg/kg) according to concentration range

3.5.3 FPD Plastic casings characterisation: Assessing Br and Sb homogeneity

Each area was measured in triplicate to ensure the reproducibility of the measurement for $t_{\text{analysis}}=10\text{s}$, considering 95% an acceptable percentual variation. Results were assessed to determine homogeneity of Br and Sb concentrations within each casing (front and rear) and item (whole FPD) and identify if there was an area with consistently higher concentrations that could be taken as reference for sorting. Concentrations were determined by calculating the median of the three analysis results. In front casings, the highest Br and Sb concentrations were most frequently found on the Bottom Left area, while in rear casings the highest concentrations were most frequently found on the Centre area. Results are presented in **Table 3.2**

Table 3.2 Frequency of highest Br & Sb concentrations per area analysed in Front and Rear FPD casings

	Area	Frequency (%)
FRONT CASING	Bottom Left	55.9
	Bottom Right	17.6
	Top Right	14.7
	Top Left	11.8
REAR CASING	Centre	60.3
	Bottom Right	11.8
	Bottom Left	10.3
	Top Left	8.8
	Top Right	8.8

3.5.4 Validation of h-XRF results: ring trial

The reference curve obtained for Technique 1 and the Calibration curve for Technique 2 are presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** To assess the correlation between both methods, we compared their results sets (**Figure 3.9**) and did a Pearson's test. As results indicate, there is a strong positive linear correlation between Br concentrations measured by Technique 1 and Technique 2 for the same group of samples in the range LOD <[Br]< 2,000 mg/kg.

Figure 3.8 Reference Curve for Method 1. Calibration Curve for Method 2 (see Section 3.4.4)

Figure 3.9 [Br] measured by Technique 1 vs. [Br] measured by Technique 2

Table 3.3 [Br] measured by Method 1 & Method 2 for samples with measured [Br] between 30 mg/kg and 2,050 mg/kg

ID	Polymer	[Br] (mg/kg)	
		Method 1	Method 2
1	HIPS	33	33
2	HIPS	184	44
3	HIPS	190	51
4	ABS	220	107
5	ABS	274	118
6	ABS	213	126
7	HIPS	219	145
8	PC+ABS	259	223
9	ABS+PET	271	276
10	ABS	306	281
11	PPE+SB	301	292
12	HIPS	325	318
13	HIPS	311	340
14	HIPS	292	380
15	ABS	471	470
16	HIPS	528	591
17	HIPS	896	901
18	ABS	1,238	997
19	HIPS	1,128	1,107
20	ABS	1,439	1,276
21	HIPS	1,448	1,453
22	HIPS	1,508	1,665
23	HIPS	2,044 ¹⁵	1,925

¹⁵ For Method 1, although values falling outside the calibration curve (> 1,340 mg/kg) presented in Figure 3.9 are recorded, as the threshold is defined at 830 mg/kg and considering that the higher the Br concentration, the more accurate the XRF results are, they are considered valid results as the error associated with the measurement will not impact on the classification of the item. The same is true for values obtained by Method 2 above 920 mg/kg.

We performed additional statistical analysis to further evaluate the correlation between the two methods.

First, we evaluated the normality of the distribution of the results for each method by doing a Shapiro-Wilk test and assessing the corresponding Q-Q plots. As hypothesis the following were considered: Ho) The variable extracted from the sample follows a normal distribution, Ha) The variable extracted from the sample does not follow a normal distribution. Results are presented below (Table 3.4 and Figure 3.10).

Table 3.4 Shapiro Wilk test results for Methods 1 & 2

Shapiro-Wilk test		
	Method 1	Method 2
W	0.786	0.834
p-value (2-tailed)	0.000	0.001
α	0.05	0.05

Figure 3.10 QQ Plots: A. Method 1, B. Method 2

As the computed p-value is lower than the significance level $\alpha=0.05$, one should reject the null hypothesis H_0 , and accept the alternative hypothesis, H_a . Results from Techniques 1 and 2 do not follow a normal distribution.

To determine whether the results follow the same distribution we did a Wilcoxon signed-rank test (two-tailed). We obtained a p-value of 0.039, lower than the significance level $\alpha=0.05$, therefore we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted that the distribution of the two datasets are different. For this test samples with results $<LOD/<LOQ$ (see **Section 3.5.4.1**) were not considered for the statistical analysis.

As the measurements by either method imply a certain degree of error which we are not able to quantify, neither of the methods provides an unequivocally correct measurement, so we assessed the degree of agreement between them by doing a Deming regression test and a Bland & Altman test (Mansournia *et al.*, 2021).

3.5.4.1 Limit of Detection/ Limit of Quantification (LOD/LOQ)

Technique 1: The analyser manufacturer reports a LOD of 1 mg/kg and 2 mg/kg for Br and Sb respectively, for two polymeric matrixes: PE (polyethylene) and PVC (Polyvinyl chloride) based on automatically selected beam conditions and an analysis time of 60 seconds ('Vanta Family X-Ray Fluorescence Analyzer. User's Manual (DMTA-10072-01EN-Rev.E)', 2019). No other reports were found for studies using the Olympus VANTA™ h-XRF analyser, therefore for our measurements those limits were considered:

$$LOD, Br = 1 \text{ mg/kg} / LOQ^*, Br = 3 \text{ mg/kg}$$

$$LOD, Sb = 2 \text{ mg/kg} / LOQ^*, Sb = 6 \text{ mg/kg}^{16}$$

*The limit of quantification was calculated as $3.3 \times LOD$ (Shrivastava and Gupta, 2011)

Technique 2: To define the signal detection limit (S_{dl}), the following formula was used (see **Equation 3-3**), while the limit of quantification was calculated as $3.3 \times S_{dl}$ (Shrivastava and Gupta, 2011).

Equation 3-3. Signal detection limit formula

$$S_{dl} = S_{reag} + 3\sigma_{reag}$$

$$S_{dl} = 5.45 + 3 \times 0.52 = 7.01 \text{ cps} \sim 10 \text{ mg/kg}$$

S_{reag} : Signal mean value of the blank sample; σ_{reag} : Standard deviation of the blank signal

$$LOQ = S_{dl} * 3.3$$

$$LOQ = 10 \text{ mg/kg} * 3.3 = 33 \text{ mg/kg}$$

¹⁶ These LODs are based on measurements made by the analyst

3.5.4.2 Deming regression test results

Results are presented in Table 3.5 and Figure 3.11 below.

Table 3.5 Deming regression results

	Value	Lower bound 95% (Mean)	Upper bound 95% (Mean)
Intercept	45.160	-5.944	96.263
Slope coefficient	0.995	0.892	1.099

Figure 3.11 Deming regression of Method 1 by Method 2

The value of the intercept is 45.160, and its confidence interval includes the value 0. This value measures whether the systematic difference of the two techniques is equal to 0. The slope coefficient is equal to 0.995, and the confidence interval includes the value 1. This means that the proportional difference between the two techniques is equal to 1.

We can confirm there are no systematic differences or proportional differences between both techniques.

3.5.4.3 Bland & Altman test results

As hypotheses the following were considered: Ho) The difference between the means is equal to 0, Ha) The difference between the means is different from 0. Results are presented in Table 3.6.

As the computed p-value is lower than the significance level $\alpha=0.05$, one should reject the null hypothesis H_0 and accept the alternative hypothesis H_a . The mean difference (Bias) is -42.504, meaning that on average Technique 1 measures 42.504 mg/kg more than Technique 2. Since we do not know the true value of the Br concentration for each sample, the mean of the two measurements is the best estimate we have.

Table 3.6 Bland & Altman test results

Difference	-42.504
t (Observed value)	-2.217
t (Critical value)	2.074
DF	22
p-value (Two-tailed)	0.037
α	0.05

The visual examination of the plot provides an assessment of the global agreement between both measurements.

The histogram (**Figure 3.12**) shows the differences are normally distributed. This was verified by a Shapiro-Wilk test. Therefore, we could expect 95% of the differences to lie between $\pm 1.96\sigma$, being these the limits of agreement. Thus, results measured by Technique 2 may be 138 mg/kg above or 223 mg/kg below those of Technique 1.

The limits of agreement are too wide to define the techniques as equivalent. However, considering $[\text{Br}] < 830$ mg/kg as a concentration threshold to sort POP plastics, all samples would have been classified under the same categories independent of the technique used. It must also be considered that the calibration curve for Technique 2 has a relatively low r^2 value although it was determined using a certified reference material made of a polymer found in our samples (ABS) and comprises 6 points including a blank. Conversely, for Technique 1 the used reference curve was determined from measuring two granulated CRMs of a type of polymer not found in our samples (low density polyethylene) and a BAM-H010 disc of ABS. Thus, neither of the curves considers the matrix effects, as the samples analysed are composed of a number of different polymers (i.e., ABS, HIPS, PS, PC+ABS, PMMA and PPE) (Bowers, 2019).

Figure 3.12 Bland & Altman test results (A. B&A plot; B. Histogram of the differences between Technique 1 and Technique 2)

3.5.5 Identification of individual Brominated Flame Retardants

Results of BFR identification and quantification are presented in **Table 3.7**. In four samples (4,7,8 and 10) high Br concentrations were determined by h-XRF, however according to GC/MS results the Br does not come from any of the targeted compounds. This could be that either: a) Br comes from a non-targeted brominated compound like TBP-DBPE, BEHTBP, BTBPE as it is known that for instance, in ABS, the use of BTBPE (1,2-bis(2,4,6-tribromophenoxy)ethane) as a substitute of traditional BFRs has been increasing (*Zhan et al.*, 2019); or b) the recoveries for these samples were considerably low. However, we were not able to verify or reject either of the hypothesis as we did not analyse samples for further BFRs and recovery rates (the amount of each brominated compound extracted from the sample by the technique used for analysis) were not determined for each sample. Recoveries were determined for PBDEs in two certified reference materials made of LPDE (Polyethylene) and PP (Polypropylene), with rates between 72-154% and 75-150%, respectively. No recovery rates were determined for TBBPA or HBCDD.

Table 3.7 BFR determination by GC/MS according to the method described in (Drage et al., 2022)

		Sample									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Polymer		ABS	HIPS	ABS	PS	PS	ABS	PS	HIPS	PC+ABS	HIPS
Year of manufacture		2004	2006	2006	2007	2007	2007	2008	2011	2015	2016
h-XRF (mg/kg)	Br	189	3,159	7,782	113,377	485	133,296	66,120	85,072	192	154,897
	Sb	66	656	2,177	34,104	272	32,784	13,644	15,491	<LOD	24,915
GC/MS (mg/kg)	BDE-28	<0.48	<0.48	<0.48	<0.48	<0.48	<0.48	<0.48	<0.48	<0.48	<0.48
	BDE-47	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24
	BDE-99	<0.21	<0.21	<0.21	<0.21	<0.21	<0.21	<0.21	<0.21	<0.21	<0.21
	BDE-100	<0.24	56	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24
	BDE-153	<0.24	9.59	0.26	<0.24	<0.24	0.29	0.4	<0.24	<0.24	<0.24
	BDE-154	<0.19	1.29	0.42	<0.19	<0.19	<0.19	<0.19	<0.19	<0.19	<0.19
	BDE-183	23.15	95.11	22.59	22.7	22.65	24.03	198.87	22.86	23.11	16.79
	BDE-209	1.29	2,000	4.66	8.48	1.32	52,000	<0.71	4.47	3.94	1.19
	TBBPA	460	650	15,000	25.71	3.95	11.56	17.11	75.13	16.92	3.26
	a-HBCDD	<0.37	120	<0.37	0.46	<0.37	<0.37	1.22	1.59	<0.37	<0.37
	b-HBCDD	<0.42	22.52	<0.42	<0.42	<0.42	0.52	<0.42	<0.42	<0.42	<0.42
	g-HBCDD	1.14	23.13	0.44	1.86	0.73	2.55	1.49	1.34	0.37	0.43
	ΣPBDEs	24.45	2,100	27.92	31.18	23.97	52,000	20.27	27.33	27.05	17.97
	ΣHBCDD	1.14	170	0.44	2.33	0.73	3.08	2.71	2.93	0.37	0.43

3.5.6 Sb determination by ICP/OES

A statistical analysis of ICP/OES results shows there are three samples with %RSD (relative standard deviation) higher than 20% (see **Table 3.8**). No common factor was found to explain this deviation, so it is assumed that it is associated with experimental aspects. These samples were not considered in further data analysis¹⁷.

A linear correlation between Sb measured by h-XRF ($[Sb]_{XRF}$) and Sb measured by ICP/OES ($[Sb]_{ICP/OES}$) was established with a R^2 value of 0.993 (see **Figure 3.13**). There is currently no certified reference material available for each of the polymers studied. Thus, it was not possible to determine extraction efficiencies and we were unable to do any further evaluation of the results as no relationships could be defined related to either the type of polymer or Sb concentration range.

¹⁷ Marked in bold in Table 3.7

Table 3.8 Sb concentrations determined by ICP/OES

Sample	Polymer	Average [Sb] (mg/kg)	SD	%RSD
1	ABS	3,015	142.6	4.7
2	ABS	53	6.6	12.4
3	ABS	23,258	654.3	2.8
4	ABS	2,343	5.6	0.2
5	ABS	691	123.0	17.8
6	ABS	35	30.8	87.5
7	HIPS	13,043	172.1	1.3
8	HIPS	533	1.2	0.2
9	HIPS	256	47.8	18.7
10	HIPS	15,037	660.0	4.4
11	PC+ABS	0	0.0	0.0
12	PC+ABS	15	9.4	64.0
13	PC+ABS	22	0.4	1.7
14	HIPS	26,578	1,094.2	4.1
15	HIPS	55	29.6	54.1

Figure 3.13 Correlation between Sb concentrations determined by h-XRF and ICP/OES

3.6 CONCLUSIONS

We performed a thorough characterization of whole FPD plastic casings by on-site h-XRF analysis, validated using reference materials and laboratory intercomparison. An assessment of the impact of analysis conditions related to dust setting on the samples showed that Br and Sb concentrations varied marginally when comparing before and after dust removal. Therefore, the presence of dust on the samples does not affect the validity of the h-XRF measurement for these parameters. As a good practice it is suggested that the area to be analysed is wiped with lint-free electrostatic cloth before the h-XRF analysis.

An evaluation of the accuracy of measurements depending on the analysis time allowed the determination of 10 seconds counting time as optimal within the following concentration ranges: LOD < [Br] < 3,500 mg/kg and LOD < [Sb] < 10,000 mg/kg, with a %Accuracy > 95%.

Comparing the homogeneity of Br and Sb distribution within and between front and rear casings it was established that for the front casing the highest Br/Sb concentrations were more frequently found in the bottom left area, while for rear casings it was the centre area. However, considering the %Accuracy levels determined for $t_{\text{analysis}}=10\text{s}$, we can conclude that in none of the cases would analysing only the centre or bottom left area on the rear and front casings respectively, have resulted in a false negative (sorting and item a recyclable when it should have been sorted as POPs or

POPs/HAZARDOUS). By further comparing results for both types of casings, we were able to determine that analysing the centre area of the rear casing is enough for sorting both samples with a %Accuracy level above 95%.

To validate our technique a ring trial exercise was conducted comprising 100 samples. Although the methods and equipment used were different, we obtained comparable and highly correlated results, demonstrating the suitability of the use of h-XRF for determining total Br in WEEE plastic samples in the LOD < [Br] < 2,000 mg/kg concentration range. We provide evidence of a need to develop suitable certified reference materials that include the types of polymers found in this matrix as it would allow to have adequate calibration curves and correct results accordingly. We are aware of a plastic standard suitable for h-XRF analysis having been developed by (Mans *et al.*, 2007), however, it is not commercially available.

As h-XRF measures total element concentrations and regulation establishes limit for specific compounds, we outsourced analysis for the determination of specific BFRs targeting those reported to be most commonly found in FPD plastics (Schlummer *et al.*, 2007; Abdallah *et al.*, 2017; Drage *et al.*, 2018, 2022; Kousaiti *et al.*, 2020; W.A. Stubbings *et al.*, 2021; Alghamdi, Abdallah and Harrad, 2022). Ten samples were sent for GC/MS determination of PBDEs, TBBPA and HBCDD, and considering the results obtained it is evident no definite conclusions can be drawn regarding a ratio between total Br and targeted BFRs concentrations. In two of the samples, the compound exceeding the legal thresholds was BDE-209, suggesting a conservative approach can be taken to consider all detected bromine is found as BDE-209 (DecaBDE) and that total Br concentration threshold could be set at 830 mg/kg. This is a reliable threshold that has been validated and is cost effective in terms of material segregation processes. There is low risk of false negatives and the risk of false positives is deemed acceptable in the industrial application of the technique. The cost/benefit of false positives does not justify additional cost of their identification and there is no danger to the environment by misclassification of material. In addition, it has been widely reported (Peacock *et al.*, 2012; Maris *et al.*, 2015; Drage *et al.*, 2018; Harrad, Drage, M. A.-E. Abdallah, *et al.*, 2019; Sharkey, 2019; Jandric *et al.*, 2020; W.A. Stubbings *et al.*, 2021) that the likelihood of h-XRF underestimating Br concentrations in plastic is virtually zero provided the measurement is performed under the proper conditions such as resting the analyser directly on the surface of the sample and its thickness is greater than the critical thickness required by the technique for the specific material.

Since 2015 there has been a downward trend in the levels of PBDEs present in FPD plastics. While high concentrations of Br have been detected in these plastics (>10,000 mg/kg), currently only 10-20% correspond to PBDEs. However, articles with PBDEs concentrations above 100,000 mg/kg may still be found in articles manufactured before the restrictions on the use of PBDEs came into force (Strobl *et al.*, 2021). This agrees with our result as regulated BFRs were found in samples manufactured prior to 2009, in line with banning of the use of certain PBDEs (i.e., tetra-BDE, penta-BDE, hexa-BDE and hepta-BDE) (Sharkey, 2019). Considerably high Br concentrations were

determined for later samples, however the low number of samples analysed and not having determined recovery rates does not allow us to make a definitive conclusion. This highlights the need to define regulatory limits based on elemental concentrations, e.g., total Br, which can be determined rapidly, easily, and inexpensively using h-XRF (Aldrian, Ledersteger and Pomberger, 2015; Guzzonato, Puype and Harrad, 2016; Jandric *et al.*, 2020).

A validation of Sb concentrations measured by h-XRF was attempted by an acid digestion and ICP/OES analysis. Results show concentrations determined by h-XRF are consistently higher than those determined by ICP/OES. However, even though a strong linear correlation was determined between both methods, the lack of a certified reference material and absence of confirmed recovery rates, does not allow definitive values to be reported. Considering the concentration limit for Br at 830 mg/kg, and that according to published reports (Harrad, Drage, M. A.-E. Abdallah, *et al.*, 2019; Sharkey, 2019) and our own observations Sb is found in concentrations between 33-55% of Br, in no case will an item be classified as HAZARDOUS without having been classified as POPs, therefore there is no risk of false negatives concerning the presence of Sb.

The results of our study provide comprehensive and highly detailed characterisation, demonstrating the reliability that can be achieved in categorizing hazardous/non-hazardous waste plastics from FPDs. This has implications for application by other waste management operators and policymakers in the more sustainable management of this waste stream. Furthermore, the defined methodology has great potential for the industry as it can be applied, with certain adaptations as needed, for the characterization of other WEEE plastics.

CHAPTER 4 The challenge of plastics management for WEEE recycling in the Global South: A case comparison between Europe and Latin America

This chapter is an accepted manuscript version of the below cited article:

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4.1 ABSTRACT

Countries with emerging legislation on waste of electrical and electric equipment (WEEE) but limited infrastructure, may find in other more robust systems the tools to develop adaptable and socioeconomically viable management schemes. Additives found in plastics of electronic goods such as brominated flame retardants (BFRs), whilst a component of a safety system, introduce characteristics which result in their waste being hazardous. Established and emerging regulatory systems need to implement legislation which impacts the management of WEEE to reduce risk to human health and the environment, while maximising opportunities for resource recovery of widely varying materials. To assess the context in developed and emerging regulatory systems, a baseline study was undertaken of WEEE plastics in Scotland and Uruguay. For the identification of BFRs in plastics, an internationally validated screening methodology using X-Ray fluorescence was adopted at different processing operations. It was observed that, using a threshold of 830 mg/kg for Br as BFR tracer, in Scotland more than 70% of the plastics would be recyclable while in Uruguay that fraction drops to 50%. These results and wider literature discussion highlight the impact that regulatory frameworks have on the quality and recyclability of recovered material. We identify future actions to be considered by policy makers for a more sustainable regulatory approach.

Keywords: Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) plastics / Brominated Flame Retardants (BFRs) / X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) / Legislation / Latin America / Europe

4.2 INTRODUCTION

Article 3 of the European Directive 2012/19/EU (*Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE)*, 2012) defines electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) as equipment which is dependent on electric currents or electromagnetic fields to work correctly. The circulation of such currents can lead to the generation of heat, so depending on how much is generated during operation, it could be necessary to take safety measures to prevent potential fires associated with the presence of combustible

materials such as plastics. To this end, EEE manufacturers must add compounds such as flame retardants (FRs) to prevent this hazard. These FRs can be halogenated or non-halogenated, and their presence is defined according to flammability standards. Among the halogenated FRs are brominated flame retardants (BFRs). Certain BFRs exhibit physicochemical and biological characteristics that have led to their classification as persistent organic pollutants (POPs) by the Stockholm Convention. In addition, there are other BFRs that, despite not having been classified within this group to date, are considered to be hazardous and/or ecotoxic, as is the case of TBBP-A (Tetrabromobisphenol A) widely used in EEE (Kousaiti *et al.*, 2020; Charitopoulou, Papadopoulou and Achilias, 2022; Okeke *et al.*, 2022).

The presence of flame retardants in polymers can be detrimental to the recycling of materials and thus inhibit progression towards a circular economy. For example, in the EU and the UK, according to (EU) Directive 2019/1021 (Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on persistent organic pollutants, 2019) and the POPs Regulations (The Persistent Organic Pollutants Regulations, 2007) respectively, any waste material containing POPs must be treated to ensure that the POPs are destroyed or irreversibly transformed. Certain consumer product waste streams, such as WEEE, contain both POPs contaminated plastics and recyclable plastics meaning these fractions must be separated before further recycling, or the total mixture must undergo treatment such as incineration, preventing any material recovery and increasing the carbon footprint of management operations. This highlights the need for technological options that allow efficient and effective separation to maximize the volumes sent for recycling. However, at present there are few techno-economically viable processes applicable at industrial scale, with most sorting being based on the “sink and float” method (Bill *et al.*, 2019; Keeley-Lopez, Turrell and Vernon, 2020).

Different techniques have been studied for the characterisation of plastics containing BFRs and Sb_2O_3 , a hazardous synergist often found in POPs contaminated plastics. To quantify BFRs, established methods include gas chromatography with electron capture detection or mass spectrometry as well as liquid chromatography with different coupled detectors (Aldrian, Ledersteger and Pomberger, 2015; Zhan *et al.*, 2019; Strobl *et al.*, 2021; Yli-Rantala *et al.*, 2021). In addition, the method generally used for the determination of Sb_2O_3 is the analysis by atomic spectroscopy such as ICP/OES after chemical extraction of Sb from the matrix. As this compound is the only source of Sb in plastics, all the Sb measured is attributed to it.

Technologies based on optical and spectrometric methods such as hyperspectral imaging (HSI) have also been developed. While the application of HSI is being implemented at industrial scale (Bonifazi, Fiore, Hennebert and Silvia Serranti, 2020; Bonifazi, Fiore, Hennebert and Silvi Serranti, 2020; Bonifazi *et al.*, 2021) it requires significant equipment investments that are not easily rationalised due to the low prices of virgin polymers.

These methods to determine compliance with regulatory limits are technically and economically demanding, and incompatible with the high material throughput required for effective processing at the industrial level. For this reason, during the past decade research has increasingly focused on more practical alternatives such X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) as a fast, non-destructive and effective technique, by which it is possible to rapidly determine total concentrations of Br and Sb as tracers of BFRs and Sb₂O₃, respectively (Sharkey, 2019; Alghamdi, Abdallah and Harrad, 2022).

There are no global regulations governing the use of flame retardants in consumer products, thus different countries impose different standards and restrictions. This variability can result in the use of certain formulations of FRs being permitted in some regions of the world but restricted in others. The Stockholm Convention centralizes the commitment of 186 countries (Idowu *et al.*, 2013) to regulate the treatment of persistent organic pollutants. However, a high percentage of the countries that have ratified the convention still do not have regulations that apply its requirements at the national level. On the other hand, in other countries although the Convention has been ratified and the corresponding regulations put in place, compliance is not regulated, and consumer products are manufactured without complying with the provisions of the Convention. This creates great complexity for international trade and the harmonization of safety regulations.

The WEEE waste stream contains various resources including precious metals (i.e., gold, platinum, copper, silver) as well as other valuable metals such as iron and aluminium. It is estimated that currently 30% of WEEE by weight is plastic material, of which 9% contain BFRs with only a small fraction corresponding to restricted BFRs such as octa-BDE or decaBDE (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2020). Because of restrictions imposed on their use, concentrations are decreasing. However, given that EEE is estimated to have a useful life of approximately 12 years, equipment containing these compounds are only now being disposed of (Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2020). Furthermore, BFRs are usually used in combination with antimony trioxide typically found in TV/Display equipment in concentrations of approximately 33-55% of the Br content (Allassali, Abis, *et al.*, 2019; Allassali, Picuno, *et al.*, 2019; Harrad, Drage, M. Abdallah, *et al.*, 2019; Haarman, Magalini and Courtois, 2020).

Consequently, WEEE is currently a global challenge with adequate handling, treatment and disposal being key to its sustainable management (Pan, Wong and Li, 2022). Worldwide, management of this unique waste stream is very diverse, with countries where collection systems are well defined, regulated and implemented, and countries where there is no legislation, control or management system (Forti *et al.*, 2020; Dias *et al.*, 2022).

To evaluate the impact of regulatory, economic, and environmental frameworks on WEEE management we selected two discrete regulatory domains in Latin America and Europe as case studies. Primary data was collected on the characteristics of WEEE plastics recovered in both cases. Display equipment was targeted as a category of appliances with significant BFR content (*The*

Persistent Organic Pollutants Regulations, 2007; Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on persistent organic pollutants, 2019) and higher penetration in Latin American markets (Dell'Onte, 2023). Being a comparable component stream of WEEE in both locations the objective was to gather compositional data on the plastic components. By using reproducible and validated characterisation, good primary data set could be used as a baseline to allow comparison of the impact of the national and global legal framework on the characteristics of the materials reaching the WEEE stream. This would also help to identify regulatory gaps that put global south countries at a disadvantage in terms of hazardous waste management. Additionally, it considers the validity of the current regulation while providing evidence for policy makers to support the development of new guidelines. It supports the adaption of the available infrastructure and technology and validates the potential of different management options.

4.3 CASE STUDY

In Latin America, the project "Strengthening national initiatives and improving regional cooperation for the environmentally sound management of POPs in electronic and electrical equipment waste", (PREAL) implemented by the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), has been underway since 2017 (Weghofer *et al.*, 2023). This project brings together 13 countries in South America, providing technical, legislative and management advice and financial support for the development of activities. One of the main objectives of this initiative is to strengthen WEEE management policies at the local and regional level for the protection of the environment by the appropriate management of hazardous waste and recovery of valuable raw materials.

In 2022, scientists representing PREAL countries were invited to share research advances in the framework of the E-Waste Academy Scientist Edition (EWAS) organized by UNIDO, in which the corresponding author of this article participated. In this instance, it was identified that even though as part of PREAL the countries involved had the opportunity to select technology for the characterization of WEEE with respect to POPs content, Uruguay was the only country that did not choose h-XRF technology¹⁸. Thus, the opportunity was identified to collaborate with the Ministry of Environment of Uruguay through the study of a particular stream of WEEE by applying a validated method of Br and Sb analysis by h-XRF as a starting point for the characterization of these wastes. The results of this study not only provide detailed knowledge on the composition of the waste stream, but also allow the evaluation of the suitability of the technology to be applied at scale.

Another challenge that Uruguay presents at the time of this study is the lack of specific legislation on WEEE and POPs. Consequently, it was also considered that this study would analyse the regulatory framework and contrast it with a comparable country in terms of population and geography, where the regulation is more developed and effectively implemented.

¹⁸ The method selected was sink/ float.

Europe, has led technological and regulatory development worldwide and frameworks consequently established provide a good reference base. The initial phase of our work was to assess the state of art for the application h-XRF for the determination of Br/Sb in WEEE plastics from the EU regulatory region (and included the UK and its devolved administrations). Subsequently the demographic characteristics were considered with the closest match to Uruguay (19 inhabitants/km²) being Scotland (70 inhabitants/km²). It should be noted that there are important socioeconomic differences resulting from the progress of economic development between Europe and the Global South. The selection of Scotland (rather than the UK) was feasible as this devolved region has regulatory responsibility for environment, education, health and economic development, whilst linked to systems across the UK, has independent responsibility for waste management.

4.4 MATERIALS AND METHODS

4.4.1 Samples for primary characterization

In Uruguay, the samples were obtained from a WEEE management company specialized in the treatment of diverse waste including non-ferrous metals recovered from different streams (e.g., electric motors, pipes, electric cables, car catalytic converters, electronic scrap and other waste), batteries and WEEEs including CRT monitors, personal computers, cell phones, home appliances, servers, peripherals and microprocessors among others (Company 1).

In Scotland the samples were taken from a display equipment recycling plant (Company 2). Focused on display equipment, this is one of the UK's leading recycling companies having successfully developed a validated methodology for the identification and sorting of TV plastic housing according to the Br/Sb content as tracers of POPs and hazardous compounds respectively (Aldrian, Ledersteger and Pomberger, 2015; Keeley-Lopez, Turrell and Vernon, 2020).

In both companies the back housings of the equipment were retrieved whole by manual dismantling, from which one sample of 6cm of diameter was cut for h-XRF analysis¹⁹. A total of 80 samples were collected comprising mainly black plastic. Relevant information on the equipment sampled in both companies is presented in **Table 4.1**.

¹⁹ Only Flat Panel Display equipment were sampled in both companies

Table 4.1. Relevant information on equipment sampled at Company 1 and 2

Sampled equipment characteristics	Company 1 (Uruguay)	Company 2 (Scotland)
Year of recovery	The equipment sampled was received from different Uruguayan companies from replacement, either due to change of technology or breakage over 2 years (between 2021 and 2022) comprising LED TVs and small display equipment (i.e., tablets).	The equipment sampled was received from different UK Compliance Schemes and UK Councils from both households and non-household sources. All the equipment was received on site during the year 2022 comprising LED and LCD TVs and monitors.
Year of manufacture	2007 - 2014	2007-2022
Origin	China and Mexico	China, Czech Republic, Poland, Turkey, United Kingdom

4.4.2 Statistical significance of selected sample size

In Uruguay the sample size was defined considering 5.6kt of display equipment waste were generated and assuming that the previously mentioned 0.11 ton²⁰ of plastic recovered from WEEE came from display equipment. Therefore, considering an average weight of 0.6kg per plastic casing results in 275 items recovered. With a confidence level of 95% a sample size of 80 items yields a margin of error lower than 10%. As for Scotland, considering an average weight of display equipment of 13kg and 164kt of plastic recovered, results in 27,000 units. Thus, for the same confidence level (95%) a sample size of 80 items has an associated margin of error slightly over 10% which is deemed acceptable for the purpose of the present study.

Regarding the differences in manufacture years between samples collected in both countries, it must be considered that there are limitations associated with the socioeconomic levels and WEEE collection infrastructure. On the one hand, in Uruguay the change of technology is delayed with respect Scotland, so that although the sampling was carried out during the same period the samples recovered in Uruguay date back to the year 2014 while in Scotland some items recovered were manufactured in the sampling year. On the other hand, given that in Uruguay there is no established system for the collection of WEEE, the items recovered correspond to those collected from public or private organizations which biases the sample to items generally similar and from the same year of

²⁰ tonne

manufacture because they were acquired at the same time. This is not observed in Scotland as the items recovered are not only from organizations but also from households.

4.4.3 Sample characterisation

Br and Sb were targeted as tracers of brominated flame retardants. The concentrations of these elements in each sample were determined using the VANTA™ X-Ray Fluorescence Analyser – C series with rhodium (Rh) anode tube using the RoHS method. All samples were analysed in the facilities of Company 2.

Each analysis was carried out in triplicate for consistency, with the window of the analyser placed directly on the surface of the sample without changing its position in between replications. A detailed description of the methodology and quality control/quality assurance used for the plastics characterization is included in (Chaine *et al.*, 2023).

4.4.4 Classification criteria

To classify items in POPs/non-POPs, the criteria presented in **Table 4.2** was followed based on Br and Sb concentrations. These criteria were set under the most conservative approach considering all detected Br is present as decaBDE with a concentration limit of 1,000ppm of this compound to classify an item as POPs waste. This limit was based on those defined in EU Directive 2019/1021 at the time of the study, and it corresponds to a Br concentration of 830 mg/kg.

Also based on EU regulations, the concentration limit for Sb was based on the Chemical Classification, Labelling and Packaging regulation (EC No 1272/2008), which establishes a concentration limit of Sb₂O₃ of 10,000 mg/kg to classify any waste as hazardous. This corresponds to an Sb concentration of 8,300 mg/kg.

Table 4.2. Sorting categories as defined in database according to total Br and Sb concentrations.

		Bromine (Br) concentration [mg/kg]	
		< 830	≥ 830
Antimony (Sb) concentration [mg/kg]	< 8,300	RECYCLE	POPs Waste
	≥ 8,300	Hazardous waste	POPs and Hazardous waste (POPandHAZ)

4.4.5 Literature review

A review of literature and legislation based on (Cronin, Ryan and Coughlan, 2013) was carried out.

4.4.5.1 WEEE scenario

Uruguay is a South American country with 3.3 million inhabitants unevenly distributed in 176,215 km² with over half of the population centred in its capital, Montevideo (Anuario Estadístico 2022, 2022). With a current GDP per capita of USD 17,313 (World Bank Open Data, 2023) the economic growth of Uruguay has fluctuated in the last two decades with a marked descent in 2020 as a result of the global pandemic. According to latest reports, in 2019 the rate of domestic WEEE generated was 12 kg per inhabitant (kg/inh) from which only about 4% were formally collected including 3.2 kg/inh of plastics (UNIDO, 2022). It is expected these numbers have not changed significantly to date since both the economic and waste management infrastructure have remained relatively unchanged. It is important to mention that the volumes of WEEE produced in Uruguay were not quantified directly but calculated using a globally accepted methodology defined by UNU (United Nations University) based on the volumes of EEE placed on the market and the average service life of each equipment category (Souteras *et al.*, 2020).

Scotland has a population of 5.5 million inhabitants (Population estimates for the UK, England, Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland - Office for National Statistics, 2021) in an area covering 77.933 km² and a GDP per capita of USD 45,251 ('GDP Quarterly National Accounts, Scotland 2022 Quarter 3 (July to September)', 2023), with an amount of domestic WEEE generated in 2019 considerably lower than that of Uruguay at 6 kg per inhabitants (Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA), 2023).

Table 4.3 presents the data for different categories of WEEE generated in for both Uruguay and Scotland.

Table 4.3. WEEE generated in 2019 by category (Uruguay and Scotland). Source: (Souteras et al., 2020), (Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA), 2023)

Category	Uruguay (ton/year)²¹	Scotland (ton/year)²²	Difference
Monitors, screens and display devices	5,613	3,563	Uruguay 36%
Large appliances ²³	7,016	9,421	Scotland 26%
Small appliances (includes small computer and telecommunications equipment)	14,987	12,691	Uruguay 15%
Temperature exchange equipment (including Fridges and Freezers)	9,313	7,233	Uruguay 22%
Fluorescent tubes and other light bulbs	677	151.6	Uruguay 78%

In Uruguay, an increase in consumption has been observed, which leads to an increase in the WEEE generated due to the calculation method used. Likewise, EEE are subjected to rapid technological changes, programmed obsolescence, and short lifespans as observed globally, recognising also rather low availability of repair options. It is also relevant to mention that the majority of recovery sources are mainly from the business sector rather than households according to the Ministry of Environment (Souteras et al., 2020).

As in most Latin American countries, due to the socioeconomic conditions, the disposal of EEE is buffered as there is a tendency to store unused equipment at home or to give it for reuse to others who perceive a value from it. It is common that once the decision to discard is made, informal systems are chosen because either there is no formal management structure available, or the user is not aware of the options available to them. In addition, informal managers generally provide financial compensation and door-to-door collection, while formal channels do not.

In a study carried out for the quantification of WEEE in Uruguay (Souteras et al., 2020), it was identified that the categories with the greatest influence on the total volumes are small appliances and temperature exchange equipment (including fridges, electrical heaters and air conditions

²¹ Predicted weights (tonnes/year)

²² Recorded weights (tonnes/year)

²³ Includes: washing machine, clothes dryers, dish washing machines, cookers, electric stoves, electric hot plates, etc. For further details on this category refer to Figure 1.1.

appliances among others). Contrary to what might be expected, monitors, screens and devices with screens, and small computer and telecommunication devices have decreased in the last decade. It is estimated that this may be associated with several reasons, such as the decrease in the weight of each individual piece of equipment or the replacement of technologies such as CRT monitors and televisions by devices with more than one function such as laptops, tablets, or cell phones. However, it is important to note that the WEEE calculation does not consider the replacement of CRT equipment by monitors and flat screens, which have a considerably lower weight. The amount of CRT equipment disposed of in Uruguay is likely to be higher than in Scotland considering the delayed shift in technology of developing countries (Clausen, Göll and Tappeser, 2017; Souteras et al., 2020).

Looking at the volumes of lamps, the behaviour for Uruguay is as expected with an upward trend, since in 2013 and 2015 agreements were signed by the central and local governments to promote the replacement of public and private lighting with LED technology (MVOTMA *et al.*, 2013; Oficina de Planeamiento y Presupuesto de la República, 2018).

Related to temperature exchange equipment, in Scotland most households, offices and education centres do not have air conditioning equipment, which in Uruguay due to the very high temperatures in summer, it is a common commodity (Shepherd, 2022; Dell'Onate, 2023). Additionally, fridges and freezers disposed of in Uruguay are likely to be older and therefore heavier than those disposed of in Scotland. There is no obvious explanation for the higher volumes of small appliances other than potentially lower quality equipment being put in the market in Uruguay resulting in a shorter use-dispose-replace cycle.

Looking at the amount of formally collected WEEE, the low percentage reported for Uruguay is explained by a poor regulatory system and a lack of infrastructure for the proper and formal management of this waste (UNIDO, 2022). However, even though Scotland has a well-established regulatory framework with the WEEE Directive having been in place since 2007, in discussion with SEPA (Scottish Environment Protection Agency) the lack of accurate data on waste generation related to illegal activity was also raised as a concern²⁴.

Due to the environmental and public health concerns associated with certain POPs/BFRs, efforts have been made to regulate or phase out their use. For example, Directive 2011/65/EU (RoHS) ('WEEE and RoHS in Latin America and the Caribbean', 2019) in the European Union and the United Kingdom restricts the use of certain BFRs, such as polybrominated biphenyls (PBBs) and PBDEs, in electrical and electronic equipment. Similar regulations have been implemented in other regions to reduce the environmental and health impact of electronic products (Liu *et al.*, 2023). In Uruguay, on the other hand, there are no legislative tools in place regulating the use of hazardous substances in consumer products, therefore the composition of EEE entering the market is not controlled. The

²⁴ R. Cowie, personal communication, March 2022

absence of regulation of material entering the market results in the presence of hazardous material, for which there is insufficient knowledge and infrastructure for treatment.

In Uruguay WEEE management is only covered as part of the Integrated Waste Management law introduced in September 2019.

Overall, while both Uruguay and Scotland have mechanisms in place for WEEE management, Scotland's system is more extensive and aligned with the European Union standards due to the former EU membership of the UK. However, Uruguay is also taking steps to improve its WEEE management practices, and the country's specific approach and progress is set to evolve in the near future.

4.4.5.2 WEEE management infrastructure

In Scotland, there are no reports on the volumes of WEEE plastics produced or managed at a national level. The main activities carried out after dismantling involve crushing and sink and float processes for separating the denser hazardous fraction (containing POPs) from the lighter non-hazardous fractions based on material densities alone (Keeley-Lopez, Turrell and Vernon, 2020). At the time of the study, it is reported by SEPA that no sites existed in Scotland to provide sorting services therefore all the recovered plastic is shipped to England. At a later stage, the non-hazardous fraction is sent for recycling whether in the UK or abroad, and the hazardous fraction is incinerated. This is due to the UK POPs regulation it must be treated to ensure POPs are either destroyed or irreversibly transformed.

According to 2023 records by the Environment Ministry of Uruguay, most WEEE operators cover mainly logistical activities, dismantling and recovery for treatment in the country or for export. It should be noted that there is considerable under-reporting of the quantities generated and recycled due to the prevalence of informal collection, dismantling and recycling activities, and existing infrastructure is concentrated mainly in Montevideo (Rodríguez-Bello and Estupiñán-Escalante, 2020).

As for plastics, the formally recovered fraction is exported for recycling in other countries, with reports of only 0.11 ton²⁵ having been exported to Europe and 0.09 ton²⁶ to Asia in 2019. Considering the total amount of WEEE produced during the same year was 39kt and estimating that 30% was plastic it is clear the formally recovered mass is negligible.

As for the detailed POPs content of materials in devices, information is very scarce, although POPs found in CRT and LCD monitors have been estimated to be 32 %wt and 0.15 %wt, respectively (MVOTMA, 2017). There are no treatment facilities in the country and POPs plastics are not being identified and segregated. The current practice is to send to landfill all WEEE plastics suspected of

²⁵ tonne

containing POPs (UNIDO, 2022). Alternatives are being evaluated for the treatment of this hazardous waste by the PREAL project (*PREAL project*, 2023). More detailed data on the characteristics of the plastics recovered would allow for improved management of this material.

4.4.5.3 *Treatment options in the Latin American region*

At the time of this study, most Latin American countries are in the process of developing standards for the management of WEEE plastics containing POPs, so the infrastructure available for their treatment is basic or non-existent depending on the country (UNIDO, 2022). Most WEEE plastics are exported outside the region as part of whole WEEE, mainly to the United States of America, Belgium, Japan, Korea, the Netherlands, Canada and China (Hernandez S., Ott and Lora Reyes, 2023). Common treatment options include mechanical and chemical recycling, as well as energy recovery processes. Mechanical recycling comprises sorting, shredding, and processing of plastic waste to produce raw materials that can be used to manufacture new products. Plastics with BFRs can be mechanically recycled if the BFR content is within acceptable limits. However, the presence of BFRs may limit the range of applications for the recycled plastic. Chemical recycling involves breaking down plastics into their monomers to produce new materials or fuels, this is the case of pyrolysis or gasification. These processes can potentially break down BFRs and other additives, enabling the recovery of plastic feedstock without the need for sorting or separation based on BFR content. However, chemical recycling technologies are still being developed and not widely available in Latin America. For instance, the PLAST2bCLEANED (PLAST2bCLEANED: Recycling process for Waste Electrical & Equipment, 2023) and NON-TOX ('NONTOX Project – NONTOX Project', 2023) projects funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, research and developed technology for the safe recycling of WEEE plastics by separately recovering the polymer, bromine and antimony trioxide fractions. Lastly, energy recovery allows plastic waste to be used for the generation of heat and/or electricity through its incineration. However, a minimum temperature of 850 °C and at least 2 seconds of gas residence time are required to break down BFRs (POPs destruction technologies, 2017) and minimize their release into the environment. Thus, it is essential to ensure that proper emission control measures are in place to capture and treat any pollutants emitted during the process.

In most Latin American countries, recovered items are disposed in landfill sites in many cases lacking any secure lining to prevent direct leaching of hazardous substances onto the ground, or incinerated in open spaces (uncontrolled burning)

4.5 RESULTS

4.5.1 Bromine and Antimony content: Classification

In Company 1 the 80 plastic samples showed to have some level of bromination with the highest being a LED TV manufactured in 2012. These samples also contained antimony however in a lower percentage with 22 samples (28%) showing non-detectable levels of Sb (LOD, Sb = 2 mg/kg).

In Company 2 out of the 80 samples, 19 showed Br concentrations below the detection limit (LOD, Br = 1 mg/kg) and the highest level corresponded to [Br]>10% wt. for samples manufactured between 2007 and 2017. As for Sb, the concentration was below the detection limit in 44 samples. All samples with Sb concentrations higher than those defined to classify an item as hazardous (8,300 mg/kg) simultaneously showed considerably high Br concentrations ranging from 5.2% wt. to >10% wt.

A summary of the median, maximum and minimum concentrations of Br and Sb measured for each Company samples are included in **Table 4.4** Error! Reference source not found..

Table 4.4. Bromine and Antimony concentrations determined by h-XRF.

		Median (mg/kg)	Max (wt. %)	Min (mg/kg)
Bromine (ppm)	Company 1	762	>15%	<LOD ²⁶
	Company 2	135	>10%	<LOD
Antimony (ppm)	Company 1	2,104	> 2.8%	53.5
	Company 2	<LOD	>6.2%	<LOD ²⁷

Based on the set concentration limits presented in **Table 4.2**, the percentages for each category were calculated. As summarized in **Figure 4.1** Error! Reference source not found., samples analysed in Company 1 more frequently exceeded the Br and Sb concentration limits. POPs waste in Company 1 accounted for 28% of the samples, while for Company 2 the percentage was significantly lower at 8%. As for the Recyclable plastics, in Company 1 this fraction corresponded to 49% of samples while in Company 2 the percentage rose to 73%. The POP and HAZ fractions were relatively similar in both cases.

²⁶ LOD = 3 mg/kg

²⁷ LOD = 6 mg/kg

Figure 4.1 Classification of plastics in Company 1 and 2 according to Br and Sb concentrations

4.5.2 Year of manufacture

Information on the year of manufacture (YoM) was retrieved from the equipment when available and/or visible. This data was collected for 42 samples in Company 1, and 79 samples in Company 2. **Figure 4.2** shows the number of items sampled by YoM, and whilst in Company 1 the highest number of items was manufactured in 2012 and 2014, in Company 2 this average moved closer in time to 2017-2020. However, the distribution of the number of items per YoM in Scotland is more evenly distributed ranging between 2007 to 2022.

Figure 4.2. Year of Manufacture of the equipment sampled

4.5.3 Amount of plastic Generated: an estimate

The amounts of plastic generated in 2019 in both Uruguay and Scotland, in each category were determined under the following considerations: i) 30% of the mass of waste monitors, screen and display is plastic, ii) the proportion (as %) determined for each classification category (**Figure 4.1**), and iii) the volumes of devices generated in 2019 in Uruguay and Scotland (**Table 4.3**). Results are presented in **Table 4.5**

Table 4.5. Estimated volumes of WEEE plastics generated in Uruguay and Scotland by category.

	ton/year ²⁸ (2019)		
	Uruguay	Scotland	Difference
Monitors, screens and display devices	5,613	3,563	37%
Plastic	1,684	1,069	37%
RECYCLE	821	775	6%
POPs	472	80	83%
POPandHAZ	390	214	45%

4.6 DISCUSSION

Although the percentage of items with known YoM in Company 1 was considerably lower, the compiled data shows a clear delay in equipment disposal in Uruguay compared to Scotland. The results for Company 1 (**Figure 4.3 A**), do not allow any conclusions to be made regarding the impact of HexaBDE, HeptaBde or HBCDD bans, as the majority of samples for which the YoM was retrieved had Br in concentrations higher than 800 mg/kg, indicating the likely presence of brominated flame retardants that could be attributed to POPs compounds (Hennebert and Filella, 2018; Sharkey *et al.*, 2018; Duflou *et al.*, 2020; W. A. Stubbings *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, a priori, bans on certain compound defined within the Stockholm Convention do not seem to be effectively applied when the destination market for the equipment lacks legislative tools to evaluate and penalize non-compliance.

The results for Company 2 (**Figure 4.3 B**) show a different scenario, where the ban on HeptaBDE and HexaBDE appears to have been complied with. The RoHS directive does not seem to have had the expected impact on POP/BFR concentrations as a considerable number of samples manufactured between 2011 and 2017 presented Br concentrations higher than 10%wt. While it may be argued that this Br was found as TBBP-A, a non-POPs brominated flame retardant, the marked

²⁸ tonne/year

descent in concentrations after the ban of decaBDE in 2017 suggests this was the brominated compound present up to that year.

Even though the volumes of waste display equipment yearly generated in both countries are relatively similar, there is an outstanding 83% difference between the estimated volumes of POPs plastics. However, the volumes of recyclable plastics are not that different as the lower percentage of samples classed under this category in Uruguay is compensated with the higher volumes of equipment produced. As for the POPandHAZ fraction, the volume of plastics sorted as such in Uruguay would be almost twice that of Scotland.

The presence of flame retardants in plastics derived from WEEE poses three great challenges: interference with recycling, emerging alternatives and global regulation. These are evidenced by the findings of this study which demonstrate the disproportionate amounts of hazardous materials being shipped to markets with low regulatory control, such as Uruguay. Moreover, it is likely this is the case in other parts the world where legislation is also limited. The fact that no global regulation exists, and each country/political community develops their own directly impacts international trade and harmonization of safety regulation. The latter, puts developing countries at a disadvantage which can be evidenced by high levels of FRs determined in consumer products put in the market.

We observed that the concentration of Br as a tracer of BFRs showed that in Uruguay WEEE plastics with Br concentrations above the limits established in the European regulations are very frequent and less than 50% of the plastic from display equipment could be recycled. On the other hand, in Scotland the data shows the positive impact of the regulatory system with more than 70% of the plastic being recyclable. It was also noted that although the Stockholm Convention banned the production and application of certain brominated compounds including flame retardants such as HBCDD, hexaBDE, heptaBDE and decaBDE, high concentrations of bromine continued to be found in equipment placed on the market afterwards. We must also highlight that bromine may be associated with non-POPs BFRs.

Table 4.6 illustrates the contrasts and potential advantages in the challenges faced in Uruguay and Scotland.

Table 4.6. Current challenges and opportunities for WEEE management: Uruguay vs. Scotland

Aspect	Uruguay	Scotland
Material	<p>Technological alternatives must be sought to cope with higher volumes of POPs and hazardous waste, and greater management costs. The weaker economic development suggests that the availability of the necessary technology will not be immediate or at an appropriate scale. This results in inefficient waste management or export, losing the opportunity to generate business and economic profit from the resource recovery.</p>	<p>With support from the government for innovation and development of new technologies, technically and economically feasible alternatives for the management of this unique waste are being sought</p>
Legislation	<p>It would be key to develop and enforce legislation that regulates the presence and management of POPs in WEEE plastics, to protect the environment and public health. Ongoing efforts should be focused on developing regulation that include control measures and restrictions on the characteristics of the products that are placed on the market.</p>	<p>Regulation puts pressure on waste managers who must make considerable investments to comply with a demanding legislation that does not focus on controlling the problem and only addresses the solution</p>
Waste management sector	<p>It is necessary to provide support to the waste management sector so that it can exist even after facing the higher management costs associated with complying with any standards.</p> <p>Promote eco-design ensuring the quality of the equipment put on the market as well as to allow users and managers to know what components it contains.</p> <p>Ensure the implementation of a system of collection, reuse, and recycling of end-of-life equipment.</p>	
Sorting criteria	<p>Screening of WEEE plastics for hazardous compounds such as POPs is a practice that should be widely adopted. One of the keys to the implementation of a screening technique at the industrial level is the speed of processing, thus, it is important to define the criteria (based on tracer elements, i.e., Br/Sb or chemical compounds) that will be used to validate the defined requirements and their implementation.</p>	
Sorting technology	<p>With relatively low investment and operating costs XRF would be a suitable, cost-effective option to consider with a capacity to determine Br/Sb concentrations in less than 10 seconds, with an approximate efficiency of 90% (Sharkey <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Chaine <i>et al.</i>, 2023). Further research on the effectiveness and efficiency of h-XRF for the identification of hazardous materials is still needed, as manufacturers are migrating the use of POPs-BFRs to non-POPs-BFRs.</p>	

4.7 CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated the challenges of considering the implementation of comprehensive worldwide regulation for WEEE materials. However, in its absence, countries can work to align their regulations, share scientific data, and collaborate in addressing common concerns related to FRs, which can lead to the development of international guidelines and standards that retain fire safety priorities yet minimize their potential environmental and human health impacts.

Our findings present evidence for regulatory authorities of developing countries such as Uruguay to have a validated characterisation of one of the most important waste streams within WEEE. This can underpin improvement of future WEEE regulations, promoting initiatives and investments to develop the necessary management infrastructure, including cross-border alternatives. Furthermore, the comparison with a similar European country such as Scotland, provides a reference case for the effectiveness of restrictions defined in that country on the management of WEEE, with evidence to encourage application of similar goals to improve public safety.

CHAPTER 5 CHARACTERIZATION AND STATISTICAL MODELING OF WEEE PLASTICS

5.1 BACKGROUND

To develop effective and efficient waste management plans, it is necessary to understand the composition and quantity of the waste in question. Proper management of WEEE plastics, including their correct sorting and subsequent recycling, allows for material recovery, thereby reducing not only the demand for petrochemical and other primary resources but also significant environmental and economic impacts. Various authors have reported on the lack of reliable information regarding WEEE generation. Studies on the characterization of plastics from this particular waste stream (Kohl and Gomes, 2018; Alassali, Abis, *et al.*, 2019; Belyamani *et al.*, 2021; W. A. Stubbings *et al.*, 2021; Jia *et al.*, 2022; Liu *et al.*, 2022) typically encompass those from different categories (e.g., mixed WEEE, monitors, fridges, mobile phones, personal computers, CRT TVs) but to date no reports focusing specifically on the characterization of display equipment waste plastics were found. However, it is highly relevant to examine these wastes individually since display equipment are generally treated separately due to the presence of hazardous components such as heavy metals and high concentrations of BFRs. Thus, the lack of knowledge about this material at its end-of-life poses a challenge that hinders proper waste management and material recovery.

WEEE plastics constitute 6.2% of the total post-consumer plastic recovered, with EEE manufacturers producing only 2% of the total recycled plastics according to reports from 2018 (Plastics Europe Deutschland and Messe Düsseldorf, 2019). In Europe, the most widely used technology in WEEE management is mechanical recycling. Recycled re-granules are still produced in considerably low volumes, highlighting the need for the industry to improve this aspect of management. Moreover, the combination of a steadily growing waste stream and changes in legislation requiring compliance with ever-higher recycling targets is driving the need to recycle plastics, in addition to the metals and glass present in WEEE, in order to meet these objectives. Achieving them is pivotal, requiring the entire WEEE management chain to function properly, integrating collection, sorting, and recycling (European Environmental Bureau *et al.*, 2023). The primary objective of this system should be the production of secondary resources. In recent decades, there has been a growing interest in recycling WEEE for resource recovery. However, predicting the volumes of waste that can be recovered and particularly the volumes of plastics that can be recycled remains challenging due to the presence of hazardous substances including persistent organic compounds, which add complexity to the recycling process, with sorting stages being pivotal.

The increasing generation of WEEE in the United Kingdom attracts particular attention from various stakeholders, including regulatory authorities, manufacturers, recyclers, and the general public. For instance, the UK has experienced a significant rise in the amount of display equipment introduced to

the market due to the transition from CRT to FPD initially, and later due to the shift from LCD to LED technology (*Timeline of Television*, 2014). Analysing and understanding the dynamics of consumption and waste generation is crucial for predicting future WEEE generation. While the FPD manufacturing industry in the UK does not stand out within the sector, the volume of display equipment items 'Placed On the Market' (POM) has been increasing over the last decade (Office for Product Safety and Standards and Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2023). In contrast, the corresponding weight of display equipment discarded and collected have been steadily decreasing (see **Figure 5.1**).

Figure 5.1. Evolution of wFPD and FPDs placed on the market (POM) in the UK. Source:

<https://www.gov.uk/guidance/regulations-waste-electrical-and-electronic-equipment>. Accessed: January 2024

Calculating estimates requires large volumes of high-quality information, so it is important to understand the intrinsic characteristics of the material which will in turn determine the potential recycling percentages. According to Article 38 of the UK's WEEE regulations (The Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Regulations 2013, 2013) the information gathered and reported regarding generation is recorded by weight and differentiated by stream, but being accounted for in tonnes does not allow each flow to be adequately understood, deeming decision-making difficult for managers and policymakers.

One of the main setbacks of the WEEE and POM recording system used by the UK authorities is evidenced here. As WEEE is recorded by weight, the number of items is unknown. Consequently, the number of items entering the FPD waste stream could be overestimated, since, for example, CRTs are accounted in the display equipment category and their weight is much higher than that of a FPD of the same screen size. Notwithstanding, CRTs are no longer marketed, so the comparison between POM and waste for this category remain somewhat incongruent when analysing trends. Aiming to bridge this gap with the information collected from a WEEE manager in the UK, it was determined that the trend in the number of FPD units is markedly increasing, while there is an almost

steady decline in CRT disposal. According to these trends, it is expected that FPD volumes will continue to increase in the coming years, and consequently, so will waste FPD (wFPD) plastics. Nevertheless, processes have not been developed that are effective and efficient enough for the classification of this material, and thus large volumes of WEEE plastics are still not being properly managed. For this reason, understanding the future of wFPD plastics generation and the recycling potential of this stream is very important for sustainable management.

The management of a particular waste must be adapted to its characteristics. Waste characterization is mostly used to assess future environmental impacts from the disposal of waste, and its results provide a simplified description of real waste behaviour, which can be used to choose strategies and technical solutions. Results from WEEE plastics characterization allow us to define the monetary return to entities according to the degree of separation, carry out quality controls, evaluate the performance of the sorting methodology, orient campaigns to impact public awareness, define action plans, and even predict the need for a determined scale of infrastructure.

WEEE management is complex, highlighting the need for tools to understand and if possible, estimate its future generation. Building predictive models in waste management is relevant for a variety of reasons (see **Figure 5.2**). Predicting waste generation can be an input to support responsible authorities in allocating management resources such as collection vehicles, recycling facilities and personnel. In addition, these models help assess the economic viability of waste management practices by forecasting waste generation and treatment volumes, allowing managers to evaluate the financial viability of the possible strategies, such as sorting, recycling, exporting and incineration. Overall, modelling could support enhancing the effectiveness, efficiency, and sustainability of waste management practices by providing valuable insights into future waste trends and facilitating informed decision-making.

Figure 5.2. Predictive modelling in waste management

This chapter presents a statistical study of the characteristics and volumes of wFPD plastics produced within a formal WEEE management system. As limitations, this study focused on Scotland, particularly on a wFPD equipment recycling plant that manages approximately 90% of the nation's FPD waste. As EEE is used in various sectors, such as services, industry, and households, the WEEE Regulations 2013 of the UK differentiates between the stream from private households (household WEEE) and that from other than private households (non-household WEEE). This study includes both streams.

Two statistically defined predictive models are proposed to estimate plastic volumes by polymer and category according to the type of FPD and the year of manufacture.

5.2 METHODOLOGY

5.2.1 Sampling

To carry out the characterization of wFPD plastics, sampling of LED and LCD back casings recovered from the production line of a recycling plant located in the UK was conducted over the course one year (June 2021 to June 2022).

To calculate the appropriate sample size, **Equation 5-1-1** was applied, considering the population (N) as the number of units of wFPD generated in 2019 in the UK. Values from the year 2020 were not considered due to the impact of the global pandemic on waste generation and management. The number of units of wFPD generated in the UK was calculated using an average weight of 12kg per item estimated based on the data on items and volumes managed at the subject recycling plant.

Equation 5-1. Sample size (Coxhram equation).

$$n = \frac{N * Z_{\alpha}^2 * p * q}{e^2 * (N - 1) + Z_{\alpha}^2 * p * q}$$

n: Desired sample size

N: Population size or universe

Z: Statistical parameter depending on the Confidence Level

e: Maximum accepted estimation error

p: Probability of the studied event occurring

q: (1-p) = Probability of the studied event not occurring

As statistical parameters, a confidence level of 99% (Z=2.579) was taken, and a probability of 50% was assigned since, due to the type of available information, the real probability of the event is unknown. This is standard practice with 50% reflecting the maximum level of variability that can be expected within the population.

Exceeding the calculated representative sample value, 1,000 samples of LED plastic casings and 1,000 samples of LCD were recovered whole from the dismantling process. The following information was recorded where available for all samples: TYPE (LED/LCD), YEAR OF MANUFACTURE (YoM), POLYMER, ORIGIN and SIZE. Additionally, the concentration of Br and Sb in each casing was determined by h-XRF measurement, and each item was classified by CATEGORY according to the criteria presented in **Table 4.2** as RECYCLE and NON-RECYCLE.

With the information obtained for the samples, a database was created. It should be noted that limitations were found regarding the lack of data on polymer, and year of manufacture. Data on polymer types was verified using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR).

5.2.2 Weight estimates

Due to the distribution of the plant's operations, it was not possible to weigh the samples collected. Therefore, a prorated weight was used for each sample depending on its size based on an average weigh of 1.5kg for a 32-inch casing.

5.2.3 Measurement of Br and Sb content

Br and Sb were selected as markers for BFRs. The levels of these elements in each sample were measured using the VANTA™ X-Ray Fluorescence Analyzer – C series (Rhodium anode tube) using the RoHS method. Every analysis was conducted three times to ensure consistency, positioning the analyser's window directly on the sample surface without altering its placement between repetitions. A comprehensive account of the methodology and quality control/quality assurance applied for characterizing the plastics is provided in **CHAPTER 3**.

5.2.4 Identification of polymer type using FTIR

FTIR is a spectroscopy technique that allows the identification of polymer type for qualitative characterization of samples. This technique provides a spectrum showing the IR radiation absorbed by specific functional groups characteristic of each polymer type according to the wavelength of the peaks. The spectra obtained were compared using the equipment's software for sample identification for which a subsample of 100 pieces was taken. Transmission measurements require a short pathlength that, depending on the material and shape of the sample, can be achieved by compressing it into a thin film. In this case, a shaving of less than 1mm thickness was extracted from each sample.

The instrument used for measurements was the PerkinElmer FTIR spectrometer UATR Spectrum Two. Since all selected samples are black due to the presence of carbon black (a pigment that gives the material that shade), the samples cannot be analysed in NIR (near infrared). Therefore, identification was done in MIR (mid infrared) ranging between 4000-600 cm^{-1} .

Before each measurement, the ATR diamond crystal was cleaned with methanol to remove any potential contaminating residue between samples that could affect the results. A background spectrum was run at the beginning of the analysis run to eliminate environmental effects.

The objective of this measurement was to verify that the polymer identified on the FPD casing is correct.

5.2.5 Characterization of the sample population

To estimate the characteristics of the sample population, a statistical study of the sample was conducted, evaluating the plastic casings of LCD and LED separately, and then the entire database containing both groups. The distribution for each relevant and measured variable was determined.

In a subsequent step, the dependence of variables was evaluated to determine if the main ones are independent regarding certain variables used as factors. In this case, for evaluating the independence between two qualitative variables, the Chi-square test was applied to generate a cross-tabulation providing the necessary probabilities for analysis.

All statistical tests were performed with a 95% confidence level, utilizing IBM SPSS statistical software version 29.0 for all analyses. ('IBM SPSS Statistics 29 Core System User's Guide', 2021)

If the p-value of the Chi-square independence test is significant ($p < 0.05$), with a confidence level of 95%, the hypothesis of dependence between the variables can be accepted. Conversely, if the p-value is not significant ($p > 0.05$), with a confidence level of 95%, the hypothesis of independence between the variables is accepted. Hypothesis testing was conducted on the entire database.

To evaluate the necessary capacity for managing wFPD plastics and the amount of potentially recoverable and recyclable material, data reported by the UK's Environment Agency for Display Equipment waste and POM items were used (Office for Product Safety and Standards and Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2023).

5.2.6 Calculation of Categorization Models

To understand the relationship between qualitative nominal variables such as Polymer, Type or Category and Size, a binary logistic regression was performed (Harrell, 2015; Wilson and Lorenz, 2015; Connelly, 2019). The objective of this statistical analysis was to obtain an adjusted estimation of the probability of occurrence of the dependent variables and to obtain a model that allows for classification of an item according to either Category or Polymer based on its Size and Type.

Important points to consider:

- Significance of the model's Chi-square in the omnibus test: If significance is less than 0.05, it indicates that the model helps explain the event, i.e., the independent variables explain the dependent variable.
- Cox and Snell's R-squared, and Nagelkerke's R-squared: Indicates the portion of the variance of the dependent variable explained by the model. There are two R-squared in logistic regression, and both are valid. It is customary to say that the portion of the dependent variable explained by the model ranges between Cox and Snell's R-squared and Nagelkerke's R-squared. The higher the R-squared, the more explanatory the model, i.e., the independent variables explain the dependent variable.
- Overall percentage correctly classified: This percentage indicates the number of cases that the model can predict correctly. Based on the regression equation and data, a prediction of the value of the dependent variable (predicted value) is made. This prediction is compared with the observed value. If it matches, the case is correctly classified. If it does not match, the case is incorrectly classified. The more cases it correctly classifies (i.e., the predicted value matches the observed value), the better the model, and the more explanatory it is. Therefore, the independent variables are good predictors of the event or dependent variable. If the model correctly classifies more than 50% of cases, the model is statistically accepted.

The objective of logistic regression is to express the probability of the event in question occurring as a function of certain variables, which are presumed to be relevant or influential. In this case, it is presumed that both the type and size of the FPD determine the type of plastic and/or the category of the casing. If the modelled event is represented by Y (the dependent variable), and the k explanatory variables (independent and control) are designated by X1, X2, X3,...,Xk, the general equation (or logistic function) is:

Equation 5-2

$$P(Y = 1) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\beta_0 - \beta_1 X_1 - \beta_2 X_2 - \beta_3 X_3 - \dots - \beta_k X_k)}$$

where $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_k$ are the parameters of the model, and \exp denotes the exponential function.

Logistic regression models (both binary and multinomial) are based on probabilities, specifically on logarithms. To determine if independent variables are related to the dependent variable, coefficients β are first calculated.

Another way to express the coefficients β is through odds ratios. Logistic regression relies on odds ratios because they are standardized measures that allow comparing the level of influence or strength of independent variables on the dependent variable. Independent variables are on different scales and are also expressed in logarithms, thus requiring standardization of the scales. The way to standardize and thus compare independent variables is through odds ratios (ORs), here called exponentials of β (e^β).

5.2.6.1 How to interpret the results?

The e^β are ORs and can be compared to understand which variable has more influence or is more strongly associated. ORs indicate the strength of the relationship. The further away from 1 it is, the stronger the relationship. To compare the exponentials of β with each other, those that are less than 1 must be transformed into their inverse or reciprocal, i.e., divide 1 by the exponential of β (but only when they are less than 1).

When e^β is greater than 1, it indicates that an increase in the independent variable increases the odds of the event occurring (i.e., the dependent variable). When e^β is less than 1, it indicates that an increase in the independent variable reduces the odds of the event occurring (dependent variable). The further away from 1 it is, the stronger the relationship between the two variables. (Szumilas, 2010)

For the study of cross variables and the estimation of a predictive model, the Polymer variable was considered binomial: BTD (Butadiene based) and PLS (Polystyrene based). This decision was made considering the types of plastic found in the samples and their distribution. Of the 9 types of plastic identified, 5 are BTD with a contribution of 45.21% to the total. On the other hand, 2 types correspond to PLS with a contribution of 54.79%. The remaining two types of plastic are based on polyphenylene ether (PPE) and have a contribution of 0.46% of the total, considered negligible for the purposes of the calculations. Similarly, the model was calculated to determine the category of the item according to the type and size of the sample. In this case, the Category variable was also considered binomial: RECYCLE and NON-RECYCLE. This decision was made considering that both POPs plastics and POPS&HAZ plastics are not recyclable (NON-RECYCLE).

The independent variables selected were Type (LCD/LED) and Size, understanding that they are two easily identifiable characteristics in the item to be recycled, which will allow for a more effective application of predictive models.

5.3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.3.1 Sampling

The sample size was calculated considering the established parameters of weights and percentages of FPDs in the Display Equipment stream and **Equation 5-1-1**.

Based on confidential information obtained from a WEEE recycling company in the UK, the following parameters were obtained:

Table 5.1. Estimated parameters used for calculating FPD waste volumes.

Average weight of display equipment (including CRT and FPDs)	12 kg
%FPD units in Waste Display Equipment stream	75%
Average weight of FPD casing (in accordance with (Peeters <i>et al.</i> , 2015))	2.5 kg

Figure 5.3 presents a calculation diagram and indicates the calculated sample size value, equal to 716 units. The decision was made to take 1,000 samples of LCD and LED respectively, understanding that a sample larger than strictly necessary to characterize the target population will be better representative of that population and will hence provide more accurate results.

Figure 5.3. Scheme indicating how the sample size was calculated from EA reported volumes.

5.3.2 Results of FTIR Analysis

Given the nature of wFPD plastics, it was anticipated to find polymer blends (W. A. Stubbings *et al.*, 2021) which was verified in the majority of the samples according to the similarity percentages obtained for the polymers identified by FTIR. However, there were in every case dominant polymer types masking the characteristic peaks of other polymers present in the blend. In 92% of the cases, the polymer type identified in the sample corresponded to that predominant as determined by FTIR analysis, for the remainder 8% the polymer identified did not match that determined. **Figure 5.4** shows coincidental spectrums for a number of samples of HIPS and ABS respectively.

Figure 5.4. FTIR results for samples corresponding to A: HIPS and B: ABS

5.3.3 Cross variable analysis

Chi-square test results are presented in **Table 5.2** indicating dependencies between targeted variables. The variables which test yielded $p > 0.05$ were Category & Type ($p = 0.055$) and Size & Polymer ($p = 0.062$), thus variables were determined to be independent.

Table 5.2. p values from chi-square tests

	YoM	Type	Size	Category
Type	0,000			
Size	0,000	0,000		
Category	0,000	0,055	0,015	
Polymer	0,000	0,000	0,062	0,000

5.3.4 Characterization

A characterization of wFPD, including both LCD and LED items, was conducted.

Figure 5.5 presents the analysis of Type vs. YoM. The predominant share of recovered devices date between the years 2006 and 2019, with a higher contribution from LCDs for the period between YoM 2006 and 2012 and a marked shift to LED prevalence from 2013 onwards. This aligns with and reflects the marked turning point in technology of the devices introduced to the market, as LEDs surged from 2.8% (YoM: 2012) to 8.4% (YoM: 2013) while LCDs dropped from 6.4% to 3.6%, respectively. Furthermore, the observed evolution for YoM allows to estimate the lifespan of different technologies considering the year of manufacture and the year of disposal (2021-2022), being 12-15 years for LCDs (27.8% of the recovered bulk) and 3-8 years for LEDs (35% of the recovered bulk). This information could in turn facilitate the estimation of the volumes of equipment by technology type that will be generated in a future period of time; however, both the volumes of POM equipment and recovered wFPD strongly depend on consumer behaviour, a variable that has not been considered in the present study.

Figure 5.5. Percentages by Year of Manufacturing

The distribution by Size and Type (**Figure 5.6**), and frequency of Sizes by YoM were also studied (**Figure 5.7** and **Figure 5.8**). Most of the recovered equipment are larger than 40 inches (54%), with a marked difference in the contribution of LED equipment to this percentage (67%). This fraction is followed by items in the range 32 inches \leq Size < 40 inches, with both adding up to 76% of the total. An increase in the contribution of LED items to each fraction is confirmed as the size of the equipment increases, indicating not only a change in technology but also a change in the design and characteristics of the end-of-life items. Looking at the evolution of size by Type and YoM, the more

recently manufactured the LED equipment the larger it is, while for LCD equipment the opposite trend is confirmed. This directly results in a reduction in the weight contribution of LCD plastics to wFPD plastics, with compensatory contribution from LED plastics.

Figure 5.6. Percentages by Size and Type

Figure 5.7. Frequency by Size and YoM (LED)

Figure 5.8. Frequency by Size and YoM (LCD)

Figure 5.9. Distribution of Category by Year of Manufacture

Regarding the distribution of Category by YoM (Figure 5.9), only in the years 2011 and 2012 the percentage of non-recyclable plastic was higher than that of recyclable. Considering at this time regulation was in place and should have been complied with, this observation could be explained by the presence of non-POPs/BFRs.

Furthermore, it is important to consider that 2011 was a year with relatively low number of items sampled (56) which could lead to a false conclusion regarding categorization.

Assessing the polymers found it was evidenced that among the recovered casings, the larger fraction corresponds to three main types of polymers: HIPS, PC+ABS, and ABS, with 43%, 33%, and 15%, respectively (**Figure 5.10**). Within each of these groups, there are different contributions depending on whether the recovered casing comes from LED or LCD equipment. For both HIPS and PC+ABS, the contribution of plastics from LEDs is markedly higher, being 10% greater for HIPS and 12% greater for PC+ABS. In contrast, for ABS plastics, the difference in contribution of LCD casings is higher by 14%.

Figure 5.10. Percentages by Polymer and Type

Evaluating the category of the recovered material according to the technology of the equipment from which it was recovered, it can be said that the trend is the same in both cases, with around 70% of the material classified as RECYCLE. Consequently, the contributions of both types to the total of recovered plastic as RECYCLE and NON-RECYCLE do not vary significantly, being 36% and 16% for LEDs, and 32% and 16% for LCDs, respectively. See **Figure 5.11**.

Figure 5.11. Percentages by Category and Type

Analysing the category according to the polymer type (**Figure 5.12**), for HIPS, the largest fraction corresponds to non-recyclable plastic based on its Br content (60%), while the opposite trend is observed for the other types of polymers, with PC+ABS showing the largest fraction of recyclable plastic (97%).

Figure 5.12. Category distribution by Polymer

This information is particularly relevant when evaluating the volumes of recovered wFPD plastic that could be effectively recycled using the processes currently employed in the UK, mainly based on sink & float technology. Density separation is based on the premise that brominated plastics are denser, so by adjusting the mediums density, the light fraction (recyclable) can be separated from the heavy fraction (non-recyclable). Cut-off densities of 1.0 kg/l and 1.1 kg/l are used (see **Figure 5.13**). The data on densities by polymer presented in **Table 5.3** confirms that by using this criterion,

there is an overlap between the densities of brominated HIPS and ABS, and potentially recyclable PC+ABS, leading to the conclusion that the latter will be lost in the non-recyclable fraction, despite it being predominantly material with acceptable Br levels for recycling.

Figure 5.13. Diagram of WEEE plastics recycling by Sink & Float technology. Adapted from (Haarman et al., 2023)

Table 5.3. Polymer density range. Source: (Haarman et al., 2023)

Polymer	Density (kg/l)
HIPS	1.04-1.06
ABS	1.05-1.10
Cut-off	1.10
PC+ABS	1.12-1.20
ABS (BFR)	1.15-1.23
HIPS (BFR)	1.15-1.18

Considering the data of FPDs discarded as waste reported by the EA for the UK in 2021 and 2022 (see Table 5.4) and the parameters defined from information collected from an FPD manager, the volumes of material generated were calculated according to the characteristics and percentages determined from this study for the representative sample.

Table 5.4. Estimated Display Equipment Waste generated in the UK. Source: (Office for Product Safety and Standards and Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2023)²⁹

	2022	2021
Household DE waste (ton)	40,428.148	39,706.859
Non-Household DE waste (ton)	20.572	6.542
Total DE waste (UK) (ton)	40,448.720	39,713.401

The results of estimating the characteristics of potentially recoverable material from wFPD are shown in **Table 5.5**. The same percentages for each category were considered for both years.

Table 5.5. Estimated classification of wFPD plastic generated in the UK.

	FPD (units)		FPD (tonne)	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
RECYCLE	1,737,461	1,769,632	4,865	4,955
NON-RECYCLE	744,626	758,414	2,085	2,124
HIPS	1,216,223	1,238,742	3,405	3,468
ABS	370,824	377,690	1,038	1,058
PC+ABS	675,376	687,881	1,891	1,926
Other polymers	219,665	223,732	615	626

As previously exposed all PC+ABS plastic would have been wrongly classified and thus not recycled but incinerated. Therefore, this would yield a yearly loss of close to 2kt of this polymer.

Finally, the impact of the Origin (country where the equipment was assembled) was assessed. Regarding Category (**Figure 5.14**) the country of origin with the higher portion of non-recyclable material was the United Kingdom (64%) which is likely related to the fact that most recovered items from this Origin (62%) were manufactured before 2009 when restrictions on POPs/BFRs had not yet been introduced or enforced. Slovakia is on the opposite end with only 6% of non-recyclable material with a larger contribution of items manufactured after 2009 (68%).

²⁹ On this table, the notation “ton” corresponds to “tonne”

Figure 5.14. Distribution of Category by Origin

5.3.5 Binary logistic regression: predictive models

5.3.5.1 Model for predicting the variable POLYMER

The coding of the dependent variables is presented in **Table 5.6**. The regression starts with Step 0. In **Table 5.7** it is shown that 34.8% of the values are missing in the regression due to data not being presented on the sample, and items not being selected for FTIR either. Therefore, the entries selected for the analysis correspond to 65.2% of the data (1,305 individuals).

Table 5.6. Dependent variable coding (Polymer)

Original value	Internal value
BTD	0
PLS	1

Table 5.7. Summary of case processing (Polymer)

Cases		N	%
Selected cases	Included in the analysis	1,305	65.2
	Lost cases	695	34.8
	Total	2,000	100.0
Non-selected cases		0	0.0
Total		2,000	100.0

Table 5.8 is the classification table for Step 0 of the regression, which is not significant in interpreting the model but it shows that without adjusting the model, a prediction of 54.8% would be obtained.

Table 5.8. Classification table. Step 0. (Polymer)

		Predicted		Correct %
		BTD	PLS	
Observed	BTD	0	590	0.0
	PLS	0	715	100.0
Global %				54.8

These tables illustrate the baseline model including the independent variables. This model's predictions rely solely on the most frequently occurring category in the dataset, which is PLS at 54.8%. Consequently, the model consistently predicts PLS, as this polymer type is the most prevalent among the items. The global percentage row indicates that this prediction method is accurate 54.8% of the time.

Table 5.9 shows the variables in the predictive equation for Step 0 including the constant β_0 . The relevant information provided in this table is the significance level (0.001) indicating the model is a statistically significant predictor; however, it would be accurate less than 55% of the time.

Table 5.9. Variables in the equation. Step 0. (Polymer)

	β	Standard Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(β)
Constant	0.192	0.056	11.936	1	0.001	1.212

The regression continues to Step 1 where the independent variables are included. To determine whether the new model improves the baseline, an Omnibus test is conducted using Chi-square tests to evaluate the difference between the log-likelihoods (-2LL) of both models. In the Omnibus test, SPSS provides three entries: Step, Block, and Model. The Model compares the new model with the baseline, while Step and Block are relevant only if the independent variables are added to the model incrementally or hierarchically. In a staged model-building approach, these rows would compare the -2LLs of the latest model to the previous version, assessing whether each new set of independent variables improves the model. However, in this analysis, all independent variables were combined into a single block, resulting in only one step. Consequently, the chi-square values for the step, block, and model are identical (**Table 5.10**). The Sig. values are $p > 0.001$, indicating that adding the explanatory variables did not enhance the accuracy of the model.

Table 5.10. Omnibus test of model coefficients. Step 1. (Polymer)

	Chi-squared	df	Sig.
Step	1.630	2	0.043
Block	1.630	2	0.043
Model	1.630	2	0.043

In this case, the Chi-square test yielded a significant results ($p < 0.05$) suggesting the independent variables explain the dependent variable well.

Subsequently, three summary measures of the models were obtained to evaluate their overall validity, as presented in **Table 5.11**.

Table 5.11. Summary of the model. (Polymer)

Logarithm of the likelihood -2	Cox and Snell R-squared	Nagelkerke R-squared
1,795.492	0.391	0.422

The model summary table indicates the portion of the variance in the dependent variable explained by the model. There are two R-squared values in logistic regression, typically the portion of the dependent variable explained by the model ranges between Cox and Snell R-squared and Nagelkerke R-squared. In this case, it would range between 39.1% and 42.2%. The overall percentage that the model can predict is 54.8%, thus the model is accepted. In the omnibus test, if there is a significant reduction of -2LL for the new model compared to the baseline, this indicates the new model is better at explaining the event. However, in this case proceeding to Step 1 did not improve the model's adjustment thus the test was stopped at this point. The accuracy probability in the PLS cases is 100%.

Table 5.12 presents the variables in the equation:

Table 5.12. Variables in the equation. Step 1. (Polymer)

	β	Standard Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(β)	95% confidence interval for EXP(β)	
							Lower	Upper
Size	0.005	0.006	0.762	1	0.043	1.005	0.993	1.017
Type	0.162	0.130	1.552	1	0.013	1.176	0.911	1.517
Constant	-0.250	0.369	0.458	1	0.199	0.779		

Both variables are significant; therefore, they good predictors of the dependent variable.

The model for predicting the Polymer (BTD/PLS) based on the size and type of FPD is as follows:

Equation 5-3. Predictive model of the variable Polymer by Type and Size

$$POLYMER = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(0.250 - 0.005 * \text{Size} - 0.162 * \text{Type})}$$

The variable "Type" can take the following values: 1 for LCD and 2 for LED.

If the result of applying the equation is closer to 0, then the plastic is BTD; if it is closer to 1, the plastic will be PLS.

5.3.6 Model for predicting the variable CATEGORY.

The variable Category is binomial. The coding of the dependent variables is presented in **Table 5.13**.

Table 5.13. Dependent variable coding (Category)

Original value	Internal value
RECYCLE	0
NON RECYCLE	1

In **Table 5.14** it is shown that 0% of the values are missing in this regression. **Table 5.15** shows that without adjusting the model it would correctly predict the CATEGORY in 69.9% of the cases.

Table 5.14. Summary of Case Processing (Category)

Cases		N	%
Selected cases	Included in the analysis	2,000	100.0
	Lost cases	1	0.0
	Total	2,000	100.0
Non-selected cases		0	0.0
Total		2,000	100.0

Table 5.15. Classification table. Step 0. (Category)

		Predicted		Correct %
		RECYCLE	NO RECYCLE	
Observed	RECYCLE	1,398	0	100.0
	NO RECYCLE	602	0	0.0
Global %				69.9

Table 5.16 presents the variables for the regression equation at Step 0.

Table 5.16. Variables in the equation. Step 0. (Category)

	β	Standard Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(β)
Constant	-0.883	0.048	332.832	1	0.000	0.414

The regression continues to Step 1, the Omnibus test.

In the omnibus test (**Table 5.17**), the chi-square test yielded a result >0.05 , indicating that the model does not help explain the event, i.e., the independent variables do not explain the dependent variable well.

Table 5.17. Omnibus test of model coefficients. Step 1. (Category)

	Chi-square	df	Sig.
Step	0.225	1	0.093
Block	0.225	1	0.093
Model	0.225	1	0.093

Subsequently, three summary measures of the models were obtained to evaluate their overall validity.

Table 5.18. Summary of the model (Category)

Logarithm of the likelihood -2	Cox and Snell R-squared	Nagelkerke R-squared
2,495.129	0.200	0.260

In this case the Cox and Snell R-squared and Nagelkerke R-squared explain that the portion of the variance in the dependent variable explained by the model will vary between 20% and 26%. This model's predictions rely solely on the most frequently occurring category in the dataset, which is RECYCLE at 69.9%. Consequently, the model consistently predicts recycle, as this category is the most prevalent among the items. Thus, the overall percentage that the model can predict is 69.9%, thus the model is accepted. However, proceeding to Step 1 did not improve the model's adjustment in this case either, thus the test was stopped at this point. The accuracy probability in the RECYCLE cases is 100%.

Table 5.19 presents the variables in the equation:

Table 5.19. Variables in the equation. Step 1. (Category)

	β	Standard Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(β)	95% confidence Interval for EXP(β)	
							Lower	Upper
Size	-0.001	0.005	0.017	1	0.095	0.999	0.990	1.009
Type	-0.051	0.109	0.216	1	0.142	0.950	0.767	1.177
Constant	-0.785	0.288	7.442	1	0.006	0.456		

The model for predicting the CATEGORY of the item (RECYCLE/NON-RECYCLE) based on the size and type of FPD is as follows:

Equation 5-4. Predictive model of the variable Category by Type and Size

$$\text{CATEGORY} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(0.785 + 0.001 * \text{Size} + 0.051 * \text{Type})}$$

Since both variables have sig.>0.05 and they are not good predictors of the dependent variable.

5.3.7 Predictive models

The statistical parameters of the predictive models show that in both cases the square R values are very small indicating low probabilities of accuracy. For the Polymer prediction model, predicting

PLS plastics is relatively good with a 54.8% probability of accuracy, while for predicting BTD it would not with 0% probability of accuracy. It is important to mention that for the development of the model, information was not available for 100% of the samples, but rather polymer data was available for 65% of the cases affecting the effectiveness of the proposed model.

On the other hand, although the category prediction model has a higher accuracy probability of 69.9%, it is also not good since the test is not significant and the square R values are too small.

This indicates that the POLYMER and CATEGORY variables are not predictable from the SIZE and TYPE of item.

5.4 OUTCOMES

The characterization study conducted provides insight into the trends in technological evolution and the materials present in the FPD equipment. According to the retrieved information, the average lifespan of LCDs ranges between 12 to 15 years, while LEDs have a shorter lifespan, ranging between 3 to 8 years. This underscores the growing issue of planned obsolescence, suggesting that the volume of waste generated by these devices will continue to escalate as they are disposed of more frequently. Additionally, as technology shifts, there is a noticeable change in the size of recovered items, with LCDs predominantly smaller than 32 in, while LEDs tend to be larger than 40 in. Despite these shifts, there is no apparent impact on the types of polymers found, with both LCDs and LEDs exhibiting a higher contribution of HIPS plastics.

The fractions of recyclable and non-recyclable material are similar in both cases, with the recyclable fraction hovering around 70%. Moreover, from the analysis of polymers, it is evident that there is a stark difference in recyclability among different types. HIPS, comprising the largest fraction, predominantly consists of non-recyclable plastic due to its bromine content. Conversely, other polymer types, particularly PC+ABS, exhibit a high proportion of recyclable plastic. This insight is crucial when assessing the potential for recycling recovered wFPD plastic, especially concerning current recycling processes in the UK reliant on sink & float technology. However, the overlap in densities between brominated HIPS and ABS and potentially recyclable PC+ABS poses a challenge, leading to the loss of PC+ABS material in the non-recyclable fraction. This finding highlights the need for further research to optimize both sorting and recycling technologies and improve efficiency in polymer separation, including flame-retardant plastics. As industry currently relies solely on mechanical recycling, looking into chemical or hybrid recycling technologies could be key for avoiding incineration and thus material loss. In addition, feedback to manufacturers is essential for enhancing recyclability by encouraging material choices that align better with existing recycling technologies and reduce reliance on additive that could in turn be non-recyclable. There is also significant scope for manufacturers to increase the use of recycled plastics in their products, potentially substituting virgin materials with recycled alternatives, especially for polymers like PC+ABS with high recyclability

potential. This shift would support a more circular economy by diversifying waste outcomes, reducing material loss, and reducing the dependence on incineration through alternative recycling technologies.

Estimating the volumes of material generated from discarded FPDs based on the findings of this study, it is apparent that the misclassification of PC+ABS plastic would result in significant annual losses, nearing 2 kt. Therefore, there is a pressing need to address this issue to enhance recycling efficiency and minimize waste. The estimation indicates that approximately 5 kt of recyclable plastic were generated from wFPDs in 2022. Nevertheless, the accuracy of this calculation remains unverifiable due to the WEEE registration method employed by UK authorities, wherein traceability is compromised once segregated items are dispatched for further management and are mixed with plastics from other waste streams. This underscores the pressing need for products to provide comprehensive details about their components, especially considering that some items lack information while others contain erroneous data, potentially leading to significant negative impacts on waste management practices. The implementation of the Digital Product Passport, currently under deliberation in the EU, is deemed essential for mitigating this issue supporting circular economy strategies.

This study evidences the complexity inherent in predicting the type of material derived from WEEE in a straightforward manner. Despite having access to an extensive database, this proved to be insufficient for developing binary representative models through the proposed statistical analysis. Consequently, it is emphasized that statistical studies for constructing predictive models must incorporate a broader range of variables influencing both the characteristics of the material (i.e., country of manufacturing, make) and the generation and disposal of WEEE, such as collection geographical area, volumes generated per area and waste producer behaviour.

CHAPTER 6 Cracking the code: improving WEEE plastics modelling using Python

6.1 BACKGROUND

The development of accurate predictive models for WEEE plastics is crucial for efficient recycling and resource management. An initial attempt based on binary logistic regression showed the statistical parameters of the predictive models had substantial limitations. Specifically, the R^2 values were considerably low, reflecting a minimal proportion of variance in the dependent variables that can be explained by the model. This results in unsatisfactory probabilities of accuracy, thus compromising the reliability of its predictions.

For the POLYMER prediction model, a moderate prediction accuracy was observed for PLS plastics with a 54.8% probability of predicting this polymer type correctly. However, the performance of the model for predicting BTD is severely inadequate, with a 0% probability of accuracy. This marked contrast highlights significant inconsistencies within the model's predictive capacity. One critical issue contributing to this inefficacy is the incomplete dataset: polymer data was available for only 65% of the samples, thereby undermining the model's robustness.

Similarly, the CATEGORY prediction model, despite showing a higher accuracy probability of 69.9%, is also unsatisfactory as the test is not significant and the R^2 values are too low. The lack of statistical significance of the test indicates that the model does not reliably predict category outcomes from the given variables. These findings demonstrate that the POLYMER and CATEGORY variables are not adequately predictable from the other variables considered in the dataset by a logistic regression binary model. This inadequacy suggests that the relationships between these variables and the rest of the dataset are either too weak or too complex to be captured by those modelling techniques.

Given these challenges, it was decided to employ Python tools and the Random Forest algorithm for several compelling reasons. First, Python is renowned for its robust data handling capabilities and extensive libraries tailored for machine learning and data analysis. Libraries such as scikit-learn provide powerful, easy-to-use tools for implementing complex algorithms like Random Forest, enabling more sophisticated and flexible modelling approaches (Parmar, Katariya and Patel, 2019).

The Random Forest algorithm is well-suited for this task due to its ensemble nature, which combines the prediction of multiple decision trees to improve accuracy and control over-fitting. This method is notably helpful for handling datasets with missing or incomplete information, as it can maintain performance by using the strengths of individual trees to compensate for data gaps (Hapfelmeier and Ulm, 2014). Moreover, Random Forest can handle large datasets with higher

dimensionality and intricate variable interactions, making it ideal for the complex WEEE plastics dataset.

By exploiting the Random Forest algorithm, this work aims to enhance the predictive power of the models focusing on the CATEGORY outcome. The ability of this method to provide information on the importance of variables can also help to identify the factors that most influence the results. This insight is crucial for refining the dataset and focusing on the most predictive variables, thereby improving overall model performance. The Random Forest model was trained using several deep features extracted from 80% of the training dataset to train the trees, while the remaining 20% was set aside as test dataset used to validate the performance of the model. Each decision tree within the forest is independently generated and each node is split based on a randomly selected subset of features. The forest is expanded to a predetermined number of trees, which contributes to high variance and low bias in the model. The final prediction is determined by averaging the class probabilities assigned by all individual trees (Belgiu and Drăguț, 2016).

Overall, the decision to transition to Python tools and the Random Forest algorithm stemmed from the need to overcome the limitations of the initial models. The low R^2 values and accuracy probabilities highlighted critical shortcomings in the previous approach, primarily due to incomplete data and insufficient variable predictability. By utilizing the advanced capabilities of Python and the robust, ensemble nature of the Random Forest algorithm, the aim was to develop more reliable and accurate predictive models for WEEE plastics, ultimately contributing to more effective recycling and resource management strategies.

In addition, the opportunity was seized to evaluate the applicability in another country, in this case in Spain, of the predictive model developed based on WEEE plastics recovered in Scotland. Amongst the main reasons to pursue this is that the comparison would provide insights into the material entering the market and in time the waste collection systems, as it was evaluated in the case study between Scotland and Uruguay. By testing the model in a different context however under the same regulatory conditions, the impact of other factors such as consumers, manufacturers or retailers' behaviour can be assessed to determine their influence on the model's predictive accuracy. Furthermore, this process would aid in determining the robustness and generalizability of the model, ensuring it is not overly tailored to the Scottish specific conditions. Additionally, such testing highlights the importance of data quality and availability, which can vary significantly between countries, thereby emphasizing the need for comprehensive datasets to improve predictive accuracy.

6.2 METHODOLOGY

6.2.1 Sampling

6.2.1.1 Training and Test dataset

For the initial dataset samples were collected according to the methodology described in **Section 5.2.1**. The data used for training the classification model was generated between 2021 and 2024 at an FPD recycling company located in Scotland. The database comprising 15,006 samples includes information on different characteristics of the FPD plastic retrieved directly from individual items' casings (i.e., Date, Type, YoM, Polymer, Size, Origin and Manufacturer) as well as information produced by analysing the plastics to determine their Category (i.e., RECYCLE or NON-RECYCLE). It is important to highlight over 85% of this extensive database was produced as part of the site's daily operations where information on Polymer was not retrieved. The information included on this variable was collected during the course of 1 year between 2021 and 2022 as part of a KTP Project.

Table 6.1 presents the number of non-null values for each variable. As can be observed, the limiting variable was Polymer.

Table 6.1. Number of non-null values found in the training data set

Variable	Non-null values
Date (of sampling)	15,006
Type (LED/LCD)	15,006
YoM (Year of Manufacture)	13,505
Polymer	1,294
Size	14,995
Origin (Country)	9,544
Manufacturer (Make)	15,006
Category (Recycle/Non-recycle)	15,006

6.2.1.2 Validation dataset

To verify the applicability of the model and to check that the model does not fit just the initial dataset, a validation test was carried out. Two databases were used for this test. On the one hand, a dataset was formed by sampling 100 items over the course of two weeks at the Scottish site and another 100 samples were taken at the Spanish site. Both databases were used separately and combined for the validation and adjustment of the hyperparameters. In both cases all the information displayed on the samples was manually retrieved and each was later analysed by h-XRF to determine Br and Sb concentration as tracers of POPs-BFRs, and by FTIR to determine the polymer type.

6.2.2 h-XRF and FTIR analysis

The measurement of Br and Sb was carried out using the VANTA™ X-Ray Fluorescence Analyser – C Series with Rh anode tube, applying the validated methods described in **CHAPTER 3**. The classification criteria were that presented in **Table 4.2**.

The identification of polymer type was by FTIR as described in **Section 5.2.4**. In addition to the samples initially analysed as presented in **Section 5.3.2**, the two sets of samples used for validation were fully analysed as well.

6.2.3 Model development

The development of the wFPD plastics classification algorithm was conducted using the Cognitive Project Management for AI Methodology (*SPSS Modeler Subscription*, 2021) (**Figure 6.1**). The primary stages encompassed process understanding, data understanding, data pre-processing, modelling, and model evaluation. Each phase in the creation of the classification algorithm was interconnected, with each step both influencing and being influenced by previous and following steps. This iterative approach allowed for continuous feedback and refinement of the process. For instance, the initial models for the classification algorithm revealed the significance of specific variables like POLYMER, while also identifying that variables such as DATE contributed to overfitting without providing additional insights into the process or data. These findings were instrumental in refining the preprocessing and modelling stages, which will be discussed in further detail in subsequent sections

Figure 6.1. Cognitive Project Management for AI Methodology (Source: <https://www.ibm.com>)

6.2.4 Data Pre-processing

The main Python libraries used for data loading, transformation, and extraction were Pandas and NumPy. Initial models constructed with the raw data using Random Forest indicated a significant dependence of CATEGORY on the POLYMER variables. Consequently, all rows with missing data for these variables were excluded, resulting in a dataset reduction to 1,294 rows. Although this led to the exclusion of a substantial portion of the data, the alternative would have involved imputing the missing data. However, imputing more than 10% of the data is generally deemed inappropriate as it can introduce statistical inaccuracies.

To evaluate the representativeness of the 1,294 items **Equation 5-1** was applied to estimate the sample size representative of the whole database (15,006) yielding an n value of 160 items greatly exceeded by the 1,294 items left to develop the model.

Furthermore, in the preliminary decision tree ensemble models, the variable DATE demonstrated a relevance of up to 20%. Given that this variable merely denotes the date on which each sample was recorded, it logically should not play such a significant role in the model. Additionally, when applied to the validation datasets, this preliminary model exhibited very low accuracy, indicating that the model was overfitting the training dataset. Consequently, the DATE variable was excluded from the model training process.

The categorical variables, MANUFACTURER, POLYMER and TYPE were converted to integers through the scikit learn ordinal encoder function [[OrdinalEncoder — scikit-learn 1.5.0 documentation](#)]. The target classification label was encoded with the label encoder from scikit-learn [[LabelEncoder — scikit-learn 1.5.0 documentation](#)] (Preprocessing data, 2024), where NON-RECYCLE was translated to 0, and RECYCLABLE to 1.

Missing values were imputed with K-nearest neighbours (KNN) algorithm using scikit-learn's KNN imputer [[KNNImputer — scikit-learn 1.5.0 documentation](#)] (Imputation of missing values, 2024). K-nearest neighbours is a non-parametric classifier and predictive tool based on the 'k' nearest point in the training dataset. Key characteristics of KNN include its reliance on distance metrics, typically Euclidean, its non-parametric nature, and its learning approach where KNN bypasses model training and makes predictions directly based on the dataset at hand. In the present study KNN was configured with 4 neighbours and uniform weights meaning regardless of their distance from the target value, each of the 'k' nearest neighbours contributes equally to the prediction.

6.2.5 Model selection and evaluation metrics

The model was built mainly using the scikit-learn library [[scikit-learn: machine learning in Python — scikit-learn 1.5.0 documentation](#)] (Getting Started, 2024).

There are several classification models, from simple, such as Gaussian Naïve-Bayes, to more complicated models such as ensembles of decision tree algorithms. The best-performing algorithm according to the established metric scores (Precision, Recall, f1 score and Accuracy) was the Random Forest classifier by scikit learn (Petkovic *et al.*, 2017).

The confusion matrix is a table that allows the performance of the classification algorithm to be evaluated by presenting how the model's predictions compare with the actual results (Marom, Rokach and Shmilovici, 2010).

For this study as the model is based on a binary label the matrix is represented as a table of four quadrants (two rows and two columns). Each row represents the actual instances and each column

the predicted ones, allowing an assessment of the accuracy of the model by showing the counts of true (positive and negative) and false (positive and negative) predictions.

True positive cases are those where the model correctly predicted the positive class (RECYCLABLE), while true negative cases are those where the model correctly predicted the negative class (NON-RECYCLE). Conversely, false positives are cases where the model predicted as a positive class when it was truly negative, and false negatives are cases where it predicted as a negative class when it was truly positive. This is represented in **Figure 6.2**.

Figure 6.2. Confusion matrix

From the values of the confusion matrix, the accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score performance metrics mentioned above can be studied.

The classification evaluation metrics used for individual label performance were the following (Goutte and Gaussier, 2005):

▪ **Precision:** is defined as the number of correctly identified members of a class divided by the total instances where the model predicted that class. In the present study it is defined as:

- For Non-Recyclable (0): $(\text{True Negative} / (\text{True Negative} + \text{False Negative}))$
- For Recyclable (1): $(\text{True Positive} / (\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive}))$

A high precision indicates that the model has a low false rate, meaning that when the model predicts a class, it is often correct. In contrast, low precision indicates a high false rate, suggesting that many of the model's positive predictions are incorrect.

▪ **Recall:** is the proportion of correctly identified members of a class to the total number of actual members in that class. In the present study it is defined as:

- For Non-Recyclable (0): $(\text{True Negative} / (\text{True Negative} + \text{False Positive}))$
- For Recyclable (1): $(\text{True Positive} / (\text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative}))$

A high recall indicates that the model can successfully identify most true instances minimizing the number of false instances. Conversely, if the recall is low it means the model is missing many of the actual positive instances and gives a higher number of false instances.

▪ **f1 score:** this metric combines Precision and Recall and it is defined as the harmonic mean of these two variables. It measures the model's accuracy determining how many times did the model make a correct prediction across the dataset. It is a quick method to determine whether the classifier is genuinely effective at identifying members of a class, or if it is taking shortcuts, such as labelling everything as a member of a predominant class.

▪ **Accuracy:** this metric indicates the fraction of correct predictions the model yields. It is defined as: $(\text{True Positive} + \text{True Negative}) / \text{Total}$

For the combined classification evaluation, the overall accuracy was considered.

6.2.6 Model training: Train and test dataset split

The dataset was divided into train and test subsets using the train-test-split function of scikit-learn for model selection, using a 0.75 training ratio and stratification on the Y axis (CATEGORY) data. As the data contained a higher ratio of RECYCLABLE samples data rebalancing methods such as SMOTE were considered but were not optimal. Thus, a stratification method was used to counteract the imbalance in the dataset. Once processed, the dataset had a similar ratio of RECYCLE to NON-RECYCLE samples.

Issues of overfitting emerged in the validation dataset, despite the favourable metrics obtained in the test dataset. This occurred mainly because the dataset did not include a sufficient number of entries to construct a robust rebalancing algorithm that could effectively prevent overfitting problems.

6.2.6.1 Hyperparameter tuning

The parameters of the function that determine how the algorithm is constructed are called Hyperparameters, and each dataset and case benefits from different hyperparameter setting. At an

initial stage, before acquiring the validation dataset, a Grid Search, using scikit-learn's GridSearchCV, was used (*Tuning the hyper-parameters of an estimator*, 2024). The resulting hyperparameters were a maximum depth of 10 (number of levels in each decision tree), minimum samples per leaf of 2 (number of samples that must be present in a leaf node representing a final decision or output in the tree), minimum samples per split of 2 (number of samples required to split an internal node, controlling the creation of nodes and sub-nodes in the tree) and 150 estimators (number of trees in the forest, determining how many trees does Random Forest use for this predictive model).

Both validation datasets were used independently and in combination for parameter tuning and model validation. Through this validation process, the optimal minimum samples per leaf and per split were determined to be 4 and 3, respectively. The values for the number of estimators and maximum depth were kept from the grid search process, as they provided the best classification scores. A higher minimum samples per leaf value ensures that leaves contain more samples, thereby making the tree more robust and less prone to overfitting. Additionally, a higher minimum samples per split value results in simpler and more interpretable trees.

6.2.6.2 Cross validation

Cross validation offers insight on the model accuracy by building the model on a set number of different train-test splits of the dataset and evaluating each iteration (*Cross-validation: evaluating estimator performance*, 2024). This aims to determine whether the model is overfitting on a particular train-test split and offer accuracy metrics on the set number of different train-test splits. This outputs accuracy scores for every model constructed with different iterations.

A cross validation was performed with scikit-learn `cross_val_score`, where five rounds of the dataset were established.

6.3 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

6.3.1 h-XRF and FTIR results

In the initial dataset of 15,006 entries, 28% of items were identified as NON-RECYCLE with Br concentrations above 830 mg/kg. Furthermore, looking at the reduced database determined by the entries with data for the variable POLYMER (1,294 items) the percentages vary slightly in favor of the non-recyclable material (36% NON-RECYCLE). **Table 6.2** present detail on percentages by category for each dataset. In no case was the Sb concentration higher than 8,400 mg/kg for items with Br concentration lower than 830 mg/kg, so all items classed as Hazardous are in turn POPs and therefore sorted as NON-RECYCLE.

Table 6.2. Category distribution by dataset

	RECYCLE (%)	NON-RECYCLE (%)
Whole dataset (15,006 items)	72	28
Test dataset (1,284 items)	64	36
Spain Validation dataset (100 items)	77	23
Scotland Validation dataset (100 items)	56	44

Regarding the determination of the polymer present in the resin, different types were found as detailed in **Table 6.3**.

Table 6.3. Types of polymers determined by FTIR (by validation dataset)

Polymer	Spain (100 samples)	Scotland (100 samples)
HIPS	56%	49%
PC+ABS	24%	26%
ABS	16%	19%
PS+PPE	2%	2%
ABS+PET	1%	-
ABS+PMMA	1%	4%

As stated in a previous stage of the study (**Section 5.3.2**), the resins are composed of blends of polymers, one of them being the predominant and the one taken as a reference.

6.3.2 Classification model

6.3.2.1 Importance of variables

The Scikit-learn Random Forest Classifier allows the user to easily extract the variables which carried more weight in the decision tree algorithm (Louppe *et al.*, 2013). **Figure 6.3** presents the importance (relative influence of each variable) to the classification mode.

Figure 6.3. Feature importance classification model using MDI (Mean Decrease Impurity)

The most important feature is POLYMER, which is in accordance with the fact that different polymers require different loads of flame retardants to comply with standards conditioning the material's CATEGORY.

The variable "MANUFACTURER" ranks as the second most critical factor in the classification of wFPD plastics. Due to legal constraints, the author is not at liberty to disclose the manufacturers according to the recyclability of their products. Nevertheless, it was observed that certain manufacturers appeared more frequently in non-recyclable samples.

The year of manufacture (YoM) emerged as the third most influential feature. Recyclable samples were more broadly distributed between 2008 and 2018 and were generally present across a broader time range compared to non-recyclable samples, which were more densely clustered around 2010 and 2016. The fourth most significant feature was the ORIGIN. Most recyclable samples originated from Poland, China, and Slovakia, while those with a higher count of non-recyclable samples were predominantly manufactured in the United Kingdom, Turkey, and Poland. Poland appears as one of the countries where most of the recyclable and non-recyclable materials are assembled. This is not an inconsistency but is related to the diversity of manufacturers that assemble their equipment in that country.

6.3.2.2 Code

See Python Code in **Appendix C – Classification model code (Python)**.

6.3.2.3 Performance metrics

The metrics used to validate the model included precision, recall, and f1 scores for individual labels, as well as the accuracy score for the overall classification performance. Cross-validation on the test set produced five accuracy scores: 0.804, 0.809, 0.835, 0.876, and 0.809. This indicates that the model's accuracy ranged from a minimum of 80% to a maximum of 88%. These results for the test set are deemed acceptable. However, the model's evaluation primarily relies on the validation dataset.

The classification tests yielded the scores as presented **Table 6.4** and **Table 6.5**, for the test dataset, the Scotland validation dataset, the Spain validation dataset and the validation dataset of both countries combined, respectively.

Table 6.4. Test set classification score

	Precision	Recall	f1-Score	Units
0 (Non-Recycle)	0.79	0.72	0.76	116
1 (Recycle)	0.85	0.89	0.87	208
Accuracy			0.83	324
Macro avg.	0.82	0.81	0.81	324
Weighted avg.	0.83	0.83	0.83	324

Table 6.5. Classification report. A) Validation set: Scotland; B) Validation set: Spain; C) Validation set: Combined Scotland & Spain

	Precision			Recall			f1-Score			Units		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
0 (Non-Recycle)	0.79	0.65	0.73	0.64	0.57	0.61	0.71	0.60	0.67	36	23	59
1 (Recycle)	0.76	0.88	0.83	0.87	0.91	0.90	0.81	0.89	0.86	47	77	124
Accuracy	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.77	0.83	0.80	83	100	183
Macro avg.	0.78	0.76	0.78	0.76	0.74	0.75	0.76	0.75	0.76	83	100	183
Weighted avg.	0.77	0.82	0.80	0.77	0.83	0.80	0.77	0.83	0.80	83	100	183

Overall, the model performed well in terms of accuracy in the validation datasets, having the highest in the Spanish dataset, with an accuracy of 83%, the lowest in the Scottish validation dataset, with an accuracy of 77%, and a combined accuracy of 80%.

However, while the model accurately classified recyclable samples, achieving a combined recall score of 90%, its performance was less effective for non-recyclable samples. For instance, in the Spanish validation dataset, the recall score for non-recyclable samples was only 57%, indicating that just over half were correctly classified. This disparity is likely due to the high ratio of recyclable to non-recyclable samples in the training dataset.

6.3.2.4 Confusion Matrix and misclassification analysis

The confusion matrix for the test and validation sets were constructed, as displayed in **Figure 6.4**.

Figure 6.4. Confusion matrices

While the test dataset misclassification is relatively low (22 out of 324 False Negatives and 32 out of 324 False Positives), the validation datasets present a higher number of misclassifications, mainly for non-recyclable samples as the training dataset presents a higher ratio in favour of recyclable items. As previously mentioned, data rebalancing methods were attempted, although likely due to the relatively low number of entries the imbalance resulted in overfitting on the training dataset, which was evidenced in the generally lower precision of the validation sets compared to that of the test dataset.

6.4 OUTCOMES

This study highlights the effectiveness of Python and Random Forest in generating predictive classification models. The Random Forest model developed for classifying wFPD plastic casings, using items recovered from both Scotland and Spain, achieved an overall accuracy of 80% on the validation dataset. The model demonstrated a classification precision of over 80% for recyclable samples and a recall of 90%. However, it slightly underperformed in classifying non-recyclable

samples due to an imbalance in the dataset. Data rebalancing methods were considered but not employed, as they led to overfitting issues caused by the insufficient number of entries in the training dataset.

The high number of missing values from the training dataset is considerable, leaving a reduced number of samples with which to train the model. Moreover, the limited number of variables is also a key factor in the performance of the model. Due to a limited number of samples and variables, the model does not perform according to industry sorting standards in the validation set.

Although the accuracy of the model is high, it is not acceptable for practical application with 20% of material being misclassified, especially since the largest proportion of error would be in non-recyclable material being classified as recyclable, which is not acceptable and does not comply with the established regulation. Nevertheless, even though a better performing classification model was developed using Python, a larger number of entries (ca. 25,000) would be required to adjust the model and improve its performance.

The differences in the performance metrics determined for the Scottish and Spanish validation datasets show that there are factors that were not considered in the model (i.e., consumer, retailer and manufacturer behavior) that might influence the determination of the model associated with the difference in materials that are placed on the market and then reach the WEEE stream.

Despite the challenges presented by a relatively small dataset and the potential need to consider more variables, this initial model establishes a relevant foundation for future research in this area. The lessons learned from the performance of this model emphasize the need for a more exhaustive dataset and an investigation on other characteristics that may have a substantial impact on predicting the recyclability of wFPD plastics.

Overall, this chapter adds to the increasing knowledge in WEEE management and machine learning, showing the possibilities and difficulties of using predictive models to address environmental sustainability concerns. Further research will need to tackle key obstacles like data scarcity, model interpretability, and adaptability to different WEEE streams. With gradual improvements, predictive models could start providing targeted insights, helping to inform more sustainable practices over the coming years.

CHAPTER 7 Conclusions, limitations, and recommendations for future action

7.1 CONCLUSIONS

This research project focused on optimizing the classification, management, and recycling of waste Flat Panel Display equipment plastic casings, specifically aiming to reduce the environmental and health impacts of flame retardants, particularly brominated flame retardants. Through a combination of technological developments, data analysis, and comparative studies, this work has resulted in a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with recycling these plastics. The findings from this research contribute not only to the technical aspects of WEEE plastics management but also to the broader discussions around regulation, sustainability, and international cooperation in the context of global WEEE management.

A key outcome of this research was the successful development and validation of a fast, reliable, and industrially applicable method for detecting hazardous substances in WEEE plastics using handheld X-ray fluorescence. One of the central challenges in managing WEEE plastics, particularly with the presence of BFRs, lies in the difficulty of accurately and quickly identifying the concentrations of these compounds in materials recovered from electronic waste. The study demonstrated that h-XRF could reliably detect bromine and antimony concentrations, even in the presence of dust, a common interference in manual recycling operations. Importantly, the dust interference had minimal impact on the accuracy of the measurements, making this technique suitable for real-world recycling environments. The method was optimized for industrial-scale application, with a 10-second counting time achieving high accuracy and throughput, which is essential for large-scale operations. Furthermore, the study identified that specific areas of plastic casings, particularly the centre area of rear casings, were highly representative of BFR levels, achieving sorting accuracy exceeding 95%. This finding is particularly valuable, as it suggests that targeted sampling could significantly reduce the risk of false negatives, enhancing the efficiency and reliability of sorting operations. The development and validation of this h-XRF method marks a significant step forward in making hazardous material detection more accessible and cost-effective, especially for smaller recycling companies or those in developing countries where access to advanced analytical technology may be limited. This advancement could serve as a practical solution for improving the sustainability of WEEE plastics recycling by enabling the identification and sorting of hazardous materials, ensuring safer and more efficient recycling processes.

Alongside the development of the h-XRF method, the research also focused on improving predictive models for the recyclability of WEEE plastics. Initially, binary logistic regression was applied to predict the recyclability of plastics based on a few variables, such as type (LCD/LED), year of manufacture, and size. While binary logistic regression is a common and straightforward statistical method, its

application in this case revealed several limitations. Here, the results showed that the logistic regression model had low explanatory power, with R^2 values indicating that the model explained only a small proportion of the variability in the recyclability of the plastics. As a result, the model's predictions were not sufficiently reliable for practical use, highlighting the complexity of accurately classifying waste materials based on a limited set of variables. This emphasized that while simple statistical models can provide initial insights, they may not fully capture the complexities of the waste streams associated with WEEE plastics, which led to the decision to refine the model. By incorporating more advanced data analysis techniques through the application of more sophisticated machine learning techniques, particularly the Random Forest algorithm, in Python the performance of the model was significantly improved. The Random Forest algorithm was able to process a more extensive dataset with additional variables such as the origin and manufacturer of the FPDs, therefore improving the classification accuracy. When tested on a diverse dataset that included samples from recycling sites in both Scotland and Spain, the model achieved an overall accuracy rate of 80%, with a classification precision of over 80% for recyclable materials. This was a notable improvement over the binary logistic regression model, as it demonstrated the ability to classify waste materials more accurately and robustly. However, while the Random Forest model performed well in terms of classifying recyclable plastics, it still faced challenges in classifying non-recyclable plastics accurately, particularly due to the imbalance in the dataset, which led to some misclassifications. Despite these limitations, this finding demonstrated the potential for machine learning-based approaches to enhance recycling practices by providing waste managers with a powerful tool for predicting the recyclability of materials. Nevertheless, the results also highlighted that further refinement of the model is necessary, particularly in addressing the imbalance in the dataset and improving the classification of non-recyclable materials. This could be achieved by expanding the dataset and incorporating more diverse variables, which would improve the model's generalizability and reliability in various recycling contexts.

In addition to technological advancements, the impact of regulatory frameworks on the recyclability of WEEE plastics was also explored, focusing on the differences observed between Scotland and Uruguay. This case study revealed significant differences in the recyclability of plastics in these two regions, largely due to the differences in regulatory frameworks. In Scotland, strict regulations such as those imposed by the European Union, including RoHS and POPs Directives, have led to a higher recyclability with a rate of over 70% for FPD plastic casings. This is related to the former regulations limiting the concentrations of BFRs in electronic waste. In contrast, Uruguay, which does not have any regulations specific to either WEEE or POPs management, faces challenges in recycling plastics, with less than 50% of the materials being recyclable. Moreover, a significant portion of WEEE plastics in Uruguay exceeded the Br concentration limits set by the EU, which further hindered recycling efforts. This finding highlighted the critical impact of regulatory frameworks on WEEE recycling rates and underscored the importance of harmonizing regulations globally. The research also revealed a troubling potential trend of hazardous materials being exported to regions with

weaker regulatory controls, exacerbating the problem of unsafe disposal practices in developing countries. The study suggests that global cooperation and the sharing of scientific data could help address these challenges by fostering more uniform regulations and facilitating the safe management of WEEE across different regions. These findings underscore the need for countries, particularly those in the global south, to strengthen their regulatory frameworks and to participate in international efforts to improve WEEE management practices, which would ultimately contribute to reducing the environmental and health risks associated with electronic waste.

Finally, this research provided a detailed material characterization of wFPD plastics, which is essential for improving recycling strategies and understanding the composition of waste materials. The study found that approximately 70% of the materials from both LCD and LED devices are recyclable, but significant challenges remain due to the presence of BFRs, especially in plastics such as HIPS. The high bromine content in HIPS often renders it non-recyclable, which is problematic given that it constitutes a large fraction of recovered materials. In contrast, materials like PC+ABS, although less abundant, showed a higher proportion of recyclable material. This finding is critical as it emphasizes the need to focus on improving sorting technologies to differentiate between these materials more effectively. The study also identified that current sorting technologies, such as the sink and float method, are inadequate for efficiently separating plastics like HIPS from potentially recyclable plastics like PC+ABS, resulting in the loss of valuable material. This evidences the need for the development of more advanced sorting technologies, such as hybrid or chemical recycling methods, to minimize material loss and improve overall recycling efficiency. Additionally, key trends were identified, such as the shift from LCDs to LEDs, and the shorter lifespan of LEDs, which points to a growing issue of planned obsolescence and increased waste generation. This material characterization forms the foundation for developing better recycling systems and targeted waste management strategies that are suited to specific contexts and recycling facilities.

In conclusion, the findings from this research offer valuable insights into improving the recycling and management of WEEE plastics, particularly those contaminated with hazardous substances like BFRs. The development of h-XRF as a reliable and cost-effective tool for hazardous material detection, the refinement of predictive classification models using machine learning techniques, and the comparative analysis of WEEE management practices all contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the complexities involved in WEEE recycling. By identifying the key challenges and opportunities in this field, this research lays the groundwork for more effective and sustainable practices that can be adopted globally. Moreover, the study underscores the importance of international collaboration, regulatory harmonization, and the continued development of innovative recycling technologies to address the growing problem of WEEE. Ultimately, this work demonstrates that with the right technological advancements, regulatory frameworks, and data-driven approaches, it is possible to reduce the environmental impact of WEEE plastics and pave the way for more sustainable recycling practices worldwide.

7.2 LIMITATIONS

When applying XRF technology to WEEE plastics, a major limitation was associated with the absence of any suitable reference material. The requirement of different reference materials depending on the type of polymer in the sample is neither feasible nor practical in its implementation at an industrial level, since different calibration settings should be used depending on the type of polymer in the sample, which is not always identified and if it is, it is not easy to visualise. Therefore, a suitable option was to compare the results of applying two analytical methods to the same set of samples. These methods were not the same but equivalent, neither the same equipment nor the same analysis time were used. However, while this was a limitation in terms of effectively validating the method developed, the results showed a high level of correlation between the two sets of results.

One aspect to consider of this work was the selection of the analysis technology. This research was conducted in the context of a KTP Project (Knowledge Transfer Partnership) between the University of the West of Scotland and RESTRUCTA LTD. Before launching the project, the company had acquired the h-XRF, so a prior evaluation to determine its suitability was not possible. Nonetheless, several studies support the application of h-XRF for the determination of Br and Sb in plastics, and its applicability and feasibility have been extensively demonstrated in the present study.

Related to laboratory analyses, initially these were attempted at the UWS facilities, however in the case of the GC/MS analyses it was not possible to complete them as the equipment did not have the necessary injection tools for the specific type of samples. A considerable number of analyses were carried out to adapt the procedure and equipment, however the results were not acceptable and were then subcontracted to the University of Birmingham. However, these analyses failed to produce conclusive results. The recoveries determined for PBDEs, assessed using two CRMs with polymeric matrices distinct from those of the analysed samples, ranged from approximately between 70% to 150%, indicating significant inaccuracies. It was not possible to resolve the discrepancies between the total Br results from h-XRF and the GC/MS results. The uncertainty stems from whether the differences arise from not having analysed all the brominated compound present in the sample or from low recovery rates. Additionally, recovery rates were not established for two critical compounds in the target sample type, TBBP-A and HBCDD.

On the other hand, Sb determination tests were carried out in the UWS laboratory, although a better assessment could have been carried out with access to microwave digestion technology. The results of Sb determined by ICP/OES show a linear relationship with those determined by h-XRF, however, they were consistently lower. This could be related to the fact that in all cases the samples digestion were incomplete likely leading to partial extraction of the Sb. Alternatively, it could be related to h-XRF overestimating the concentration of this element.

Regarding the collection of information directly from the recycled equipment, it was not possible in all cases to identify all the data sought, as some manufacturers do not include them on the labels or on the resins. This meant that not all data were available for all entries in the database. In addition, there was also a time and resource constraint, as a more adequate statistical adjustment would have required a database of about 25,000 entries with all variables complete, whereas only 1,254 could be completely filled in. The primary issue arose from the lack of data on polymer type, identified as the most relevant factor in determining whether an item is recyclable or non-recyclable. This information was not retrieved in the routine operations of the plant where the study was conducted, therefore even though other variables were addressed, information on polymer type was missing. Collecting data from the information displayed on FPD casings is challenging and time-demanding, as much of the required information is not readily visible on labels. Accessing these details often requires reading labels, examining the interior of the resin for identification codes of polymers or additives, being familiar with these codes, and interpreting manufacturing dates, which are frequently presented in complex diagrams. Therefore, more thorough sampling would have yielded more representative data, but it was impractical to carry out. Data collection could be much more straightforward if the information was clearly displayed on the equipment's label, or more easily retrieved like for instance through a QR code as it is proposed by the Digital Product Passport.

Relating to the availability of information but linked to BFRs and their impact on health, the dynamic nature of these compounds used in WEEE plastics remain a critical area of concern and was thus a limitation to this study. Legislative changes and compound-specific bans frequently shift the types and permitted concentrations of BFRs in use, directly influencing the composition of waste profiles. Substituting restricted compounds with alternative substances introduces additional uncertainty, as the health effects of many replacements remain unexplored. In this context, adopting a conservative approach such as linking Br presence to POPs/BFRs is justified, given the lack of comprehensive data on the safety of newly introduced compounds.

In terms of access to the material, while no difficulties were encountered in Scotland, in Uruguay and Spain there may be bias in the results. This is associated with the fact that the materials retrieved are from equipment sourced mainly from offices or institutions (public and private), and therefore the sample may not be representative across society.

As for predictive modelling, the model developed using Random Forest offers valuable forecasting capabilities but struggles to keep pace with the rapid evolution of product designs and industry trends. As manufacturers move toward larger displays and reduced material usage per FPD unit, the recyclability profiles of products may shift, potentially altering waste compositions in ways not fully captured by the current framework. This gap underscores the challenges of accurately predicting future recycling outcomes in a landscape defined by continuous innovation.

Finally, it should be noted that the present work focuses on a single category of WEEE. Although it was selected because it is the stream with the highest concentration of BFRs, this does not allow us to determine or affirm if other plastic materials in WEEE were POPs or hazardous and should be managed separately.

While these limitations highlight areas for improvement and further investigation, the insights gained provide a robust foundation for understanding BFRs in WEEE plastics, offering valuable data and methodologies that advance the field. By acknowledging these challenges, this work sets the stage for future studies to build upon its findings and address the evolving complexities of waste management and material analysis.

7.3 FUTURE WORK

The advancement of screening technologies for hazardous chemicals in end-of-life materials is a critical area for future research. Developing efficient, cost-effective methods to detect BFRs in WEEE plastics could significantly enhance industrial recycling practices. Particularly, further exploration into manual dismantling as a pre-processing technique should be prioritized. This approach could help produce more homogeneous, bromine-free plastic fractions, reducing the environmental and health risks associated with BFRs in the recycling stream. It is essential to evaluate the economic, environmental, and health benefits of such methods to inform future waste management strategies.

In addition to enhancing screening methods, this study also underscores the need for more comprehensive statistical models to predict the characteristics of plastics recovered from WEEE. The complexity of accurately assessing the plastic material composition suggests that models incorporating a wider range of variables would enhance the precision of predictions. Thus, improving the availability and quality of information presented in the EEEs is essential for advancing the development of predictive models that support the various stakeholders involved in WEEE plastic management. Efforts should focus on streamlining data retrieval and interpretation processes. The integration of technologies, such as QR codes, could facilitate faster and more efficient information access through optical character recognition (OCR) systems, significantly reducing the time required for manual data extraction. By building on tools such as Python and Random Forest, this research sets a foundation for the development of more accurate predictive models, which could significantly optimize WEEE plastics management, leading to better recycling outcomes.

Another important area for future investigation is the characterization of WEEE plastics, particularly with regard to the presence and behaviour of brominated compounds. While current regulations address certain BFRs, manufacturers are increasingly using novel, currently unregulated brominated additives as alternatives. These novel BFRs share chemical similarities with those already restricted, suggesting they may eventually be designated as POPs. Given this potential, it is essential to monitor the presence of these new BFRs in WEEE plastics and assess their long-term effects. Furthermore,

existing studies often overlook these novel compounds, leading to misleading conclusions about the true scope of brominated additives in WEEE plastics. Reviewing total Br concentration thresholds used for sorting plastics is also critical, as current methods fail to account for the full range of brominated components, leading to inaccurate baselines that hinder effective recycling efforts. Establishing a more precise total Br concentration limit will improve sorting efficiency and favour the management of recyclable materials.

Addressing the broader issue of BFRs in WEEE plastics, there remains a significant gap in the understanding of cross-contamination during recycling processes. Results of this study highlight the need for further research into how BFRs may unintentionally transfer from one product to another during recycling, especially in the case of black plastics which are likely to end up being used in the manufacturing of consumer products. The migration of hazardous compounds in the recycling stream could pose serious risks to both human health and the environment. As such, more research is needed to evaluate the sources of exposure and potential impacts, particularly in terms of occupational health risks in WEEE processing facilities. Airborne flame retardant particles in these environments could present significant hazards, requiring focused attention on exposure pathways and mitigation strategies.

Finally, the evolving nature of BFR regulations adds another layer of complexity. While certain BFRs like PBDEs and HBCD are restricted under the Stockholm Convention due to their classification as POPs, new brominated additives continue to be introduced into the market. These substances are not yet regulated, but their chemical similarities to restricted BFRs suggest they may eventually be included in future regulatory frameworks. It is crucial to conduct ongoing research into the presence of these novel BFRs in WEEE plastics and their potential to be classified as hazardous materials in the future.

Addressing these research gaps and advancing screening technologies, predictive models, and characterization methods are vital to improving the management of BFRs in WEEE plastics. The findings from this study provide a solid foundation for future work in this area, paving the way for more effective recycling strategies and contributing to the long-term sustainability of WEEE management.

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APPENDIX A. WEEE Legislation Worldwide

Appendix A. (Europe)

Generated volume: 12 Mt Generated in 2019 (Forti *et al.*, 2020)

Country	WEEE Generation (kt/year)	Legislation/Regulation	Comments	Ref.
EU countries	7.889	Directive 2002/96/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 January 2003 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE)—Joint declaration of the European Parliament, the Council and the Commission relating to Article 9, 2003.	Instrumented to enable environmentally sound WEEE management. Sets targets for collection and recycling for all Member States. Aimed at minimizing WEEE generation by promoting reuse, recycling, and recovery. Each Member State must devise their own strategy to reach collection and recycling targets. Mandates EEE manufacturers and importers to collect end-of-use and end-of-life EEE from consumers and properly manage them.	
		Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE), 2012.	Recast of Directive 2002/96/EC. Sets new collection targets. Officially replaces Directive 2002/96/EC in 2014.	(Shittu, Williams and Shaw, 2021)
		Directive 2002/95/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 January 2003 on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment, 2003.	Aimed at restricting the use of hazardous substances in the manufacture of EEE. These substances include: brominated fire retardants such as PBDEs (poly-brominated diphenyl ethers), POPs (persistent organic pollutants), lead and mercury, among others.	
		Directive 2011/65/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2011 on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment, 2011.	Recast of Directive 2002/95/EC. Restriction of hazardous substances was expanded to other types of EEE. Defines 0.1% w/w (1000 ppm) as the admissible threshold values for the concentrations of PBDEs and PBBs that can be present in new products manufactured to be marketed in the EU.	
United Kingdom	1.586	WEEE Directive (2013)	Implements Directive 2012/19/EU.	N/A

Appendix A (Africa: Generalities)

Legislation is either lacking or not being properly enforced in these countries. Regulation of WEEE management relies on international agreements.

	International Agreement	Ref.
<p>Basel Convention, 1992</p>	<p>International Environmental Agreement between 53 signatory countries aimed at controlling trans-boundary movements (import/export) of hazardous waste with specific restriction on the movement of toxic waste from developed to less developed or developing countries.</p> <p>Does not regulate WEEE directly but through the fact that WEEE contains hazardous substances and is therefore, hazardous waste.</p> <p>Allows hazardous waste movements if there is a bi/multi-lateral agreement for sound treatment of the waste in the destination country.</p>	
<p>Bamako Convention, 1991 (enforced in 1998). African treaty.</p>	<p>Aimed at restricting hazardous waste movements into and between African countries.</p> <p>Does not mandate compliance but provides advice on management.</p> <p>Seeks to complement the requirements of the Basel Convention in order to prevent transboundary movement of hazardous waste into African countries.</p> <p>Creates a framework for adequate management of hazardous waste ensuring the protection of African communities from the negative health and environmental impacts of unregulated waste management.</p>	<p>(Shittu, Williams and Shaw, 2021)</p>

Appendix A (Africa)

Generated volume: 2.9 Mt Generated in 2019 (Forti *et al.*, 2020)

WEEE					
Country	Generation (kt/year)	Legislation/Regulation		Comments	Ref.
South Africa	416	National Waste Management Strategy		Classifies WEEE as hazardous waste.	(ERA, 2021)
		EPR 2020	Regulations,	The WEEE notice includes expected targets for collection and recycling over the following five years. Amendments to be proposed by May 2021.	
Nigeria	461	Harmful (Special Provisions)	Waste Criminal	Prohibition of deposition and dumping of harmful waste on any land, territorial waters and related matters.	(Benebo, 2012)
		National Environmental (Sanitation and Waste Control) Regulation 2009	Regulation	No person is to engage in any activity likely to generate Hazardous waste without permission from the agency. That who generates hazardous waste must ensure such waste is treated using appropriate methods. Export and transit of hazardous waste is prohibited unless express permission from the agency. Hazardous waste destined to another country is not permitted to transit through Nigeria without consent of the agency.	
		Guide for Importers of Used EEE (UEEE)		Importers of UEEE to register with authority. Import of functional UEEE ³⁰ is allowed. Import of near-end-of-life WEEE is prohibited.	
		The National Environmental (Electrical Electronic Sector) Regulations SI No 23, 2011		Adopts polluter pays principle. Ensures environmentally sound waste management. Defines the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders.	

³⁰ UEEE: Used Electric and Electronic Equipment

Appendix A (Asia)

Generated volume:: 24.9 Mt Generated in 2019 (Forti *et al.*, 2020)

WEEE				
Country	Generation (kt/year)	Legislation/Regulation	Comments	Ref.
		Notification on seventh category waste importation, 2000	Import of the seventh category of waste is banned.	
		Technical policy and pollution prevention and control of WEEE, 2006	Establishes the “Reduce, Reuse, Recycle” and the “polluter pays” principles. Designates resources for environmentally sound collection, reuse, recycling, and disposal of WEEE.	
		Prevention and Control of Pollution from IT Products, 2007	Restricts the use of hazardous substances. Sets eco-design requirements. Manufacturers/importers (producers) must provide information about their products.	
China	10.129	Pollution Prevention of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment, 2008	Aimed at preventing pollution generated during disassembling, recycling and disposing of WEEE. Establishes a licensing scheme for WEEE recycling companies.	(Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
		Regulation on recycling and disposal of WEEE, 2011	Defines an obligation to disassembly WEEE and centralize its recycling. Establishes a fund to support WEEE recycling.	
		Administrative measures for levy and use of treatment fund for waste electronic and electric products, 2012	Imported EEE must pay the fund The fund for WEEE treatment subsidizing is set by the state.	

Generated volume:: 24.9 Mt Generated in 2019 (Forti *et al.*, 2020)

WEEE				
Country	Generation (kt/year)	Legislation/Regulation	Comments	Ref.
		Restriction of Hazardous Substances in EEE, 2016	Introduces a compliance list for management. Establishes a system for conformity assessment.	
		WEEE Treatment List, 2014 ed. Enforced in 2016	Extended the original 5 categories to 14.	
		WEEE fund standard update, 2016	Lowers the subsidy for management of waste TVs and PCs (personal computers), rises subsidy for waste air conditioners management.	(Song <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
		Pilot project on EPR (extended producer responsibility) in electronics industry, 2015	Producers must lead EEE design and production, as well as WEEE collection and recycling.	
		Promotion Plan: EPR principle	Provides guidance for producers to implement eco-design, selection of secondary materials and involvement in WEEE collection and recycling.	
			Only authorized dismantlers and recyclers are allowed to collect WEEE.	
India	3.230	E-waste (management) Rules, 2016	Puts producer responsibility organization (PRO) in place.	(Forti <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
		National Resource Policy, 2019 (DRAFT)	Proposes a stronger role for producers regarding recovery of secondary resources from WEEE.	

Appendix A (North America)

Generated volume: 9.3 Mt Generated in 2019 (Forti *et al.*, 2020)

WEEE				
Country	Generation (kt/year)	Legislation/Regulation	Comments	Ref.
United States of America	6.918	No federal legislation regulating WEEE management in place.	Legislation varies between states: different scopes, impacts and bans on WEEE disposing in landfills. In general, all states which have implemented regulation take an EPR approach.	(Forti <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Mexico	1.220	General Law for the Prevention and Integral Management of Waste (LGPEGIR—for its acronym in Spanish), 2004	Defines WEEE as technological waste and classifies it as special management waste, making states and municipalities responsible for its prevention, transport, storage, handling, treatment, and final disposal.	(SEDEMA, 2020)
		NOM-161-SEMARNAT-2011	Sets the obligation to present plans for electrical and electronic waste.	
		NADF-019-AMBT-2018 (Environmental Standard for the Federal District. Electrical and Electronic Waste, requirements and specifications for its management)	Seeks to establish the requirements and specifications for the correct separation, storage, collection, transport, treatment, recycling and disposal of electrical and electronic waste within Mexico City.	
Canada	757	Ministry of Environment is responsible for WEEE management. No related federal legislation is in place. WEEE mainly managed under the Stewardship Programme: Electronic Product Stewardship Canada (EPSC) organized and controlled by the private sector.		(Shittu, Williams and Shaw, 2021)

Appendix A (South America)

Generated volume: 3.8 Mt Generated in 2019. [22]

WEEE				
Country	Generation (kt/year)	Legislation/Regulation	Comments	Ref.
Brazil	2.143	National Solid Waste Policy	Establishes that every stakeholder within the lifecycle of EEE is responsible for its management at the end-of-life of the product. It promotes WEEE reverse logistics.	(Forti <i>et al.</i> , 2020)

Appendix B. Vanta™ Control charts

Appendix B (EC-680m_Bromine)

Appendix B (EC-681_Bromine)

Appendix B (EC-681_Antimony)

Appendix C – Classification model code (Python)

```
import pandas as pd

import numpy as np

from matplotlib import pyplot as plt

    # Display options for pandas to show all columns

pd.options.display.width = None

pd.options.display.max_columns = None

pd.set_option('display.max_rows', 25)

pd.set_option('display.max_columns', 3000)

data = pd.read_excel("Database (extended).xlsx")

    # Columns are renamed

data = data.rename(columns={"Type": "category",

                            "CATEGORY": "label",

                            "Weight (kg)": "weight",

                            "SIZE": "size",

                            "DATE": "date",

                            "YoM": "yom",

                            "Polymer": "polymer"

                            })

data = data.drop('date', axis = 'columns')

    # Data is processed in order to fit it into the model

data['weight'] = data['weight'].astype('float64')
```

```

data = data[data['label'].notna()]

# Import libraries for coding

from sklearn.preprocessing import OrdinalEncoder

from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder

# Separate independent variables from the target variable or label. The Label encoder will be used
for the

# target variable, and the Ordinal Encoder for the independent variables.

# The first 6 rows are selected which are the columns of the independent variables.

X = data.iloc[:,0:6]

# Y the target variable is "label"

y = data['label']

# Code each categorical variable (continuous variables do not need to be coded)

for variable in X.select_dtypes(exclude=np.number).columns:

# An instance of the Ordinal encoder is started

oe = OrdinalEncoder()

# Match it with the values of the variable and transform the values into numbers

X[variable] = oe.fit_transform(X[variable].values.reshape(-1,1))

# Do the same for the target variable

le = LabelEncoder()

y = le.fit_transform(y)

X.info()

"""

Imputation. KNN

"""

from sklearn.impute import KNNImputer

```

```
KNN_imputer = KNNImputer(n_neighbors=3)
X = KNN_imputer.fit_transform(X)
X = pd.DataFrame(X, columns=data.iloc[:,0:6].columns)
X.info()
```

```
"""
```

Partition

The full database could be used to train the model. However, a percentage of the dataset must be left out of the training. This is so that the model can be later evaluated

```
"""
```

```
# Partitioning of dataset into train and test
```

```
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, train_size=0.75, random_state=123)
```

```
"""
```

RF Model

Now a Random Forest model is generated. But before that, the best hyperparameters for the model are determined

This is done with GridSearchCV, which generates models with all the possible combinations and chooses from all of them the one that matches best RF Model

```
"""
```

```
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report
from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV
```

```
param_grid = {
    "n_estimators":[50,100,150,200],
```

```

"max_depth" : [None, 10, 20, 30],
"min_samples_split":[2,5,10],
"min_samples_leaf":[1,2,4]
}

# This is pre-run to find the best hyperparameters

# grid_search = GridSearchCV(estimator=RF_model, param_grid=param_grid,
#
#           cv = 5, scoring = 'accuracy', n_jobs = - 1)

# grid_search.fit(X_train, y_train)

# best_params = grid_search.best_params_

# print("Best params = ", best_params)

# The best hyperparameters were:

# Best params = {'max_depth': None, 'min_samples_leaf': 2, 'min_samples_split': 2, 'n_estimators':
150}

# With this, the mode was generated using the best hyperparameters obtained earlier. An instance
of Random Forest is started

RF_model = RandomForestClassifier(random_state=123,

                                max_depth=None,

                                min_samples_leaf=2,

                                min_samples_split=2,

                                n_estimators=150)

# It is adjusted to the training dataset

RF_model.fit(X_train, y_train)

# And a prediction is generated

y_pred = RF_model.predict(X_test)

# Now the classification report is used to show how well has the model performed

```

```
print(classification_report(y_test, y_pred))

print(le.inverse_transform([0,1]))

"""

Importance of variables

"""

importances = RF_model.feature_importances_

forest_importances = pd.Series(importances, index=X_train.columns.values)

std = np.std([tree.feature_importances_ for tree in RF_model.estimators_], axis=0)

fig, ax = plt.subplots()

forest_importances.plot.bar(yerr=std, ax=ax)

ax.set_title("Feature importances using MDI")

ax.set_ylabel("Mean decrease in impurity")

fig.tight_layout()

plt.show()
```

Appendix 1. Management of WEEE Plastics Containing BFRs: Current Trends and Challenges

WEEE contain a variety of resources, including precious metals (i.e., gold, platinum, silver), as well as other valuable metals, such as iron and aluminium. These high-demand materials make WEEE economically attractive to both informal and formal recyclers. However, their management in the informal sector poses a threat to both the health of the people involved and the surrounding ecosystem due to the presence, generation, or use of toxic substances, including BFRs. This is a worrying matter, particularly in middle and low-income countries where WEEE is usually managed under poor conditions, causing serious health impacts on workers and children who are usually linked to the activity as workers themselves or by playing close to where WEEE is processed (Forti *et al.*, 2020).

It is estimated that around 2.6 million tons of WEEE plastics are currently produced annually in Europe. The mass of the collected material is limited to 700 kt/year of which only approximately 30% (200 kt/year) can be sent for recycling due to current processing capacities. Management of the remaining 500 kt/year of recovered plastics is mainly managed by incineration for energy recovery or fuel replacement in cement kilns (44%), and landfilling (11%) (Cardamone, Ardolino and Arena, 2021). It is predicted that by 2050 recycling will increase to 50%, energy recovery to 44%, with landfill being the least selected option decreasing to a projected 6% (Ahirwar and Tripathi, 2021).

Appendix 2. Flame Retardants

Over a decade ago, updates in regulatory frameworks governing the use of BFRs were put in place. The European Union and the UK have implemented measures to restrict the use of certain BFRs through directives such as the Restriction of Hazardous Substances (RoHS) (*Directive 2011/65/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2011*). These regulatory initiatives aim to balance the need for fire safety with environmental and health considerations, promoting the development and adoption of safer products, however, BFRs continue to be integral to the safety of electrical and electronic equipment.

The combination of BFRs with Sb_2O_3 as synergist is associated with its cost-effectiveness and apparent independency from the chemical structure of the BFR and the polymer within which it is incorporated. Thus, Sb_2O_3 is typically found in concentrations of approximately 33-55% of the Br content (Alassali, Abis, *et al.*, 2019; Alassali, Picuno, *et al.*, 2019; Harrad, Drage, M. A.-E. Abdallah, *et al.*, 2019).

Research on decaBDE- Sb_2O_3 combinations revealed a rapid reaction sequence, with the rapid formation of SbBr_3 . This phenomenon likely explains optimal antimony-to-bromine molar ratio of 1:3 in antimony-bromine flame retardants. The primary flame-retardant action of both Sb-Cl and Sb-Br formulations involves reactions of either SbBr_3 with major flame-propagating radicals such as $\text{H}\cdot$, $\text{O}\cdot$, $\text{OH}\cdot$, and $\text{HO}_2\cdot$, as well as the resultant hydrogen halides, HBr, through a series of intricate chain reactions. The principal propagation and termination reactions can be succinctly summarized as (Horrocks, 2020):

Other termination/flame inhibition reactions are proposed with the formation of antimony oxy-species:

In the context of flame retardancy, Sb_2O_3 appears to be equally efficient when combined with commonly used chlorinated and brominated flame retardants, indicating the above reaction mechanisms are marginally affected by either chemical properties of the flame retardant or the polymer matrix in which they are present. The primary flame retarding mechanisms in a polymer matrix predominantly involve gas phase processes. However, the release of HCl or HBr, functioning as acids, promotes char-forming reactions in polymers such as cellulose, poly(vinyl alcohol), and poly(vinyl acetate) by dehydrating pendant –OH groups.

Numerous FRs, while exhibiting quantifiable or significant levels of toxicity, degrade into compounds that are also harmful, so much that in certain cases these degradation products may serve as the primary agents of toxicity. For instance, halogenated compounds containing aromatic rings have the potential to undergo degradation into dioxins, particularly under conditions of high temperature, such as during their manufacturing, exposure to fire, recycling processes, or prolonged exposure to sunlight (Speight, 2017).

Appendix 3. X-Ray Fluorescence

Principles of XRF

X-Ray Fluorescence spectroscopy operates on the principle that exposure of a material to short-wavelength X-Rays initiates a cascade of atomic interactions, fundamentally altering the electronic structure of constituent atoms. Upon absorption of high-energy X-Rays, atoms within the material undergo ionization, leading to the excitation of an electron from an inner shell. This excitation creates a "hole" in the inner shell, which is subsequently filled as higher energy electrons transition to lower energy levels, emitting energy in the form of a photon. These emitted photons, classified as either α or β , correspond to transitions between different electron orbitals within the atom. The resulting fluorescent photons possess characteristic energies specific to each element, thus serving as a unique signature for element identification and quantification in a sample (Beckhoff, 2006).

In Energy Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence (ED-XRF) analysis, samples are exposed to high-energy *primary* photons generated by an X-ray tube or a radioisotopic source. This primary photon has sufficient energy to excite electrons within the sample, causing it to emit *secondary* X-Ray photon, a phenomenon known as *fluorescence*, as electrons return to their original orbits. The emitted X-Rays exhibit energies specific to the elements present in the sample, appearing as peaks in an energy spectrum. The intensity of these peaks directly reflects the concentration of the corresponding elements, often quantified through comparison to well-characterized standards. The theoretical foundation of XRF is firmly grounded in the interaction of electron beams and X-Rays with samples. X-Rays, characterized by their high energy and short wavelengths, induce ionization in materials, triggering the emission of fluorescent radiation as electrons transition between energy levels. This emitted radiation, always of characteristic energy, serves as a distinctive fingerprint for each element present in the sample. By precisely measuring these fluorescent energies using electronic detectors and amplifiers, and employing sophisticated software algorithms for quantitative determinations, XRF enables rapid and accurate identification and quantification of elements in a wide range of materials (Shackley, 2018). **Figure A.3.1** graphs the series of events described above.

Figure A.3.1 Diagram depicting X-Ray fluorescence events

X-Rays, integral components of the electromagnetic spectrum, can be characterized either by their wavelength (λ , nanometres) or by their energy-particle (kilo-electron volts, keV). Surrounding the nucleus are electron-hosting orbitals, denoted as K, L, and M, ordered from the innermost to the outermost. As previously described, when subjected to irradiation by a primary electron beam, atoms within a sample emit X-Rays provided the photons possess adequate energy. These X-Rays, emanating from the sample's atoms, are termed secondary X-Rays or fluorescent X-Rays. (Bajaj and Joshi, 2021)

The closer an electron shell resides to the nucleus, the stronger this attraction becomes, characterized by a high binding energy. Consequently, electrons in shells closer to the nucleus exhibit greater resistance to removal compared to those in shells farther away. In spectral terms, the binding energy of a K shell electron surpasses that of an L or M shell electron.

Upon the filling of an electron vacancy by an L shell electron, it manifests as a $K\alpha$ line. Similarly, transitions between M shell electrons and K shells yield $K\beta$ lines, or between M and L shells result in $L\alpha$ or $L\beta$ lines (see **Figure A.3.2**).

In X-Ray analysis, $K\beta$ lines predominate for low atomic numbers ($Z < 11$), although for lighter elements, $K\beta$ lines may significantly contribute to the spectrum. $K\alpha$ lines typify elements with atomic numbers ranging approximately from $Z = 11$ (Sodium/Na) to $Z = 92$ (Uranium/U). L lines are discernible for elements from low atomic numbers (Lithium/Li, $Z = 3$) to U, while M lines are evident for medium atomic number elements (Aluminium/Al, $Z = 13$) up to U as well.

Each element within the sample, upon excitation by primary X-Ray photons, emits X-Rays uniquely characteristic of that element. However, owing to X-Rays' susceptibility to transmission, reflection, diffraction, scattering, and photoelectric absorption, they are subject to matrix effects. Consequently, the intensities of the generated X-Rays may not exhibit direct proportionality to the concentration of elements within the sample.

The distinct line spectrum characteristic of an element emerges from the intricate interplay between electrons or X-Ray photons and the atoms within the sample. When an electron or X-Ray photon interacts with an electron in the atom, it disrupts the electron's equilibrium, prompting its removal from its orbital. This displacement creates a vacancy, a state of imbalance within the atom's inner shell, seeking restoration.

In its excited and unstable state, the atom compensates this imbalance by filling the vacancy with an electron from an outer shell. As this outer orbital electron transitions to occupy the void in the inner shell, it emits an X-Ray photon. However, it's essential to recognize that this electron transition necessitates sufficient energy to displace electrons from the inner orbital.

Generally, the higher the atomic number, the greater the energy required from the X-Ray to stimulate the corresponding electron transitions. This underscores the intricate relationship between atomic structure and the resultant X-Ray spectra, elucidating the elemental composition and properties of the analysed materials (Lampman, 2019).

Figure A.3.2 Interplay between electrons or X-Ray photons within the atoms

The versatility of XRF extends from its basic principles, which find application in other instrumental methods such as X-Ray spectroscopy (Gallhofer and Lottermoser, 2018).

X-Ray Sources

The X-Ray tube serves as the generator of X-Rays essential for atom excitation within the sample. The initiation of primary X-Ray production involves the application of current to the filament within the tube. Electrons are emitted from a cathode and propelled towards an anode through an electric field generated by a positive potential at the anode relative to the cathode. Upon reaching the anode, they impact the target, engaging with its atomic structure and dissipating their energy through various mechanisms. (Cesareo *et al.*, 2009).

X-Ray Detectors

In energy-dispersive analysis, fluorescent X-Rays emitted by the sample are captured by a solid-state detector, generating a continuous distribution of pulses. These pulses' voltages correspond to the

energies of the incoming photons. A multichannel analyser (MCA) processes this signal, producing a digital spectrum that can be further analysed for obtaining analytical data.

An effective characterization of materials relies on the efficient and accurate detection of photons. Detectors operate by ionizing atoms upon interaction with incoming X-Ray photons, with the resulting charge proportional to the energy of the incident photons. Analysing fluorescent radiation typically involves either wavelength-dispersive or energy-dispersive methods. The latter, prevalent in handheld XRF spectrometers, entails capturing emitted X-Rays using solid-state detectors, which generate a continuous stream of pulses whose voltages correspond to the energies of incoming photons.

Historically, gas proportional counter (GPC) detectors were employed in early instruments, while modern iterations favour solid-state detectors such as PIN diodes, Si(Li), or silicon-drift detectors (SDDs). These detectors vary in resolution and speed, with proportional counters exhibiting the lowest resolution, PIN diodes occupying a mid-range, and Si(Li), Ge(Li), and SDDs offering superior resolution. These advancements in detector technology have greatly enhanced the precision and efficiency of XRF analysis, further consolidating its position as a cornerstone technique in materials science and analytical chemistry. (Bosco, 2013)

These advancements signify a significant leap forward in X-Ray detection technology, enabling more sensitive, accurate, and versatile analysis in various fields, from materials science to environmental monitoring.

Spectral interference, matrix effects and calibration

In XRF analyses, two of the greater challenges are the matrix effects and spectral interference. Spectral interference takes place when the detector resolution is deficient or when the energy levels of two elements closely align. Matrix effects, on the other hand, occur when the presence of one element in a sample alters the measured intensity of X-Rays from another element, either by absorbing or enhancing radiation. Nevertheless, advancements in sources, detectors, and data processing have notably enhanced the precision of XRF spectra.

Upon selecting an analytical program or application, calibration becomes necessary prior to conducting analyses. Calibration in XRF demands considerable time to achieve satisfactory quality, nevertheless, once the calibration setup is established, periodic recalibration, typically annually, suffices, facilitated by drift monitor correction.

Calibration can be influenced by various factors, notably background spectral interference and matrix effects.

Matrix effects can either enhance or diminish excitation on characteristic lines, leading to inaccuracies in spectral line representation. These effects have the potential to introduce significant errors, up to 300%, in quantitative data, requiring the corresponding correction. Addressing matrix effects entails calibrating the instrument with standards comparable to the sample type.

Following correction for these effects, robust calibration curves are established, plotting measured intensities of each element against their concentrations across multiple standards. Subsequently, analysis of unknown samples involves reading off the calibration curve to ascertain the concentration of each element.

In this case study, the samples were composed of an indefinite variety of polymers and additives, difficult to determine in a practical, efficient, and economical manner. For this reason, no reference materials were available for each of the samples analysed, and consequently, no corresponding calibration curves were determined to minimize matrix effects. On the other hand, a calibration of the analyser was done (by the supplier of the equipment) using two polymeric reference materials: ERM³¹-EC680m and ERM-EC681m, made of low-density polyethylene, each with different concentrations of As, Br, Cd, Cl, Cr, Hg, Pb, S, Sb, Sn, Sn and Zn. Although this polymer was not found in the samples analysed, it is the reference material commercially available most similar to those studied. (Cesareo *et al.*, 2009; Bosco, 2013; Gallhofer and Lottermoser, 2018; Alghamdi, Abdallah and Harrad, 2022)

Sample preparation

The method selected for sample preparation in XRF analysis is relative to the nature of the samples and the elemental composition being determined. The preparation step is especially important due to the inherent matrix effects.

For instance, for geological samples, mainly two methods are employed: the creation of fusion discs and the fabrication of pressed pellets from powdered samples. The selection between these methods rests on the elements targeted for analysis and their expected concentrations. Regardless of the chosen method, initial milling of the sample into a fine powder is required for both reducing the particle size and ensuring sample homogenization, thus mitigating matrix effects. (Marguí, Queralt and De Almeida, 2022)

³¹ ERM: European Reference Material

For analysing samples different than geological (i.e., consumer products, paintings, pipelines, etc.), it is important to consider that when a material has undergone coating, painting, or any surface treatment, there exists the possibility of the analyser providing inaccurate identifications, misrepresenting the true nature of the sample. To ensure accurate identification of coated materials, it is recommended to grind an area slightly larger than the measurement window, effectively eliminating the surface treatment. The careful selection of appropriate grinding materials is crucial to prevent interference with subsequent analyses. While it may not be necessary to thoroughly clean and grind all materials, the removal of obvious metal dust is advised to maintain the integrity of the analytical process. ('Vanta Family X-Ray Fluorescence Analyzer. User's Manual (DMTA-10072-01EN-Rev.E)', 2019)

For the materials, products and methodology developed in this research project, either of these sample preparation methods were considered feasible except for dusting. The objective of the methodology developed is the measurement of the elements of interest directly from the surface of the plastic casing as recovered from the FPD dismantling line. It is important to consider that there might be an uneven dispersion of flame retardants within the sample which can impact XRF precision. Consequently, conducting repeated measurements across various areas of the sample surface can mitigate the influence of such heterogeneity.

Sample thickness

In XRF analysis, samples are considered of "infinite thickness" when their thickness largely exceeds the penetration depth of radiation. For very thin samples, typically less than a few micrometres, the XRF intensity is roughly proportional to the thickness of the sample since X-rays can pass through without significant attenuation and the fluorescence X-rays can escape with minimal absorption. Additionally, if the sample is too thin, it may not contain sufficient material to produce a strong XRF signal, leading to lower intensity and potentially less accurate results. In an intermediate thickness range, where the sample is thick enough to produce a strong signal but not so thick that self-absorption becomes significant, the relationship between XRF intensity and elemental concentration is most reliable. A recommended minimum sample thickness of 2 mm has been proposed to optimize accuracy in XRF analysis. Accurate results in this range often require careful calibration of the XRF instrument, considering the sample's thickness and the elements of interest.

For thicker samples, greater than a few millimetres, primary X-rays and fluorescent X-rays generated deeper within the sample can be absorbed by the material itself before reaching the detector, a phenomenon known as self-absorption. This reduces the intensity of detected X-rays, leading to lower apparent concentrations of elements and a non-linear response, making accurate quantification

challenging without complex corrections. Additionally, the presence of other elements within the sample matrix can interfere with XRF results. Heavier elements can absorb the fluorescence X-rays of lighter elements, and secondary fluorescence can occur when X-rays emitted by one element excite other elements, altering the detected intensities. To mitigate these issues, several approaches are employed, such as using calibration standards with known thicknesses and compositions similar to the samples being analysed, specialized thin film XRF analysis techniques for thin samples, and correction algorithms to account for self-absorption and matrix effects. Consistent sample preparation techniques are also crucial to minimize variability in sample thickness. Understanding and addressing the effects of sample thickness are essential for obtaining accurate and reliable XRF results. (Cesareo *et al.*, 2009; Alghamdi, Abdallah and Harrad, 2022; Sharkey *et al.*, 2022)

XRF applicability and Hand-held XRF (h-XRF)

Although XRF exhibits lower sensitivity compared to atomic spectrometry methods like ICP-AES (Inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy) and ICP-MS (Inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy), it has significant advantages, including minimal sample preparation, quick analysis times, detection of multiple elements, and suitability for field use via handheld analysers.

XRF delivers analysis times as short as a minute or less, with estimated throughput reaching approximately 60 samples per hour using handheld devices operable by non-experts. It is important to consider that the accuracy of XRF measurements may be hindered by short measuring times. Ensuring sufficient testing durations, extending up to 30 seconds, can reduce reading errors by 4–8%. (Aldrian, Ledersteger and Pomberger, 2015)

While laboratory-grade XRF instruments have been in existence since the early 1960s, progressive advancements in hardware and software over the past decade have significantly facilitated the development of portable devices. In early 2010's XRF was mainly used for analysing and identifying alloys (70%), minerals (9%), and screening consumer products such as toys and electronics for compliance. However, the remarkable impact of h-XRF in screening soil contamination stands out. XRF has gained such widespread acceptance that both the RoHS and the WEEE Directives in the EU, provide protocols for utilizing h-XRF for screening purposes and ensuring compliance.

Nonetheless, several studies have revealed that employing portable XRF for regulatory compliance screening remains an imperfect approach. For instance, accurately quantifying elemental bromine in plastic materials poses challenges, partly attributed to primary and secondary X-ray attenuation in low-

density matrices (such as hard plastics and textiles), as well as the presence of additional air in expanded materials (like insulation and cushioning foams). (Sharkey *et al.*, 2022)

Most h-XRF analysers use energy dispersive rather than wavelength dispersive technology. A digital pulse processor is employed to monitor both the energy and the rate of arrival of X-Rays. Composition data, including the elements detected, their relative concentrations, and associated uncertainties, are promptly displayed on the screen of the instrument, providing near real-time results. These analysers are powered by batteries and can typically operate for several hours without needing recharging. (Palmer *et al.*, 2006)

The advantages of XRF extend to h-XRF instruments, making them rapid, user-friendly, cost-effective compared to alternative methods, and importantly, non-destructive. However, there are constraints related to sample size, as optimal XRF analysis typically requires samples larger than 10 mm in the smallest dimension and thicker than 2 mm. While h-XRF instruments can now analyse samples as small as about 2 mm, accuracy decreases accordingly. (Shackley, 2012)

Another significant restraint relates to the incapacity of XRF screening to determine the chemical form of detected elements. In the case of Bromine determination as tracer for BFRs, since Laboratory Proficiency Control Levels (LPCLs) exclusively encompass specific brominated compounds, the presence of an unregulated BFR leads to "false exceedance." Consequently, the material is erroneously labelled as hazardous concerning POPs content.

In the context of false exceedances, it's crucial to note that, as previously mentioned, Sb_2O_3 is commonly utilized alongside POPs-BFRs to enhance flame retardancy, thus serving as a synergistic agent for these flame retardants. Consequently, simultaneous measurement of Sb and Br concentrations in WEEE samples, where the Br concentration indicates surpassing LPCLs at ratios ranging from approximately 1:2 to 1:4, would offer evidence that the detected Br is related to the presence of PBDEs, confirming the validity of the exceedance (Alghamdi, Abdallah and Harrad, 2022).

Safety considerations

In the UK the use of X-Rays and radioactive materials is regulated by the (*The Ionising Radiations Regulations 2017*, 2018). Users are required to consult their safety officers and review relevant actions for compliance. When operated correctly, typical exposures from an XRF analyser remain considerably lower than those from typical background sources. Nonetheless, such equipment requires licensing, and analysts should adhere to the principle of ALARA (As Low As Reasonably Achievable) in their operation, striving to minimize human exposure to X-Rays.(Palmer *et al.*, 2006)

Scattering may occur during analysis when the X-Ray photons interact with electrons. This poses a challenge when determining the elemental composition of a sample, while also producing secondary radiation that may be a potential risk to the user, as radiation is emitted in all directions from within the sample. Thus, the intensity of X-Ray scatter varies during the measurement of various materials.

The composition of the sample matrix significantly impacts the radiation intensity surrounding the h-XRF spectrometers. A study comparing scattered radiation of Steel, Sand and Polyethylene (PE) showed that the latter was the material that most strongly scattered radiation, showing that low density materials enhance scattering around the spectrometer as the penetration depth of the X-Ray photons increases. In fact, it was demonstrated that PE scattered radiation so efficiently that radiation coming from the analyser was detected up to 4 meters away from the source. (Rouillon, Kristensen and Gore, 2015)

Although radiation exposure related to h-XRF devices is relatively low, it must be justified. All exposures should be optimized and kept as low as reasonably achievable by minimizing exposure times, maximizing the distance to the radiation source and implementing shielding where necessary. h-XRF operators may consider using test stands in the laboratory or employing shielding options when measuring lightweight materials like plastics. Furthermore, it is important to recognize that each measurement scenario is potentially unique, and the resulting dose rates would consequently vary.

Olympus, the supplier of the Vanta™ h-XRF analyser used for this research, advises organizations employing this equipment to establish a comprehensive radiation safety program comprising:

- Monitoring the radiation dose of key personnel.
- Surveillance of radiation levels in the surrounding areas.
- Provision of site-specific and application-specific information regarding the XRF system.
- Conducting an annual review and updating the program as needed.

Regarding shielding concerns, the Vanta emits a tightly collimated X-Ray beam. Despite attenuation, the beam trajectory may extend over several meters through open air. To ensure adequate shielding, it is essential to enclose working area of the beam with protective panels.

Appendix 4. State of the art of WEEE plastics treatment

The most suitable recycling approach for any plastic waste stream largely depends on the polymer matrix composition and its contaminants such as flame retardants. Recycling methods including depolymerization, pyrolysis, gasification, and dissolution, offer a viable solution for handling mixed waste streams containing flame retarded plastics. In Europe, investments adding up to 7.2 billion euros are planned for chemical recycling plants by 2030, with recycled plastics production anticipated to surge to 3.4 Mt. (Bifulco *et al.*, 2024)

Among the most popular treatment methods chemical recycling emerges as the most favourable approach comprising the transformation of plastic waste materials into lower molecular weight products. It includes two primary processes: solvolysis and thermolysis. Solvolysis involves dissolving polymers in a solvent and treating them with or without catalysts and initiators. It can also serve as a preliminary step before thermo-chemical processes like pyrolysis. Thermolysis, on the other hand, entails heating polymers in an inert atmosphere, such as nitrogen, in the absence of air, oxygen, or vacuum. It encompasses various processes, including pyrolysis (both thermal and catalytic), gasification, and hydrogenation.

Pyrolysis stands as an environmentally sustainable and economically viable technique, aiming to recover monomers or valuable chemicals suitable for subsequent use as fuels or chemical feedstock in the production of new items (Charitopoulou, Lappas and Achilias, 2023; Mtibe, Mokhena and John, 2023; Santo Stefano *et al.*, 2024). While predominantly applied on a laboratory scale due to considerable energy requirements, it is regarded as a significant advancement in end-of-life plastics management. However, these gaseous, liquid, and solid fuels produced in this process often carry bromine contamination (preferentially found in gases) originating from flame retardants initially present in the plastic. Such contamination poses challenges and a promising approach to address this issue involves catalytic upgrading of pyrolysis vapours through a secondary stage of vapor-phase cracking. Essentially, this technique consists of the exposure of vapours exiting a pyrolysis process to a heated fixed bed containing a porous catalyst. (De Freitas Costa *et al.*, 2023; López *et al.*, 2024)

Appendix 5. Analysis conditions: Health and Safety protection measures

To ensure the safety of the h-XRF operator and those passing by or working in adjoining rooms, radiation exposure measurements were taken during the analysis time of the samples using TRACERCO™ X-Ray Monitor. As the density of plastic is low from the radiation point of view, and materials of low thickness were used, a high level of scatter was detected. Understanding that this scattered radiation could in time negatively affect the operator, it was decided to develop a remote operation system.

For this purpose, an analysis station was constructed consisting of 4 walls lined with leaded sheets encasing a stand and a table. The h-XRF analyser was placed on a stand and remotely operated using the Vanta™ Desktop App placing the window of the analyser directly on the surface of the plastic. This allowed for triplicate analysis of each point to be performed without moving the analyser and analysing the exact same point on the sample, generating consistent replicates (see **Figure A.5.1**).

Figure A.5.1 FPD plastic casing being analysed with the remotely operated VANTA™ handheld XRF Analyser

Appendix 6. Additional steps taken for methodology development

h-XRF analysis conditions (sample placement)

i. Aim

Using certified reference material (BAM H010) ABS discs of 1mm, 2mm and 6mm determine the error related to the how the sample is measured relative to its positing being directly placed on the testing table or leaving an air gap behind the table.

This will demonstrate whether the fact that the thickness of the samples is similar to (and in many cases less than) the critical thickness, affects the analysis results by integrating the material directly behind the sample into the measurement.

ii. Materials and Methods

Br concentrations were determined in BAM H010 ABS discs of different thicknesses comprising 1mm, 2mm, and 6mm.

Table A.6.1 BAM H010 ABS discs certified concentrations

Element	Mass fraction in mg/g	Uncertainty U* in mg/g
Lead	479	17
Bromine	240	21
Cadmium	93	5
Chromium	470	36

As at this point the optimal testing time had not been determined, in all cases the samples were analysed for different times (50s, 30s, 20s, 15s and 10s) in order to determine the error associated to test time.

Samples were tested in two different settings:

- Placed directly on PMMA table (Thickness: 3cm)
- Placed on a stand allowing the disc to have over 6cm of air behind it, representing the scenario of analysing the exterior surface of a whole FPD casing.

Figure A.6.1 h-XRF analysis setting (air gap behind the sample)

The percentual error in Br concentration measured ($[Br]_{error}$) was determined as:

Equation A.6.1

$$[Br]_{error} (\%) = \frac{[Br], \text{median (mg/kg)} - [Br], \text{CRM (mg/kg)}}{[Br], \text{CRM (mg/kg)}} \times 100$$

iii. Results

Table A.6.2 and Table A.6.3 present the h-XRF analysis results and error calculation results considering a reference Br concentration of 240 mg/kg. The concentrations presented are medians determined from measuring each disc in triplicate for each analysis time.

Table A.6.2 Results for Br measured with h-XRF and sample placed directly on table

<i>Analysis time</i>	50s	30s	20s	15s	10s
Thickness	Br, median (mg/kg)				
1mm	240	240	240	245	245
2mm	240	243	243	243	243
6mm	241	241	241	241	241
Thickness	Br, error (%)				
1mm	0	0	0	1.9	1.9
2mm	0	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1
6mm	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6

Table A.6.3 Results for Br measured with h-XRF and sample placed on stand (air behind disc)

<i>Analysis time</i>	50s	30s	20s	15s	10s
Thickness	Br, median (mg/kg)				
1mm	242	242	242	243	243
2mm	241	242	242	242	243
6mm	241	241	241	242	242
Thickness	Br, error (%)				
1mm	0.8	0.8	0.8	1.2	1.2
2mm	0.4	0.8	0.8	0.8	1.1
6mm	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.8	0.8

iv. Conclusion

Although the thickness of two analysed discs (1 mm and 2 mm) is below the critical thickness for h-XRF polymer measurement (2 mm), the associated measurement error remains consistent under different conditions. Specifically, placing the disc directly on a material like PMMA, which could potentially provide additional thickness for beam penetration, does not significantly alter the error compared to measurements taken with an air gap behind the sample. In both scenarios, the error remains below 2%, with its maximum observed during analysis times of 15 seconds or less. This level of error is acceptable in industrial processes, particularly since the error in h-XRF measurements is expected to decrease with increasing bromine concentration. For the defined concentration limit of 820 mg/kg, the error becomes negligible.

h-XRF analysis: FPD sampling for Br/Sb analysis

i. Aim

The aim of this study is to determine the representativeness for Br and Sb of the casing by each surface (exterior and interior)

ii. Materials and methods

In this report the word “sample” is used to describe whole TVs (front and back casings as one single item). The word “sub-sample” is used to describe either front or back casings.

The samples were analysed as follows:

- Back casing: 5 points (Top left, Top right, Bottom left, Bottom right, Centre) on the outer and inner surface were tested.
- Front casing: 4 points (Top left, Top right, Bottom left, Bottom right) were tested on the outer and inner surface, as far as the sub-sample geometry allowed it.

Each individual point was measured in triplicate to ensure the reproducibility of the measurement, amounting to a total of 18 points tested and 54 tests performed per sample.

The concentration of each individual point was determined by calculating the median of the three testing results. Thus, the $[\text{Br}]_{\text{median}}$ and $[\text{Sb}]_{\text{median}}$ were determined for each testing point as follows:

Table A.6.4 Areas analysed by h-XRF in both back and front casings of each FPD sampled

ITEM	SIDE	
	INTERIOR	EXTERIOR
Back casing		Top Right
		Top Left
		Bottom Right
		Bottom Left
		Centre
Front casing		Top Right
		Top Left
		Bottom Right
		Bottom Left

Homogeneity of Br and Sb within each casing (comparing internal and external concentrations)

To evaluate the homogeneity in the distribution of Br in each sub-sample the following parameter was considered:

Equation A.6.2

$$\% \text{ of Ext/Int Difference} = \left| \frac{\text{Average [Br], ext} - \text{Average [Br], int}}{\text{Average [Br], sub - sample}} \right| \times 100$$

For this parameter a maximum of 10% was defined as acceptable.

iii. Results and Discussion

▪ **Back casings**

Results for Br

A total of 144 casing sides were tested, corresponding to 72 FPDs. Among these, 20 sub-samples showed a percentile difference of 10% or more between the exterior and interior median bromine (Br) concentrations. Two samples (210614.08 and 210616.05) exhibited Br concentrations exceeding 820 mg/kg and 2,000 mg/kg, respectively. For the remaining samples, the error percentage did not indicate that Br concentrations could surpass 820 mg/kg. Therefore, analysing only one side of the sub-sample would not have resulted in a non-recyclable item being misclassified as recyclable.

Results for Sb

For 3 sub-samples, there was a percentile difference between exterior and interior median Sb concentrations greater than 10%. Sb concentrations for these sub-samples were either considerably higher or lower than 8,400 mg/kg. See **Table A.6.5**.

Table A.6.5 Results for samples with Sb concentration differences greater than 10% between interior and exterior surfaces of the back casing

Sample No.	Casing/Back	Internal/External	[Sb] average per side (mg/kg)	Ext/Int diff (%)
210614.08	Back	External	18,895	12
210614.08	Back	Internal	16,753	
210616.05	Back	External	4,307	32
210616.05	Back	Internal	3,123	
210622.04	Back	External	129	20
210622.04	Back	Internal	105	

Analysis results are presented in **Supplementary information**.

- **Front casings**

Results for Br

A total of 39 subsamples were analysed in both the interior and exterior surfaces. Additionally, in 29 cases, only the exterior surface could be analysed due to the interior geometry of the sub-sample, preventing measurement on the interior side. As a result, the analysis parameter could not be determined for these cases. For 18 sub-samples, the percentile difference between exterior and interior median Br concentrations was 10% or greater. Among these, seven sub-samples had Br concentrations exceeding 820 mg/kg, and two exceeded 2,000 mg/kg. In two samples, misclassification could have occurred, with non-recyclable items potentially being identified as recyclable (false negatives) if only one side had been analysed (see **Table A.6.6**).

Table A.6.6 Results for samples with Br concentration differences greater than 10% between interior and exterior surfaces of the back casing

Sample No.	Internal/External	[Br] average per side (mg/kg)	Ext/Int difference (%)
210621.09	External	832	48
210621.09	Internal	474	
210621.11	External	1	200
210621.11	Internal	876	

Results for Sb

For 5 samples, Sb concentrations for these samples were either considerably higher or lower than 8,400ppm, however, on the external surface of the front casing of sample 210614.08 a Sb concentration almost 5 times lower than that of the interior surface was determined. See table below.

Table A.6.7 Results for samples with Sb concentration differences greater than 10% between interior and exterior surfaces of the front casing

Sample No.	Internal/External	[Sb] average per side (mg/kg)	Ext/Int difference (%)
210614.08	External	3,871	130
210614.08	Internal	18,384	

Analysis results are presented in **Supplementary information**.

iv. Conclusions

The exterior and interior surfaces of both back and front casings were tested according to the established testing plan, with a 10% threshold defined as acceptable for all evaluated parameters. The analysis focused on determining whether both sides of each sub-sample (casing) needed to be tested. For bromine (Br) concentrations in back casings, testing only one side was deemed sufficient, as no false negative classification of non-recyclable items as recyclable would have occurred under this approach. However, for front casings, testing only one side would have resulted in two sub-samples being misclassified as recyclable. From the 72 front casings tested, two could have been incorrectly classified as recyclable waste. Extrapolated to a daily throughput of 1,000 FPDs, this could translate to 30 back casings and two front casings being misclassified if only one side was analysed for Br concentration. Thus, while testing one side may suffice for back casings, it is not reliable for front casings.

A similar trend was observed for Sb concentrations in back casings, where testing one side could also be considered sufficient. However, for front casings, a significant difference between interior and exterior Sb concentrations was identified in one sample (210614.08). This suggests that if only one side were tested, up to 15 front casings could be misclassified as recyclable waste in a daily throughput of 1,000 FPDs (1.5%).

No consistent tendency was observed for either Br or Sb concentrations to be higher on the interior or exterior surfaces.

Supplementary information

h-XRF bromine and antimony results for back casings

Sample No.	Surface	[Br] average per side (mg/kg)	[Br] Ext/Int diff. (%)	[Sb] average per side (mg/kg)	[Sb] Ext/Int diff. (%)
210614.01	External	24		0	
210614.01	Internal	23	5	0	0
210614.02	External	48		169	
210614.02	Internal	46	4	154	10
210614.03	External	0		0	
210614.03	Internal	0	67	0	0
210614.04	External	56		0	
210614.04	Internal	55	2	0	0
210614.05	External	5		0	
210614.05	Internal	5	0	0	0
210614.06	External	385		59	
210614.06	Internal	374	3	54	8
210614.07	External	1		0	
210614.07	Internal	0	100	0	0
210614.08	External	111,141		18,895	
210614.08	Internal	99,643	11	16,753	12
210614.09	External	87		0	
210614.09	Internal	86	2	0	0
210614.10	External	44		0	
210614.10	Internal	36	20	0	0
210614.11	External	63,362		10,820	
210614.11	Internal	61,425	3	11,327	5
210614.12	External	8		0	
210614.12	Internal	8	10	0	0
210615.01	External	0		0	
210615.01	Internal	0	ND	0	0
210615.02	External	143,514		29,551	
210615.02	Internal	145,628	1	30,073	2
210615.03	External	1		0	
210615.03	Internal	1	50	0	0
210615.04	External	357		87	
210615.04	Internal	360	1	92	5
210615.05	External	284		85	
210615.05	Internal	289	2	85	0
210615.06	External	0		0	
210615.06	Internal	0	ND	0	0
210616.01	External	0		0	
210616.01	Internal	0	200	0	0
210616.02	External	51,218		8,490	
210616.02	Internal	49,702	3	8,187	4
210616.03	External	137		0	
210616.03	Internal	138	1	15	0

Sample No.	Surface	[Br] average per side (mg/kg)	[Br] Ext/Int diff. (%)	[Sb] average per side (mg/kg)	[Sb] Ext/Int diff. (%)
210616.04	External	0	0	0	0
210616.04	Internal	0		0	
210616.05	External	24,662	29	4,307	32
210616.05	Internal	18,443		3,123	
210616.06	External	1	67	0	0
210616.06	Internal	0		0	
210616.07	External	0	0	0	0
210616.07	Internal	0		0	
210616.08	External	9	0	176	2
210616.08	Internal	9		179	
210616.09	External	93,811	1	27,836	1
210616.09	Internal	94,518		28,031	
210616.10	External	61	4	0	0
210616.10	Internal	58		0	
210616.11	External	224	2	126	6
210616.11	Internal	219		119	
210616.12	External	0	0	0	0
210616.12	Internal	0		0	
210621.01	External	35	2	0	ND
210621.01	Internal	36		0	
210621.02	External	87	17	0	0
210621.02	Internal	73		0	
210621.03	External	0	200	0	0
210621.03	Internal	1		0	
210621.04	External	0	0	0	0
210621.04	Internal	0		0	
210621.05	External	4	142	0	0
210621.05	Internal	24		8	
210621.06	External	107,988	2	28,810	2
210621.06	Internal	105,657		28,145	
210621.07	External	521	2	126	3
210621.07	Internal	529		123	
210621.08	External	0	200	0	0
210621.08	Internal	0		0	
210621.09	External	1,563	3	311	4
210621.09	Internal	1,517		298	
210621.10	External	70	2	0	0
210621.10	Internal	71		0	
210621.11	External	30	7	0	0
210621.11	Internal	28		0	
210621.12	External	91,860	1	17,691	1
210621.12	Internal	91,098		17,455	
210413.05	External	0	ND	54	7
210413.05	Internal	0		51	
210413.15	External	0	200	0	0
210413.15	Internal	0		0	

Sample No.	Surface	[Br] average per side (mg/kg)	[Br] Ext/Int diff. (%)	[Sb] average per side (mg/kg)	[Sb] Ext/Int diff. (%)
210506.02	External	1	133	0	0
210506.02	Internal	0		0	
210506.12	External	13	71	0	0
210506.12	Internal	6		0	
210622.01	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210622.01	Internal	ND		ND	
210622.02	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210622.02	Internal	ND		ND	
210622.03	External	87	4	ND	ND
210622.03	Internal	83		ND	
210622.04	External	ND	ND	129	20
210622.04	Internal	ND		105	
210622.05	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210622.05	Internal	ND		ND	
210622.06	External	120,425	1	29,642	0
210622.06	Internal	121,217		29,742	
210622.07	External	3,044	6	477	7
210622.07	Internal	2,869		446	
210622.08	External	27	10	ND	ND
210622.08	Internal	30		ND	
210622.09	External	133	0	ND	ND
210622.09	Internal	133		ND	
210622.10	External	23,895	2	6,249	2
210622.10	Internal	24,348		6,379	
210622.11	External	1	0	ND	ND
210622.11	Internal	1		ND	
210622.12	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210622.12	Internal	ND		ND	
210628.01	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210628.01	Internal	ND		ND	
210628.02	External	4	120	53	ND
210628.02	Internal	1		ND	
210628.03	External	6	105	ND	ND
210628.03	Internal	2		ND	
210628.04	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210628.04	Internal	ND		ND	
210628.05	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210628.05	Internal	3		ND	
210628.06	External	17	74	ND	ND
210628.06	Internal	8		ND	
210628.07	External	109,606	1	34,194	1
210628.07	Internal	110,631		34,441	
210628.08	External	1,487	0	345	2
210628.08	Internal	1,489		339	
210628.09	External	109	2	ND	ND
210628.09	Internal	107		ND	

Sample No.	Surface	[Br] average per side (mg/kg)	[Br] Ext/Int diff. (%)	[Sb] average per side (mg/kg)	[Sb] Ext/Int diff. (%)
210628.10	External	62,484	0	8,551	1
210628.10	Internal	62,222		8,487	
210628.11	External	100,927	1	21,201	1
210628.11	Internal	100,282		20,990	
210628.12	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210628.12	Internal	ND		ND	
210628.13	External	117,303	3	30,219	3
210628.13	Internal	114,303		29,358	
210628.14	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210628.14	Internal	ND		ND	

h-XRF bromine and antimony results for front casings

Sample No.	Surface	[Br] average per side (mg/kg)	[Br] Ext/Int diff. (%)	[Sb] average per side (mg/kg)	[Sb] Ext/Int diff. (%)
210614.01	External	5	-	ND	ND
210614.01	Internal	-	-	-	-
210614.02	External	732	-	263	3
210614.02	Internal	-	-	-	-
210614.03	External	956	30	ND	ND
210614.03	Internal	704		ND	
210614.04	External	113,429	1	22,778	2.9
210614.04	Internal	111,931		22,129	
210614.05	External	11	73	ND	ND
210614.05	Internal	5		ND	
210614.06	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210614.06	Internal	ND		ND	
210614.07	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210614.07	Internal	ND		ND	
210614.08	External	13,129	155	3,871	130
210614.08	Internal	104,363		18,384	
210614.09	External	ND	-	ND	ND
210614.09	External	-	-	-	-
210614.10	External	341	54	79	50.2
210614.10	Internal	197		47	
210614.11	External	10	-	ND	-
210614.11	Internal	-	-	-	-
210614.12	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210614.12	Internal	-	-	-	-
210615.01	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210615.01	Internal	ND		ND	
210615.02	External	13	60	ND	ND
210615.02	Internal	7		ND	
210615.03	External	ND	ND	67	ND
210615.03	Internal	ND		ND	
210615.04	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210615.04	Internal	ND		ND	
210615.05	External	2	ND	ND	ND
210615.05	Internal	ND		ND	
210615.06	External	2	ND	ND	ND
210615.06	Internal	ND		ND	
210616.01	External	1	-	ND	ND
210616.01	Internal	-	-	-	-
210616.02	External	111,788	-	22,378	0
210616.02	Internal	-	-	-	-
210616.03	External	11	-	ND	ND
210616.03	Internal	-	-	-	-
210616.04	External	1	-	ND	ND
210616.04	Internal	-	-	-	-

Sample No.	Surface	[Br] average per side (mg/kg)	[Br] Ext/Int diff. (%)	[Sb] average per side (mg/kg)	[Sb] Ext/Int diff. (%)
210616.05	External	32,925		5,989	0
210616.05	Internal	-	-	-	-
210616.06	External	1	ND	ND	ND
210616.06	Internal	ND		ND	
210616.07	External	2	67	ND	ND
210616.07	Internal	1		ND	
210616.08	External	33	-	58	0
210616.08	Internal	-	-	-	-
210616.09	External	11,897	144	6,219	116
210616.09	Internal	73,302		23,435	
210616.11	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210616.11	Internal	ND		ND	
210616.12	External	33,311	66	ND	ND
210616.12	Internal	16,850		ND	
210621.01	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210621.01	Internal	-	-	-	-
210621.02	External	283	0	60	0
210621.02	Internal	-	-	-	-
210621.03	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210621.03	Internal	-	-	-	-
210621.04	External	9	0	ND	ND
210621.04	Internal	-	-	-	-
210621.05	External	ND	ND	113	0
210621.05	Internal	-	-	-	-
210621.07	External	64	71	ND	ND
210621.07	Internal	31		ND	
210621.08	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210621.08	Internal	ND		ND	
210621.09	External	776	48	165	52
210621.09	Internal	474		97	
210621.10	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210621.10	Internal	ND		ND	
210621.11	External	1	200	ND	ND
210621.11	Internal	876		128	
210621.12	External	98,984	1.1	19,154	0.08
210621.12	Internal	97,896		19,170	
210622.01	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210622.01	Internal	ND		ND	
210622.02	External	1	0	ND	ND
210622.02	Internal	-	-	-	-
210622.03	External	32	31	ND	ND
210622.03	Internal	24		ND	
210622.04	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210622.04	Internal	-	-	-	-
210622.05	External	98	0	ND	ND
210622.05	Internal	-	-	-	-

Sample No.	Surface	[Br] average per side (mg/kg)	[Br] Ext/Int diff. (%)	[Sb] average per side (mg/kg)	[Sb] Ext/Int diff. (%)
210622.06	External	104,133	5	28,038	0.5
210622.06	Internal	99,069		27,906	
210622.07	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210622.07	Internal	ND		ND	
210622.08	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210622.08	Internal	ND		ND	
210622.09	External	11	63	ND	ND
210622.09	Internal	6		ND	
210622.10	External	1	ND	ND	ND
210622.10	Internal	ND		ND	
210622.11	External	1	ND	ND	ND
210622.11	Internal	ND		ND	
210622.12	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210622.12	Internal	ND		ND	
210413.15	External	ND	ND	82	0
210413.15	Internal	-	-	-	-
210506.02	External	1	0	ND	ND
210506.02	Internal	-	-	-	-
210506.12	External	36	0	ND	ND
210506.12	Internal	-	-	-	-
210413.05	External	ND	ND	107	61
210413.05	Internal	ND		57	
210628.01	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210628.01	Internal	-	-	-	-
210628.02	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210628.02	Internal	-	-	-	-
210628.03	External	3	0	ND	ND
210628.03	Internal	-	-	-	-
210628.04	External	37	0	ND	ND
210628.04	Internal	-	-	-	-
210628.05	External	15	0	ND	ND
210628.05	Internal	-	-	-	-
210628.06	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210628.06	Internal	-	-	-	-
210628.07	External	51	59	ND	ND
210628.07	Internal	28		ND	
210628.08	External	106,668	0	29,584	0
210628.08	Internal	-	-	-	-
210628.09	External	8	0	ND	ND
210628.09	Internal	-	-	-	-
210628.12	External	1	200	ND	ND
210628.12	Internal	0		0	
210628.13	External	16	50	ND	ND
210628.13	Internal	10		ND	
210628.14	External	ND	ND	ND	ND
210628.14	Internal	ND		ND	